

EVALUATION OF SERVICE QUALITY AND PATIENT SATISFACTION IN EASTERN NEPALESE HOSPITALS

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I hereby declare that this thesis and the work done is fully conducted by myself. I have not submitted this any part of thesis to other educational degree or comparable academic award to any other institution. It is my original research. I have clearly acknowledged the source and attributed, where I have consulted the published work.

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Date: 21/02/2021

Abstract

Service quality and customer satisfaction have become vital indicators of the success of business in today's competitive market. Emphasis on service quality in the health care industry has increased lately due to a growing concern for health and well-being. As such, it is important for health care sectors to provide quality services to meet the expectations and needs of customers. Therefore, measuring service quality is important to identify customer satisfaction and experiences of service.

The aim of this research is to evaluate service quality and patient satisfaction in Nepalese hospitals. The health care industry is one of the fastest growing industries in the service sector. Services that are delivered in hospitals are similar in nature, but their quality varies from hospital to hospital. In Nepal, the hospital industry continues to expand, and promises are made regularly to provide better services. This study focussed on the east of the country where there are more than 150 hospitals. In particular, Koshi zonal hospital and Birat Nursing home were examined using various service models. The literature review chapter introduces a number of models, including SERVQUAL, which are used to measure service quality. The literature also focuses on the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction, and it examines customer repurchase intentions.

Qualitative research methods were used to conduct the research. The fieldwork for this research was conducted in two hospitals in Nepal, where interviews were performed using a semi-structured, in-depth approach to gain a profound knowledge of the research topic. Meetings were conducted with fewer than 35 participants who had experienced service in these hospitals. The study identifies a gap between service expectations and the needs of the patients. Finally, the study results in the generation of the conceptual model titled "ECET". This model measures customer perceptions of service quality and the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction. Lastly, the study produces a few recommendations which hospitals could follow in future to provide quality services to patients and to improve customer satisfaction. The model provides identifies opportunities for future research.

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1 CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

This chapter introduces the concepts of service quality, customer satisfaction and consumer purchase intentions, and it sets out the connections between them. Service quality and customer satisfaction have become key requirements for businesses to succeed in competitive markets. As such, several researchers have looked at this topic over the last two decades (Pantouvakis & Bouranta, 2014). The main purpose of conducting this study is to identify the key dimensions of service quality for hospitals service quality, and the relationship between service quality, customer satisfaction and purchase intentions in the context of Nepalese Hospitals. The research harnesses these variables to measure the quality of services and customer satisfaction in health care centres.

The external business environment has become more competitive and unstable due to various external PESTEL (political, economic, social, technological, environment and legal) factors. Therefore, to improve performance and compete in the marketplace, organisations must focus on developing a culture that embraces ethics. The level of service provided to customers must also achieve a high rate of satisfaction (Kuo, et al., 2009). Service is characterized by intangibility, perishability, inseparability and variability (Zeithmal, et al., 2013). Service providers and service receivers should consider the exclusive and different attributes of service while trying to identify service quality (Kotler & Keller, 2009) .

The term “service quality” was first described by Parasuraman, Zeithmal & Berry (1988, p.16) as “*a global judgement or attribute relating to the superiority of service*”. Since customers always expect a high level of service, providers must fulfil expectations by delivering quality service. Delivering expected levels of service quality can help organisations to create a brand image amongst customers that can help to increase their competitive advantage (Negi, 2009).

Customer satisfaction can be achieved by understanding the needs, expectations, and behaviours of customers. Companies have started creating strategies to address the requirements of customers, and to identify their expectations in order to design responsive services (Kuo, et al., 2009). Solomon (2011, p37) defines customer behaviour as “*the science of consumer behaviour is defined as the study of individuals, group or organisation, and the process they use to select, secure, use and dispose of products, services, experiences, or ideas to satisfy needs, and the impact of these processes on consumers, organisations and society.*”

Researchers suggest that consumer behaviour can affect managerial decision making in both services and manufacturing contexts. Customer satisfaction is generally based on perspectives of services, rather than the reality of service. Factors like the quality of the product, customer service, trust, reliability, brand image and the culture of the organisation can all influence the attitude of customers internally and externally (Kotler & Keller, 2009). It is challenging for service providers to understand the perspectives of customers. Researchers have explored this area in the past (Oliver, 1993). Providing a higher level of service quality has a significant influence on the competitive advantage of the organisation that seeks to provide customer satisfaction and retain customers and market share. Increasing market share can improve profitability (Al-Neyadi, et al., 2016). As such, organisations should focus on quality products and maintain high standards of service quality to sustain themselves in the market.

1.1 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Service quality has become a primary objective of service providers seeking to match customer expectations and needs with excellent service. To achieve this objective, providers must understand customer evaluations of service quality and their perceptions of products. Service providers must understand how customers evaluate the quality of their service offerings, and how they choose between organisations. There is also a need to understand customer loyalty (Pantouvakis & Bouranta, 2014)

Previous authors, Zeithmal, et al., 2009, p77 suggest that “*the main objective of any service provider is to develop and provide offerings that would satisfy the needs and expectations of consumers*”. Similarly, Kotler (2009) mentioned if the expectations of the customers are met and exceeded the satisfaction rate of customer will be high. To achieve their objectives, (Kumar, et al., 2009) service firms should establish a strategy which can measure corporate performance as well as customer satisfaction over time.

Zeithmal, et al., (2009), p77 argue that “*...a sound measure of service quality is necessary for identifying aspects of service needing performance improvement, and also examining the amount of improvement needed in every aspect of the service offering.*” Since service is defined by intangibility, inseparability, perishability, and variability, service providers have increasingly struggled to understand service (Boetsch, et al., 2011). Therefore, both service providers and service researcher must understand the unique nature of service to address the various issues related to service quality (Mosadeghrad, 2013). Customers always expect high

quality and superior service from providers. It is therefore increasingly incumbent on service providers to fulfil their requirements. Therefore, delivering excellent service helps organisations to gain recognition and enhance their brand image. These advantages make a positive contribution to customer value and loyalty

Like service quality, customer satisfaction has also been identified as a vital factor for businesses seeking to survive in competitive markets (Chakravarty, 2010). Customer satisfaction can be defined as the interpretation of service by service users in terms of their expectations, and the actual performance of the service (Lee & Lee, 2011). It has been argued (Dortyol, et al., 2014) that when customer expectations are met by service providers, they become satisfied. Likewise, if the required standard of service is not met, customers are dissatisfied. Other authors (Andaleeb & Conway, 2006) argue that satisfaction levels vary between customers, and satisfaction can be evaluated based on individual perceptions. Customer values are effectively the outcome of a comparison that is made regarding the fulfilment of the customer's needs after encountering service (Palmatier, et al., 2007).

Nepal is a small country located between India and China. It is one of the least developed countries in the world and offers an overall poor level of health care services. People living in rural areas are uneducated, and the hospitals in those areas are often understaffed and undersupplied with infrastructure. Due to its status as the least developed country, it has been unable to establish a universally accessible system of health care. More than 90 per cent of people must access expensive private health care in Nepal (Paudel, 2009).

According to CBS (2011), the total population of Nepal is approximately 26.49 million, and given the current level of political turbulence, the country has recently changed its title to the Federal Democratic Republic of Nepal, comprising seven states. Topographically, Nepal is divided into 3 regions. The area of flat land is known as the Terai and this is located in the Southern part of the country, bordering India. The 'hill' region is the central part of Nepal, and it is covered with the mountains. Lastly, the snowy mountain in the north borders Tibet and China (World Atlas, 2018).

The changing demography in Nepal has resulted in an overall increase in health care services. Kathmandu, the capital of Nepal has witnessed significant economic development over recent years. In the context of Nepalese health care, hospital management and skills development

have not been a government priority for some time. Although there are various policies and guidelines for government, hospital management has suffered as a result of bureaucratic systems and political instability. Shrestha, Vaidya & Bajracharya (2011) state that most hospitals and diagnostic services are centred in the capital and major cities. Therefore, rural populations have significantly less access to healthcare. The healthcare infrastructure in Nepal is inadequate and compares unfavourably against most global averages.

The first modern medical services started with the establishment of Bir hospital in 1889. Until then, the country tended to rely on traditional systems to diagnose and prevent illness. Some rural areas without access to healthcare services still depend on rituals. Due to low literacy rates, people still believe that some diseases are caused by supernatural powers. Although the government has banned traditional medical practices due to the lack of availability and the lack of education, such practices remain popular. Most people prefer to search for traditional remedies such as Ayurveda, Siddha, and meditation, especially in rural areas. Beliefs about health and seeking treatment can adversely affect healthcare provision and the use of medicines to treat illness (Paudel, 2009).

According to CBS (2011) the health care system in Nepal is regulated by the Ministry of Health and Population (MOHP). The MOHP is responsible for making policies, planning hospital, financing, organising human resources, and monitoring and evaluating hospital services. Hospitals are typically designated as either public, private or NGO (Non-governmental organisation). Public hospitals are directly regulated by government. Private hospitals are run by private organisations or individuals, and they must be licensed by the MOHP. NGO hospitals are run by non-profit organisations as a part of social service strategies for communities (Paudel,2009).

This study was conducted in a district called Morang (Fig 2), which is situated in the eastern region of Nepal. The selection of this district was based on its ease of access to the researcher. Due to the lack of availability of public transport, travelling was a major concern during the gathering of data. The researcher chose two hospitals in this region. The first was a government hospital called Koshi Zonal Hospital which is one of the oldest government hospitals in Nepal. Zonal hospitals are the biggest type in Nepal, in terms of their size and facilities. Secondly, a private nursing home was chosen: Birat Nursing Home. This hospital is regulated by the Department of Health Services (DOHS) under the Ministry of Health and Population (MOHP).

The main agenda of DOHS is to provide preventive, promotive, and curative health services throughout Nepal.

Birat nursing home was established in 1995 as a private entity with modern facilities. Private hospitals must obtain a license from the MOHP and must follow all policies and rules designated by the government. Due to the poor service levels and a lack of trust in government hospitals, there is high demand for private hospitals. The failure of government hospital to provide better services, along with increasing demand for better treatment by patients has resulted in a growing number of private hospitals in different cities. Both private and public hospitals provide similar kinds of medical services to patients. The Fig 1 shows the current Map of Nepal where Fig 2 Indicates the area where the study was conducted (World Atlas, 2018).

FIGURE 1 MAP OF NEPAL

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FIGURE 2 MAP OF STUDY AREA

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Quality health care is an illusion for citizens of less developed or developing countries who continue to face severe health care service challenges. Factors like poverty, geographic location, age, unemployment, the unavailability of services and incompetent management of health services are real problems for these countries (WHO, 2015).

In the current market, the service sector is one of the most rapid-growing industries in the world which, and health care organisations are no exception (Dagger, et al., 2007). If organisations wish to succeed, service quality must play an essential role in improving organisational performance (Parasuraman, et al., 1985). In this competitive business environment, increased competition has influenced both private and public service providers the world over, and developing countries are heavily implicated. Therefore, to survive in the competitive market, organisation need to deliver services that satisfy customer needs. Research shows that healthcare has advanced over the years with developments in technology. Services are now provided to patients in a timely fashion (Zeithmal, et al., 2013).

In contrast, in developing countries like Nepal, many factors including poor infrastructure, poor sanitation, inequality and political instability contribute to poor service quality in health care settings.

According to the Kathmandu Post (2020), Nepal's maternal mortality rate is still 239 deaths per 100,000 live births despite the government's target of 125 for the year 2020. According to the World Bank (2015), almost 80% of citizens dwell in rural areas, and healthcare facilities in these areas are very poor. People must therefore travel to nearby cities for health care. Since it is difficult to reach remote areas as a consequence of poor transportation facilities, there are real challenges that must be overcome to provide better health care facilities to the population (Shrestha, 2021).

Service quality has become one of the primary drivers of customer relationship development and value creation. Patients are considered as customers in this thesis, and their perceptions of service in hospitals is considered one of the most significant measures of service quality (Dortyol, et al., 2014). Furthermore, high levels of service quality can deliver increased profits for the success. If customer satisfaction is achieved by the service provider, this can contribute to customer retention. Similarly, Padma et al., (2009) argue that to survive in a competitive market, the service provider must deliver quality services in terms of patient care. Due to rising competition in the marketplace, customers expect high quality in terms of services, so providers need to understand these expectations and provide quality services that are better than their competitors (Parasuraman, et al., 1985). Customer care and satisfaction are key to maintaining service quality levels in hospitals. Indeed, hospitals can achieve this by providing quality services to patients in technically and functionally superior ways (Nam, et al., 2011). Further, other authors (Lee, et al., 2011) have suggested that patient satisfaction depends on the level of service in each hospital. A great deal of research was conducted in the late 20th century in this area (Andaleeb & Conway, 2006). For example, Aldana et al., (2001) note the rise of research around this time in the area of customer satisfaction with quality health care. Most of these publications focused on patient comfort as the key to success in the health care industry. Research was carried out into the expectations of patients, and the scale of customer satisfaction and quality health care services provided by the hospital of Bangladesh. Aldana et al.'s research was based on a sample of 1,913 patients using a systematic random sampling procedure. Their study found that the most important predictor of patient satisfaction was the behaviour of medical staffs towards patients. Respect, trust and kindness were particularly key.

Furthermore, researchers explored “service quality and the relationship between service quality, customer satisfaction and consumer purchase intentions” (Jani & Han, 2011). Several models were proposed over the past two decades to measure service quality. The most popular methods used by different service providers and researchers were the SERVQUAL (Parasuraman, Zeithmal & Berry, 2003); and the SERVPERF models (Cronin & Taylor, 1992). Customer satisfaction is also a key indicator of the success of business, and this topic was studied by different researchers using various points of view. Wilson et al., (2008) argue that the quality of service can be measured using personal service quality and situational factors as key indicators of patient satisfaction. Indeed, satisfaction is directly related to service performance. Some researchers have proved this relationship such as Kuo (2003), and Gera (2011). Furthermore, it is crucial to understand customer views of service quality for any service provider to ensure responsiveness to clients (Wilson, et al., 2008). Several studies in health care have mentioned that patient satisfaction has gained more importance in recent years, particularly in developing countries like Nepal, India, Pakistan, and Bangladesh. Patient satisfaction is seen as a key measure of service quality, and a means to improve the performance of hospitals. Reliable and trustworthy management styles can help hospitals to deliver high levels of service and satisfaction to patients (Aagja & Garg, 2010).

Similarly, concerns for patient satisfaction have grown sharply in recent years as the desire to provide a competitive advantage for hospitals increase. To deliver better patient satisfaction, it is vital to measure the perceptions of patients in the area of service quality. It is also vital to come up with strategies for quality improvements in healthcare settings (Agus, et al., 2007).

1.3 RESEARCH AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

The purpose of this research is to measure the quality of service provided in Nepalese hospitals to service users. The study identifies service quality based on patient satisfaction. The research also identifies the challenges faced by the Nepalese health care sector.

The main research objectives

1. To identify the key indicators of service quality which are vital for patient satisfaction in hospitals in Nepal.
2. To review existing conceptual models and theoretical issues related to service quality, customer satisfaction and consumer purchase intentions
3. To identify the extent to which service quality dimensions influence patient satisfaction in Nepalese hospitals.
4. To identify the relationship between service quality, customer satisfaction and future purchase intentions.
5. To develop a framework to measure service quality in health care settings to shape customer satisfaction with service quality.

The main aim of this research is to measure service quality based on customer satisfaction and purchase intentions after receiving service. The research was conducted in Nepalese hospitals and it set out to understand patient expectations and perceptions of service quality in these settings. Patient perceptions refer to levels of patient comfort with service delivery. The hospital sector in Nepal is improving when it comes to service, but these improvements are limited to major cities only. Rural areas continue to be deprived of quality services. Since hospitals perform poorly, many face fierce competition from competitors. In terms of quality service, Nepalese hospitals provide poor services which results in patient dissatisfaction. Therefore, to understand patient expectations and perceptions, hospitals need to create a strategy to measure service quality in detail in order to build trust, earn customer loyalty, and fulfil the needs of patients through improved services. Delivering high quality services is the only way to create customer loyalty and satisfaction and increase customer retention. In a competitive market, understanding the needs of customers has become crucial. As such, companies increasingly seek to be more customer-centric and product-centric. Customer retention has become a strategic priority for the organisation. The main drivers of customer

retention and future purchase intentions are customer satisfaction. This can be achieved via prompt service and by fulfilling the needs and expectations of customers through excellent service. Customer satisfaction is a key indicator of the success of business, and it can help business over the long-term. Customer satisfaction can also influence the purchase intentions of customers. Purchase intentions and positive experience can therefore greatly impact on business performance (Dortyol, et al., 2014) .

Therefore, the primary purpose of this research is to evaluate the key dimensions of service quality in Nepal's hospitals, and to understand the relationship between service quality, patient satisfaction and retention in these hospitals. The research focuses on the perceptions of participants to map the relationships between customer satisfaction, the service quality dimensions and customer buying behaviour. The findings can help hospitals plan to boost the quality of their services in order to satisfy customers and achieve a superior level of performance. This research therefore scrutinizes the critical determinants of hospital service quality that positively influence the gap between the expectations and satisfaction of customers.

1.4 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The main agenda of the research question is to recognise the level of service quality that is provided by Nepalese hospitals. The extent to which this influences patient intentions to use services in the future is also examined. The main research question of the study is:

Why is service quality vital for customer satisfaction and consumer purchase intentions, and how are these two related?

The sub research questions for the study are:

- I. What are the pivotal elements that measure perceptions of quality amongst patients in hospitals in Nepal?
- II. Why is service quality so key for health care centres when it comes to customer satisfaction?
- III. Why higher service quality matters for customer satisfaction and consumer purchase intention?
- IV. How do service quality and customer satisfaction influence consumer purchase intentions in Nepalese hospital?

1.5 RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

Health care service has become one of the fastest-growing sectors in the world (Lanka, et al., 2009) because of increasing numbers of patients seeking quality services. At the corporate level, quality service delivery is considered an important and essential strategy to become successful and survive in a competitive market (Zeithmal, et al., 2009). The high-level of quality service is connected to patient impressions of the delivery of quality care. A better quality of service offers a healing environment where customers can return to utilize the same services again (Aagja & Garg, 2010). Previous service quality perceptions are shaped by factors like communication, provider courtesy, support, up to date equipment/facilities and low waiting times. These are the essential quality care aspects provided by health care businesses. Today's competitive market has seen a sharp rise in private hospitals in Nepal. These provide better services than government hospitals. In the context of Nepalese hospitals, the gap between the demand and supply of services in healthcare are significant, and this has driven the growth of private hospitals in Nepal (Adhikari, 2013).

Hospitals in Nepal should focus more on increasing the quality of their services to meet the needs and expectation of customers. In this way they can become more successful in competitive markets. As customer satisfaction is a crucial factor for business growth, service quality is a key dimension for building relationships with customers and understanding customer retention (Wilson, et al., 2008). If organisations can provide quality services to meet the expectations of their customers, this will mean they can enhance customer satisfaction and customer expectations, creating advantages in terms of competition (Lanka, et al., 2009). This can drive better higher economic returns for the organisation in the long term.

It has become essential for hospitals to measure service quality continuously against customer expectations, needs and perceptions. In this way they have come to recognise how to improve and have come to understand the expectations of patients when it comes to service. Many health care service providers fail to understand the importance of customer satisfaction and this can be risky (Gilbert, et al., 2004). A number of researchers (Voon & Abdullah, 2014; Lai, 2015; Kondasani & Panda, 2016) argue that service quality influences both buyer satisfaction and purchase intentions. Service quality is a vital tool for service marketers because by improving the quality of services, customer satisfaction can improve. This in turn may influence intentions to purchase the service. As such, delivering quality services is a key driver of satisfaction. Moreover, the service provider needs to identify which factors uniquely influence satisfaction amongst customers to deliver a better level of service to customers. Providing top service quality to customers will help to create opportunities to differentiate the organisation from its competitors. This can also help them to attract new customers and retain existing ones (Gupta & Rokade, 2016). Service quality has become a strength for organisations. There is also a difference between service perceptions and expectations of service amongst customers of the organisation (Zeithmal, et al., 2013) .

Competition in the delivery of excellent services and raising the level of customer expectations has made service providers work hard to satisfy their customers and enhance customer retention. Lee & Yom (2007) evaluated the relationship between the dimensions of service quality and variables like price, productivity, efficiency, customer satisfaction, profitability, and purchase intention. Any organisation needs to have a clear overview of service marketing design, and the implications for future buying behaviour across different

sectors. Researchers like Pai and Chary, (2016) argue that perceived preference has a powerful effect on customer satisfaction. Some researchers have pointed out that customer satisfaction is influenced by service quality, perceived quality, and consumer purchase intentions (Pai & Chary, 2013), however, there are arguments that relate to the relationships between service quality, customer satisfaction and consumer purchase intentions. These are arguably indirect relationships and are hypothetical within different service settings (Lee, et al., 2011). Consequently, it is important to identify the attributes of service retailing design and how these can affect future purchase intentions. Health centres therefore need to consider the characteristics of both their customers and their operational characteristics to understand the gap between service perceptions and customer intentions. This could help them to develop better marketing strategies (Pramanik, 2016).

This research will identify the key dimensions of customer satisfaction in hospitals, and the relationship between satisfaction and quality in terms of health care centres in Nepal. The study will focus on the views of patients and their perceptions of service quality in the Nepalese health care sector. By understanding the perceptions of patients, it will be easy for service providers to understand their needs. Providers must understand the needs of patients because technical skills are meaningless if they do not fulfil patients' needs (Pai & Chary, 2013). The study also adds to the literature in the area of service marketing by contributing in depth knowledge in relation to the service quality dimension. It also has implications for customer satisfaction and purchase intentions in developing markets. The findings could help health centres develop and implement market-oriented strategies.

1.6 OUTLINE OF THE RESEARCH

FIGURE 3 STRUCTURE OF RESEARCH

The above figure (3) provides the path of the thesis. Chapter one provides an overview of the study. It begins by presenting the background to the study and offers a discussion on the rationale. It also introduces the primary aim of the research, and the objectives. It provides brief overview of Nepal and justifies the reason for choosing this country as the research setting.

Chapter two presents a literature review on service quality and customer satisfaction. It addresses various service quality dimensions introduced by different authors, and It reflects on their views towards customer satisfaction and customer repurchase intentions. The literature review also critically evaluates existing theories on service quality posited by different authors that support the research objectives. The chapter also critically evaluates the SERVQUAL model which is used to measure service quality.

Chapter three identifies on the methodological approach and the research design that has guided the research. It provides a justification for the chosen research design, research methods, research strategy and research method, and it identifies the strengths and weaknesses of each of these. This chapter also identifies the sample design and discusses the reliability and validity of the research. It identifies the data analytical process and discusses research ethics. It also presents details of the pilot study that preceded data collection.

Chapter four discusses the findings of the study. Data that were collected from interviews with health service users are analysed to examine their perceptions of service quality level of service satisfaction.

Chapter five interprets the findings in some detail and the five major themes generated from the interviews are used to inform the ECET model of service quality for hospitals. This chapter also answers the overall research question.

Chapter six provides a conclusion to the study. The chapter concludes the research and identifies the contribution it makes to the literature. It also summarizes the research objectives and identifies the limitations of the study. It provides a set of recommendations for future research.

1.7 SUMMARY OF THE CHAPTER

Service quality, customer satisfaction and purchase intentions are key factors that shape the success of business in competitive markets. To succeed, organisations must understand the needs and expectations of customers. By understanding customers, and their expectations, businesses will be able to calibrate products according to customer expectations. Therefore, this research focuses on the relationships between service quality, customer satisfaction and purchase intentions. Service quality and patient satisfaction in health care have become important subjects in developing countries like Nepal. The gap between the expectations of patients, and their perceptions of service is therefore worth exploring. Understanding patient expectations is more important to provide tailored services, and this step is critical for service providers in delivering quality service. Numerous studies have indicated that customer satisfaction has a positive impact on future purchase intentions and is the best indicator of future profitability.

This section has therefore introduced the thesis and provided an overview of the research background and problem. The study has been undertaken to investigate poor service quality in Nepalese hospitals. The chapter has identified the main aims and objectives of the study. Similarly, the country's profile has also been presented along with a brief description of the Nepalese health system. An introduction to the hospitals in which the research was conducted was also provided.

The following chapter presents a literature review on service quality and it examines the various service quality frameworks purposed by several authors to measure service quality.

The characteristics and importance of service quality and customer satisfaction will be discussed. The next chapter introduces the global model of service quality which is called SERVQUAL. Furthermore, the chapter will address the benefits of service quality in the health care industry and the consequences for customer satisfaction, and consumer purchase intentions. Furthermore, the relationship between service quality, customer satisfaction and customer purchase intentions will be addressed in the next chapter.

2 CHAPTER TWO LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

The primary objective of this research is to evaluate quality in the Nepalese hospitals. In current situations, the primary goals of hospitals are to provide the best possible standards of care to patients. The right to receive quality can be considered a right that all patients can rely on, and it is the responsibility of the hospitals to provide quality care to patients.

This chapter will focus on the service quality literature drawing on work published by several researchers. The chapter aims to critically evaluate existing research on service quality, customer satisfaction and consumer purchase intentions. The chapter will focus on discussing the various concepts, dimensions and models of service quality. It will review the relationship between service quality, customer satisfaction and consumer purchase intentions. It will also review the SERVQUAL model (Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry, 1985) as a means of measuring service quality. It will assess whether this model is an appropriate measure of implementation in the health care sector of Nepal.

2.2 DEFINING QUALITY OF SERVICE IN HEALTHCARE

Service is an activity which helps to fulfil a need. Service can be experienced and are therefore intangible. Business operators often assess their service quality according to the satisfaction levels of their customers. They measure service to improve, to identify problems quickly, and to evaluate service so that satisfaction levels are improved. Services have become a vital aspect of organisations nationally, regionally, and globally, and service is regarded one of the most powerful drivers of growth in businesses. The success of the organisation depends on a strong relationship with its customers, and this interrelationship often shapes customer satisfaction and loyalty towards the organisation. It also determines the outcome and revenue growth of the organisation and has implications for customer relationships, increases in performance, market value, customer loyalty and organisational brand image (Lanka, et al., 2009). Offering service is a pivotal activity of the organisation. Service is the process of the organisations communicating and delivering product to customers by providing comfort, and by maintaining a high level of attraction towards its product. To meet customer expectations and needs, it is essential to develop and deliver excellent quality service to influence the buying behaviours of customers. This can improve the image of the organisation and can help it to sustain itself in competitive markets (Ladhari, 2012). The high level of service “*..high level of service helps in*

delivering customer satisfaction leading the organisation for sustainable competitive advantage in the volatile market” (Gronroos, 2007, p.72).

Quality care has become important to current generations and can be considered a significant concept in our lives. Service quality can differentiate services and build a competitive advantage for the organisation. Therefore, organisations should prioritise the delivery of quality services in key areas. In the health care industry, the quality of service covers three main elements. First, the quality service patients receive, which is the service they are provided with. Second, the quality of medical professionals, which refers to professionalism in healthcare, and the level of experience health care professionals possess to meet customers’ expectations. Lastly, administration quality refers to the administrative quality of hospitals as they go about providing efficient and productive resources to meet the needs of patients. Healthcare has started taking service quality seriously in a bid to deliver higher levels of service (Ovretveit, 2014).

The importance of health care has increased recently due to progress that has been made in medical and technological areas. Much attention is given to providing efficient and quality health services as perceptions of service quality has changed in the last decade. Patients now set high standards for quality service before attending for treatment, so it is crucial to understand the expectations of customers in the healthcare sector (Padma, et al., 2010). Moreover, due to developments in technology, healthcare customers are now demanding high quality, efficient and reliable services (Rajguru, 2018). A previous study on healthcare service shows that delivering a high level of service quality has a significant relationship with patient satisfaction in hospitals (Ramez, 2012). Similarly, all hospitals provide the same service, but they do not offer the same quality. As a result of the technological revolution, customers today have become more aware of service standards and alternatives. In this context, healthcare service providers can use service quality as a strategic differentiation weapon to build a variety of services to rival their competitors (Padma, et al., 2010).

As stated by Gronroos (1984), the health care service quality model comprises two dimensions: technical and functional quality, and these are pivotal to the success of service organisations. Gronroos (1984) defines technical quality as the technical accuracy the firm possesses to carry out procedures where information is confidential and generally not available to the masses due to its technical nature. Furthermore, technical quality refers to the professional procedures and accuracy of service providers (Negi, 2009). Functional quality refers to the behaviours

associated with service delivery. Furthermore, it has been described as the nature of the distribution of services, and how service has been delivered to, and received by patients (Mukuvi, 2013). To perceive of better-quality, customers mostly rely on the functional qualities of hospitals, such as their physical facilities, atmosphere, cleanliness, care quality, empathy, manners, responsiveness, and courtesy towards customers (Duggirala, et al., 2008). Patients generally lack the knowledge or expertise to examine the technical quality of hospitals with any accuracy, so functional quality is a major area of assessment for customers when it comes to the quality of service in health care (Mehta, 2011). This means that functional attributes have a significant impact on perceptions of service quality, so hospitals should evaluate services based on customer perceptions. They must therefore measure the functional quality of their services (Ladhari, 2008). Health care providers must also prioritise the development of functional qualities in services because these can influence perceptions and patient satisfaction, as well as service purchase decisions. Donabedian (1980) proposes that three components of quality have to be considered, and these are the input, the process, and the outcomes. In health care these translate to well-trained staff, qualified professionals, staff that are committed to quality improvement, and validated standards. This process is about responsiveness to the needs of patients and patient care and maintaining dignity and empowerment. Outcomes refer to the effectiveness of the care provided as well as patient perceptions and satisfaction.

Similarly, different authors have introduced various service quality dimensions for health care organisations. Baker et al., (2008) illustrate that the service quality dimension spans three key elements which are interpersonal quality, accessing health services and amenities. Interpersonal quality is the level of respect for patients as well as emotional support and empathy. This also refers to accessing health services and waiting times, as well as delays to appointments. Amenities refers to physical facilities such as the waiting room, examination room and equipment used. Where the Bakar et al., (2008) qualifies the functional quality of hospital address by (Edura & Kamaruzaman, 2009). Campbell et al., (2011) identified six dimensions associated with the effective delivery of service quality in health care. These are timeliness, accessibility, appropriate services, safety, and continuous and effective health service. Furthermore, the perceptions of service quality in health care are related to core attributes like empathy, reliability, trust and outcomes. In health care settings, patients belonging to different geographic and demographic groups, and those with different

behavioural needs have different service needs and perceptions of service quality (Clemes, et al., 2014).

To improve service quality and to ensure that a desirable quality level is attained, the health care industry needs to design a quality strategy which adopts an overall approach over a period of time. There are a number of possible methods which could be used to improve quality which include increasing resources, reorganisation, or financial reform, strengthening management, developing standards and guidelines, empowering patients, and promoting their rights. Other methods include adopting quality management systems, engaging in quality assessment, continuous quality improvement, and utilising quality indicator comparison systems (Ovretveit, 2014).

While quality information can be produced for these three components, Zhang et al. (2016) advise that structural measures might not explain what has been done to the customer, while outcomes are only partially dependent on the health service provided. Since it is accepted that efficient healthcare organizations are in a better position to deliver results, it may be more meaningful to assess processes before forming judgements of service quality (Kumar, et al., 2009).

It is challenging for health care service providers and receivers to measure service levels because the health care system is diverse, and the needs of customers keep changing as per their requirements. This creates challenges for hospitals seeking to estimate the quality of service required (Choi, et al., 2004). Health care providers must be able to measure health service quality so that they can identify their strengths and weakness and maximise their services (Zhang, et al., 2016). Measuring service quality in hospitals can benefit hospital management and can help them to understand the needs of their patients. It is therefore vital for hospitals to effectively adopt a service quality culture to provide a superior quality of service for their customers. A summary of qualitative findings in relation to health care provision by different researchers is presented in the table below:

TABLE SERVICE QUALITY DIMENSIONS

Authors	Dimensions
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Ovretveit (1992)	Customers, Professional and management
Parasuraman et al. (1994)	Servqual (Tangibles, reliability, assurance, responsiveness, and empathy).
Asubonteng et al. (1996)	Technical quality and Functional quality
Campbell et al. (2000)	Timeliness, Accessibility, Safety and security, effectiveness.
Clemes et al. (2001)	Reliability, Tangibility, Assurance, Empathy, Outcome, Administrative, Food, Responsiveness
Duggirala et al. (2008)	Personnel quality, Infrastructure, Administrative process, Process of clinical care, Safety, the overall experience of medical care and social responsibility.
Aagja and Garg et al. (2010)	Admission, Medical service, Overall service, Discharge process and Social responsibility.
Atinga et al. (2011)	The environmental facility, Support care, Courtesy, Communication and Waiting time
Mosadeghard (2012)	Cleanliness, Physical facilities, experienced health care professionals, Quality of hospital food.

2.3 CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION OF SERVICE QUALITY

In the modern competitive era, service quality has become a critical determinant of competitiveness. Service quality combines a range of key factors that are crucial to the success of any service business. As such, service is regarded as a powerful weapon that can fuel the growth of profit in an organisation. The success of service firms often depends on their relationship with service users, and this determines satisfaction levels and customer loyalty. High-level service quality strategies in any organisation can influence the outcomes of the organisation. Examples include increasing sales and driving customer retention and profit (Lanka, et al., 2009). Quality has been mentioned as totality of characteristics and features of the product which meet the requirements of service users. Furthermore, quality can be defined as a multi-dimensional phenomenon, so it is impossible to improve the level of service without identifying the significant aspects of it (Kotler & Keller, 2009). The three main output dimensions of service quality are the performance of the service, its technical quality, and the organisational image (Ovretveit, 2014). These represent the gap between perceived quality and expected quality in terms of the service encountered.

Service quality is considered a critical determinant of competitiveness. Prioritising service quality can help organizations to differentiate themselves from other organizations, and to gain a lasting competitive advantage. High quality service is considered an essential determinant of the long-term profitability of organizations. Service quality is defined as a comparison between customer expectations and service performance. Any organization offering quality service meets the needs of its customers and remains cost-economical in competition. Where there are improvements to service quality, the firm can become more competitive. Superior service quality is achieved by knowing the operational process as a result of identifying problems in service and defining measures for service performance, outcomes and customer satisfaction (Mukherjee & Nath, 2005).

Some researchers argue that the definitions of service quality revolve around the perception and identification of customer requirements (Palmatier, et al., 2007). Similarly, Parasuraman, et al., (1985) argue that the quality of service is the difference between the expectations of service and the real service received. Expectations are desires and wants, and perceptions are an overall evaluation of service after it has been received (Pramanik, 2016)

Service quality can be divided into two categories: technical quality and functional quality (Gronroos, 1984; Parasuraman et al., 1985, Zeithmal et al., 2009). Technical quality refers to the

accuracy and correctness of the technical skills for service delivery. In the context of health care, it is about the technical skills of medical diagnoses and procedures (Zaim, et al., 2010). Furthermore, it also refers to the qualifications and skills of the service organisation members, such as the skills of doctors and nurses. Functional quality refers to the process of the service delivered to customers. In hospitals, patients mainly focus more on operational facilities than technical ones, because most patients do not know about the technical skills required. Patients tend to focus on the cleanliness of the wards, the quality of the food, staff manners, and the atmosphere of the hospital. Several researchers have identified functional quality as an important dimension in seeking to understand the perceptions of the patients in hospitals. Functional quality helps service providers evaluate patient perceptions of service quality and helps the, to understand how patients evaluate quality in hospitals (Kamra, et al., 2016). Solomon (2011) found that, rather than technical skills, patients rate service quality according to non-technical skills. Their perceptions are also influenced by their previous experiences with the service encounters (Zeithmal, et al., 2009). Thus, a medical service provider tends to achieve a higher perceived level of quality when they meet the patient's expectations (Zaim, et al., 2010). Service perceptions can occur at different levels throughout the organisation with, for example, core services, physical facilities, and communication with providers. On the other hand, overall customer satisfaction with service organizations is based on all of their encounters with the organization (Sureshchandar et al., 2009).

Parasuraman et al., (1991), argue that the competitive advantages and market growth of any company are gained by improving the quality of service they provide to customers. The importance of service quality has developed over time. Many researchers have developed a different view of services. The company that provides better service quality to customers is likely to enjoy greater financial success. However, Ramez (2012) counters that service quality is not only about the final product or service which is given to customers, but it also includes all of the processes which occur from production through to delivery. Carauna (2002) suggests that quality service helps customers to compare its performance with their expectations. This refers to the difference between the expectations a customer has of service, and the service that they perceived (Zeithmal, et al., 2009). Perceived service quality is analyzed based on the expectations of customers and the service provided by suppliers (Zeithmal, et al., 2013). If supplier performance is poorer than anticipated, this will result in less perceived quality which creates obstacles to performance. Studies have therefore been conducted by researchers

focusing on service quality and customer satisfaction in the health care industry, and in other service industries. These are presented in the table below:

Author (year)	Dimensions	Sample/Approach	Findings
Padma et al., (2009)	Perceived service quality from the perspective of patients and their family in Indian Hospitals.	Questionnaire	Two elements to measure the dimension of service quality in the context of hospitals from the perspective of service users and their families.
Gaur et al., (2011)	Patient satisfaction, loyalty, and behavioural intentions	Questionnaire	Doctors' interactional behaviours are essential to develop an excellent relationship with patients and can increase customer loyalty.
Zafar et al., (2012)	Customer satisfaction, loyalty, and service quality	500 Questionnaire completed by customers using the service	Handling of tangibility, reliability and conflict will directly and positively result in customer satisfaction and loyalty.
Badara et al., (2013)	Service quality, customer satisfaction and loyalty	240 Questionnaires	Tangibility and Reliability have no influences on customer loyalty, no positive relationship between customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Siddiqi (2011)	Tangibles, Responsiveness, Reliability, Assurance and Empathy	100 Questionnaires'	Customer satisfaction and service quality are positively associated, and customer satisfaction and purchase intentions are positively related.
Ragavan & Mageh (2013)	Service quality dimensions and customer satisfaction	400 questionnaires	The positive correlation between tangibles, responsiveness, reliability, assurance, and customer satisfaction were negative between empathy and customer satisfaction.
M.M. Khan & Fasih (2014)	Tangibles, Reliability, Assurance, Empathy	225 questionnaires	Service quality has a significant and positive relationship with satisfaction and purchase intentions of customers.
Al Azzam (2015)	Service quality and customer satisfaction	400 Questionnaires	Service quality is positively associated with customer satisfaction.

Table 2: Service quality research conducted by Researchers

2.4 CHARACTERISTICS OF SERVICE QUALITY

Scholars have argued that the characteristics of service mean that they cannot be compared with goods, since they are about processes and not physical ‘things’ (Palmatier, et al., 2007). Service can be characterized by different key characteristics, the pure service can’t be seen or touched or stored because the services doesn’t have physical manifestation where they are considered as part of a process of interaction (Schneider & White, 2004). Some authors argue that services are acts, deeds, performances, or efforts. Therefore, services are mainly characterized by the dimensions of intangibility, heterogeneity, inseparability, and perishability. IHIP (intangibility, heterogeneity, inseparability, and perishability) has been widely accepted since the 1980s. However, it was later criticized by a number of authors (Lovelock & Wirtz, 2007) . Similarly, Rust (2004) noted that perceptions of changes to the characteristics of service have occurred due to the development of technology. The characteristics of services are examined below:

2.4.1 Intangibility:

Service is intangible, which means it cannot be seen or touched before it is bought. Service can be measured through the subjective perceptions of customers (Kandampully & Suhartanto, 2000). Lovelock and Gummenson (2004) filter intangibility into three-dimensions: physical, mental and generality. Physical intangibility refers to untouchability, and mental intangibility refers to visualization or imagination. Generality refers to accessibility or inaccessibility (Manary, et al., 2013). Services are intangible and cannot be touched as they are invisible and do not have any physical existence. Hence, they cannot be touched, held, tasted or smell.

2.4.2 Heterogeneity:

Heterogeneity is a form of variability in service. Each service is unique and has benefits. Even the same provider cannot repeat the same service twice. The variation of service is dependent on the skill levels of the service producers. Heterogeneity reflects the potential for high variability in service delivery (Zeithmal, et al., 2013). Onkvisit and Shaw (1991) consider heterogeneity as an opportunity to provide a unique and flexible product, and the service provider can benefit by customising service.

2.4.3 Inseparability:

Another important feature of service is inseparability. Inseparability refers to the delivery and use of services and means that services are produced and consumed at the same time. It has been stated by Gronroos (1978), Carmen & Langeard (1980), and Upah (1980) that service production and consumption are inseparable. Service providers often create a 'correct' version of service so that it can be consumed when needed (Dibb, 2006). According to Zeithaml & Bitner (2003), customers can be available at the time-of-service production and can even take part in the service delivery process. Service delivery takes place during the process of service production which creates an opportunity for the customer to evaluate performance. Simultaneously, the customer can influence other customers when it comes to services. Therefore, the service provider must understand the expectations of customers before service delivery. This can result in the provision of the best possible services for customers, which can eventually meet their needs. The employee must be ready to provide quality customer services after the service delivery process (Zeithmal, et al., 2009).

2.4.4 Perishability:

Perishability means that service cannot be stored for future use, and the consumption of service must take place immediately, before the service is wasted. This means that service is not valued if it is not used on time. (Ghobadian, et al., 1994) argue that service cannot be stored for consumption later, which means that it is perishable, and is the duty of the service provider to confirm that the service provided is correct each time. Moreover, it is essential for the service provider to add extra benefits to their products by adding additional value like aftersales care, remote support and an insurance policy. This can enhance customer service, which enables the service quality provider to enjoy a competitive advantage (Zeithmal, et al., 2009).

2.5 IMPORTANCE OF SERVICE QUALITY

Researchers have acknowledged the central importance of service quality measurements. Managing quality is crucial in any type of business. Quality products help to maintain customer satisfaction and loyalty and helps the organisation to reduce the risk and cost of reducing faulty products. After the industrial revolution, which started around 1700, people were more focused on mass production and less so on service quality. It was only in the 1980s that people realized that producing a large number of products does not meet the needs of customers automatically

and does not ensure a return on investment. As such, industries manufactured goods and services as per the needs of customers to create satisfaction. Then, organisations focused on providing quality services to maintain strong relationships between performance and quality. As a consequence of research, companies came to understand that competitive advantage can only be achieved by providing quality services (Zeithmal, et al., 2013). Service quality has a direct effect on the global economy, as half of the world economy is service-oriented. It is a more useful and fundamental concept in the service-providing sector, especially if the company has to sell services instead of products (Amaratunga, et al., 2002). To improve the quality of services, companies implement various plans so that they can meet the needs of customers and remain competitive (Sureshchandar, 2009). By standardizing services, companies can not only achieve external gains but can also celebrate internal achievements. Apart from customer satisfaction and loyalty, high-quality service provides in any firm creates various advantages such as standing out amongst competitors and earning a good reputation in the market. Other benefits include a rise in market share value and earning outstanding revenue on services and investment (Jandavath & Byram, 2016). Mehta (2011) also indicates that high-quality services enhance overall internal performance and service quality. In order to compare and evaluate service, firms can collect data and analyse where the satisfaction of customers comes from, and what additional efforts must be made to meet strategic goals (Mosadeghrad, 2013). By comparing and evaluating, the firm can identify its position in the market (Abdul & Chong, 2007).

It can therefore be argued that service quality is directly proportional to customer satisfaction and has a direct effect on market share value and customer loyalty. This can result in reduced costs of production, and higher outputs and profits, as well as staff satisfaction.

2.6 CONCEPTUAL MODEL OF SERVICE QUALITY

Service quality is the core product, and it is also a type of performance. It is the performance that customers are interested in. Quality service gives companies the chance to compete with competitors for customers to build customer confidence (Clemes, et al., 2014). Quality in the organisation is mainly distinguished by the relationship between expectations of service and the service experience at the time of delivery. In the service quality literature, authors have developed several models to identify the significant determinants of service quality. The

earliest thinking came from Gronroos (1982) and Parasuraman et al. (1985). Their ideas are based on the relationship between customer expectations and perceptions. Similarly, Oliver (1980) introduced the disconfirmation paradigm on a similar basis of the connection between expectations and perceptions.

In the last three decades, different researchers and authors have tried to develop concepts of service quality. Some were broadly accepted and remain in use today. The two most salient models are discussed below.

2.6.1 NORDIC SCHOOL MODEL

The Nordic school model was the first service quality model to emerge in the 1980s from the Nordic (Gronroos, 1984) and the American schools of thought (Parasuraman, Zeithmal, and Berry, 2003). This model consists of three main dimensions to measure quality. These are technical, functional and image quality.

In contrast, the Nordic model recommended two dimensions of service quality which are functional and technical quality. Technical quality is what consumers receive from the service provider as the result of the transaction. In contrast, functional quality is how customers receive the service quality or how customers obtain the technical outcome. Technical and functional quality are antecedents of the image of the organisation, which is the third dimension of the model (Gronroos, 1988). The organisational image influences the customer's expectations of service quality, so the corporate image of the organisation is the final result of how the customer perceives the firm.

FIGURE 4 NORDIC MODEL

The Fig (4) display the dimensions of Nordic Model, Gronroos (1982) introduced the concept of the “perceived service quality model” and argued that the outcomes of the organisation are determined by perceived quality amongst customers. Costumers compare their expectations of service with their perceptions of real service. Therefore, the quality of service is informed by these two main factors which are named as the expectations of service, and perceptions of service. In this model, customer perceptions are the main features that are used to measure service quality and determinants to influence service quality. According to this model, the first objective is to find the resource that can affect these variables, and to identify this so that the firm can act upon it accordingly. This theory was a further refinement to the model proposed by Gronroos (1983;1983a;1984) and it incorporates work by Swans and Combs (1976). These authors found that the perceived performance of service was divided into two sub-processes which are instrumental performance and expressive performance. Moreover, it is connected to the psychological level of a return, such as the interaction of customers and service providers. According to Gronroos (1982), customers rate their expectations (a function of market communications, image, consumer wants and needs, word of mouth, consumer experience with the same service provider or their competitors) against their perceptions. Customers often continuously contact the same service provider, wherever their service perceptions are gathered from each different service encounter.

In effect, Gronroos introduced another quality dimension along with the technical and functional aspects called image. The image of any service provider depends upon technical and functional quality, price, external communications, physical location, the appearance of the site, and the competence and behaviour of the service firm's employees. A reputed and well-known brand image is an asset to the organisation because image plays a vital role in customer perceptions of service. Vision has an impact on the communications and operations of the organisation. A positive company image can be a significant advantage to the organisation, whereas a negative image can have the opposite effect. Furthermore, Gronroos (1982) argued that the perceived service quality model can only remain a conceptual model which might help the researcher to understand service dimensions. This model was developed to provide the services equivalent model of a product features model (Clemes, et al., 2014).

This model mainly considers three dimensions which are outcomes, processes, and image. However, the model focuses most keenly on how customers perceive quality. It does not evaluate service performance and does not determine customer satisfaction and dissatisfaction. As such, the model cannot be called a 'service quality dimension' model. Rather, it is a model that offers an overview of the constructs of quality.

The diverse aspects of service quality models which were proposed by Gronroos, and his team have been commonly embraced by those that study service quality. The customer perceptions model was applied by Manolis and Windsor (2002) and Kang and James (2004). However, some have criticized the model, especially three aspects model. Bernard and Shostack argue that functional and technical quality fail to describe all of the aspects of service adequately (Clemes, et al., 2014). They counter that the service quality framework is primarily based on services in which interference with human service will occur. As such, this model is not adequate to properly address physical and technological services which play such an essential role.

2.6.2 THE NORTH AMERICAN SCHOOL (GAP MODEL)

The North American school gap model of service quality was advanced by Parasuraman, Berry and Zeithmal (1985), and more recently described in Zeithmal and Bitner (2003). This model was more popular than the Nordic school model in the service market. It has served as a framework for research in service marketing for more than two decades. This model was also named as the “disconfirmation model”. It originated in 1985 and was later refined in 1985,1991,1993 and 1994 by Parasuraman et al., (1994). This model describes the expectations of customers, and the performance of the service industry. The model mainly identifies four specific gaps leading to the fifth gap between customer expectations and perceived service quality. According to Zeithmal, Bitner & Gremler (2009), the customer gap refers to the difference between the customer’s expectations of service, and their perceptions of service. To improve service quality, managing the customer gap is critical in the organisation. (Wilson, et al., 2008). Gaps 1-4 are called provider gaps as they take place in the organisation . Gap 5 is influenced by gaps 1-4, so service quality can be improved by reducing gaps 1-4 (Wilson, et al., 2008).

Parasuraman et al., (1985) argue that service quality in an organisation is the gap that occurs between customer expectations and perceptions of service. This study was performed to recognise service quality concepts. The researchers chose four service industries with different goals, and the upper-level executive were interviewed. From the interviews, it was concluded that there were gaps in the perceptions of service quality by the provider and the receiver. All of the gaps are illustrated below:

FIGURE 5 GAP MODEL

2.6.2.1 Gap 1: Expectation of Customers – Perception by management gap

There is a gap between the expectations of customers in relation to service, and observations that management make in relation to these expectations. Managerial personnel may not always have a clear view of the indicators of high-quality service, and for this reason quality can be perceived differently by customers (Wang, et al., 2002). It is therefore crucial to measure service delivery in a way that is easy for the staff who deliver service directly to customers. If they are made aware of service measures, they can comply with these policies and provide the best service (Ravichandran, et al., 2010).

2.6.2.2 Gap 2: Perception by Managerial Team-Translation of quality specification gap

This gap is a consequence of management's perceptions of the needs of customers, and the specifications for the service being delivered. This gap can arise due to mismanagement and the reduced availability of resources for the facility. This difference can damage customer perceptions of service quality (Parasuraman et al.,1985).

2.6.2.3 Gap 3: Service quality specifications – Service delivery gap

Gap 3 is also called the service performance gap, and service firms often put standards in place to maintain service quality. Regardless, it can be challenging for them to maintain their service delivery standards. This gap arises due to variability within the work schedules and processes of employees (Parasuraman et al., 1985: 45). Sometimes, employees underperform tasks, and some deviate from the guidelines of the company. A lack of staff training can also elicit poor performance, as can poor communication between lower-level employees and senior staff (Al Bassam,2013). As such, worsened employee performance can affect service quality perceptions from the customer's point of view.

2.6.2.4 Gap 4: The service delivery – External Communication gap

This gap is the difference between the service promised by the company and the service it delivers, particularly where delivery falls short of the promise made by the organisation. (Al Bassam,2013). This difference can occur because of poor communication with customers, or insufficient knowledge provided via advertisements. Over-promising service is also damaging (Parasuraman et al.,1985).

2.6.2.5 Gap 5: Expected service – Perceived service gap

Gap 5 is the difference between the service expected and customer perceptions of service. This gap is a function of the previous four gaps (Parasuraman et., 1985). The gap model is used as a tool by organisations to recognise gaps in service delivery. The model can help service providers identify problems and provide solutions to improve the service that customers receive. The gap model has received criticism from several authors and has subsequently been refined several times. Indeed, Parasuraman and his team redeveloped the gap model and its

five dimensions and named it the SERVQUAL model. This model can be used to measure customer perceptions of service quality (Parasuraman et al., 1988).

The Gap model by Parasuraman (also known as the service quality model) acts as a user satisfaction framework to define service quality in organisations. Indeed, service providers have to focus on removing the five gaps to achieve quality service and patient satisfaction (Mukuvi, 2013). This model enables service providers to identify problems in the delivery of service quality in order to achieve better performance. The gap between the service user's expectation and perceptions after using the service should be as narrow as possible. Satisfaction occurs when the service user has a positive perception of service. Otherwise, the level of service may fall below expectations.

2.6.3 THE LEHTINEN & LEHTINEN MODEL

Lehtinen & Lehtinen (1991) proposed a three-dimensional, and two-dimensional model which measures service quality. The three-dimensional model consists of three main service qualities, namely physical quantity, interactive quality, and corporate quality. The physical quality dimension usually refers to the physical elements of services. Physical factors can be divided into two parts: physical products and material supports. Physical products are generally used in the primary stage of the service production process. The support needed to complete the production process by establishing a strong framework is known as physical support. This is illustrated in the figure below:

FIGURE 6 LEHTINEN & LEHTINEN MODEL

Physical support can be further split into two parts: environment and instrument. The situation/environment can refer to the overall appearance of firms, and instruments are related to the physical supports needed during the delivery of services.

Similarly, the second dimension: interactive quality, is self-explanatory. This refers to the interaction between the service provider and customers. In this sense, quality can be defined as a way of evaluating the interactive skills of the service provider, and the extent to which an individual can respond to customer queries. Such interactions are not only limited to humans, but may also involve technology, for example, cash machines or employees in financial institutions (Brady & Cronin, 2001). The third element of the model is corporate quality, which is mainly based on time. This quality develops as the service organisation evolves. It primarily focuses on the evaluation of corporate image. Physical and interactive conditions can only be determined if customers are involved, whereas the quality of an organisation is based on time. As such, Lehtinen and Lehtinen (1991) suggest that the organisational dimension can be used as an effective tool, and as a safety net for any drawbacks linked with the other two qualities.

Lehtinen and Lehtinen (1991, p288) proposed another two-dimensional model as an alternative and proposed that it could be seen as complementary to the first model. The two-dimensional model consists of the process quality and the output quality of service production. According to Lehtinen and Lehtinen (1991, p288), “the process in quality can be addressed as the collective views of the customers concerning production process regarding their attachments with the product or services.” If customer opinions are taken into account, the firm can act according to their views, which can fuel customer satisfaction. As this dimension focuses on the customer's views, it further contributes to continuous service quality improvement (Lehtinen & Lehtinen, 1991).

The second dimension of the two-dimensional model holds that output quality can be achieved by the tangible and intangible aspects of the firm. Lehtinen and Lehtinen suggest that service quality can also be achieved through the tangible aspects and intangible aspects of the firm. For this illustration, they took the tourism industry as an example. The output quality achieved was described by customers articulating their feelings towards services.

Lehtinen and Lehtinen's model (1991) shares similarities with the model proposed by Gronroos (1982). Gronroos' model also included technical and functional qualities, which are considered

to be vital factors in the financial sectors. Lehtinen and Lehtinen proposed a similar idea relating to interactive behaviour between various aspects of the process to gain service quality. A model was designed during the earlier era of the service sectors. Other firms and businesses tend to follow the model as it covers most aspects of quality. The model acts as a framework for other scholars like Rust and Oliver (1994) when it came to designing the three-component model in 1994. Service delivery, service product and service environment were the main three components of the model, as with Lehtinen and Lehtinen's three-dimensional model. It is considered one of the most useful models to measure service, A key criticism for this model is limited because this model was the earliest model of service quality (Brady and Cronin, 2001, p.35).

2.7 MEASURING SERVICE QUALITY

To improve service quality, a number of quality measurement theories were introduced, including total quality management. These theories were tested on various organisations from the last decade around the world. The focus of these new theories was to improve the service delivery process based on a customer-centric approach (Geletta, 2018).

Exploratory research performed by Parasuraman, Zeithmal and Berry (1985) found ten overlapping dimensions which can assess service quality for customer satisfaction. These are tangible, reliability, responsiveness, credibility, communication, competence, security, courtesy, understanding the customers and access. Later, this model was developed and modified by Parasuraman et al., (1991) and was titled the SERVQUAL design model. The model incorporates five service quality measurement dimensions which can measure service quality. The model is useful for measuring service quality perceptions. Later, Parasuraman et., (1991) conceptualized the model's name SERVQUAL model with the five major dimensions to measure service quality. This model remains popular amongst organisations today. Servqual assumes that the difference between customer perceptions and customer expectations of services can give clues as to the service quality standards of the organisation. Service quality is measured based on service delivery to service receivers. If the service provided meets or exceeds the expectations of the user, then the service is perceived to be of a strong quality. The ten dimensions of service quality are summarised in the table below.

Dimensions	Meaning
Tangible	Physical aspects like physical facilities, pieces of equipment, personnel's appearance
Reliability	Performance consistency and dependability, accuracy of services, providing the right service at the right pace.
Responsiveness	The willingness of providing service, timeliness of the service, prompt service
Competence	Skills and qualification of the professionals, the research capability of the organisation
Access	Accessibility, approachability, location, waiting time
Courtesy	Politeness, Respect, Empathy, kindness
Communication	Understandable communication, service and product explanation about cost, duration etc
Credibility	Trustworthiness, believability, honesty, company reputation
Security	Privacy, less risk, safety, confidentiality
Understanding the customers	Understanding the needs of customers and their requirements, giving individualized service, attention.

Table 1: SERVICE QUALITY 10 DIMENSION

2.7.1 THE SERVQUAL MODEL

SERVQUAL is a concise multiple-item scale with good reliability and validity. Retailers use this to better understand the service expectations and perceptions of their consumers with the aim of improving service. This model provides a basic skeleton through its expectations and perceptions format, encompassing statements for each of the five service quality dimensions. SERVQUAL can identify problems in the organisation and can help to improve performance.

The Servqual framework helps to measure service quality in the organisation. This model was introduced by Parasuraman et al., (1995), and has become one of the most widely used tools to measure quality in several service industry settings. The framework consists of five key dimensions, and these are described later.

Many authors have listed the advantages of Servqual (Mukuvi, 2013). The model was mainly developed to identify gaps between the expectations of consumers and the service they receive. This can help the company to determine whether the service they are providing is of a sufficient quality or not. According to Zeithmal, et al., (2009), factors like communications, previous experience, external disclosure and personal needs influence customer expectations. Parasuraman et al., (1988) argue that Servqual was designed to measure the service provided, and this can be used to track service quality trends which may cause customers to criticise service quality.

GAP 1	The needs of customers which are not understood by management.
GAP 2	After understanding customer satisfaction, management does not try to fulfil their expectations
GAP 3	The gap between demand and supply for customers when management fails to get proper customer knowledge. The gap arise between specification of quality and the delivery of the service.
GAP 4	When the organisation over-promises services (in advertisement)
GAP 5	The gap between service expectations and the service experienced by the customers.

TABLE 4: SERVICE QUALITY GAPS

In the above model, the dimensions of SERVQUAL such as communication, security, competence, and tangibles reveal much about perceived quality where there is a gap between expectations of service and that which is experienced. This is known as the service quality gap and is shaped by the influence of several external factors. This model has been criticized by researchers such as Chin Gang and Lukong (2010) who stated that only focuses on the delivery of service and fails to focus on the outcomes of the service provided. Shafiq et al., (2017) suggest Servqual is the most salient and useful model for measuring service quality.

After receiving criticism for their original ten-dimension model, Parasuraman et al., (1988) started refining the stages of the model and focusing on condensing the scale of its dimensionality and reliability. After a process of refinement, they produced the SERVQUAL model to measure service quality globally. The model is based on the five major service quality dimensions (Kansra & Jha, 2016). The Servqual model was successful in terms of meeting the challenges of reliably measuring customer perceptions of service providers by introducing a new measure (Kumar, et al., 2009). The model has been successfully used to measure service quality by organisations for some time. The model was the subject of considerable attention from service providers after its introduction, and it is now used by many organisations. Some researchers have applied the model in their own research and have evaluated and even criticized it (Bateson & Hoffman, 2011; 2008; Kuch & Von, 2007). The five dimensions of the Servqual model are discussed in more detail below.

2.7.1.1 Reliability:

Reliability is the ability of any company to perform the service they have promised to provide, accurately and trustfully. According to Parasuraman et al., (1988), reliability is the most important factor in terms of service. Reliability depends on identifying and handling customer service issues and trying to provide quality service for the first time within a promised timeframe without error. According to Helkkula and Kelleher, (2010) reliability is about executing service in a timeframe that is guaranteed to consumers. In the health care industry, reliability is key, as patient satisfaction is crucial. Patients depend on hospital staffs to receive excellent service without errors as health is so key to human survival. Caruana and Pitt (1997, p.612), state that: “*reliability is consisting of consistency and good performance with dependability.*” Parasuraman et al. (1988, p.23) suggest “*reliability is the ability to perform the*

promised service dependably and accurately.” It is a fundamental requirement for customers who want to see services performed correctly, the first time they are attempted by the service provider, when they are asked to do so. As such, service providers are required to honour and respect their promises. No matter what service customers purchase, its reliability is valued above all else, and customers are satisfied if their expectations of reliability are met. This drives customer satisfaction and development in terms of brand loyalty. Hensley and Utley (2019) suggest a framework for service reliability can help when it comes to allocating tools for technical errors and failures so that managers can understand problems and come up with solutions. Any service provider or company is deemed trustworthy if they emphasise factors such as promise-keeping, effective communications, and safe and secure transactions when needed.

2.7.1.2 Responsiveness:

Responsiveness refers to a willingness to help customers by providing urgent services. For example, in the health care sector, this is about managing waiting times. According to Zeithmal, Bitner, and Gremler (2006), responsiveness is closely related to reliability, and the desires of employees to provide services to customers at a given time. The collaborative nature of service places service providers in a very high-risk position when trying to deliver quality services. Ho Voon (2008) argues that the company can recognize the needs of its customers. Doucette (2010) states that effective communication and commitment to customers can create competitive advantage. This involves the timeliness of service. Customers expect prompt service and examples include the immediate return of phone calls, and the provision of product support (Parasuraman et al., 1985). On the other hand, Simons (2014) argues that responsiveness is about the commitment of a company to assist its customers and provide service in real-time. This practice will build trust in the customer’s minds towards the company, which will affect their decision-making process.

Furthermore, Wilson and Frimpong (2004) argue that if the customer is happy with the service received, then perceptions of service quality will be high. Responsiveness is key for the organisation who follows a service-oriented strategy for business success, and where regular interactions with customers are common.

2.7.1.3 Empathy:

Empathy refers to the care, love and attention provided to the customer by service providers.

As per Parasuraman et al. (1985), empathy is the attention and care provided to the individual by firms. This process involves employees giving individualized care and attention to customers. Employees must be able to understand the needs of their customers. Ananth et al. (2011) state that empathy is about providing individual attention. In health care, this is about understanding the needs of patients. Customers like to interact with organisations where staff are available to help. They prefer an easy-to-access network and organisations that are committed to identifying the needs of their consumers in order to deliver proactive services. This aspect depends on how well coordinated, courteous and organised the company is.

In developed countries like Japan, being courteous to customers is part of the culture of organisations. This is expected to the extent that customers will stop dealing with the organisation that does not have this written into its culture. Approachability is a significant variable because customers feel more relaxed and satisfied with businesses that employ friendly staff and user friendly systems. Each customer wants to feel special and wants to deal with people who understand their needs and expectations. Knowing the names of regular customers and creating lasting relationships are good strategies for any service provider.

To the better-perceived service, customers want service providers firm to figure out the the key problems they have in meeting customer needs (Wilson, et al., 2008). This method is more beneficial for SMEs seeking to compete with bigger companies. Those that are empathetic to their customers tend to succeed more.

2.7.1.4 Assurance:

Assurance refers to the knowledge that employees show while building trust and confidence with customers. Parasuraman et al. (1985) argue that assurance is a mind game. It is the ability of employees to instil confidence and trust. Sadek et al., (2010) argue that the characteristics of assurance are politeness. Friendly staff with strong product knowledge and experience are real assets. The key indicators for assurance are courtesy, safety and security, skills, trust and credibility (Huang et al., 2011). If customers have a bad experience of service, they may question the ability of the organisation and the appropriateness of its systems. They may doubt the security, safety, credibility, and courtesy of the organisation. For example, when the credit cards are used for transactions which are carried out online due to the advancement of technology. As a result, customers seek safe and secure operations to process transactions (Niranjanamurthy and Chahar, 2013). However, the growth of new technology carries risks,

such as the hacking of online accounts. In such cases, customers prefer organisations who can provide secure services, and who prioritise confidentiality and privacy when it comes to information. As such, maintaining safety is key and will create trust and a strong relationship between key workers and customers (Jain & Gupta, 2004).

2.7.1.5 Tangible:

Tangibility refers to the physical appearance of facilities such as equipment. According to (Brady and Cronin, 2001), tangibility refers to solid materials such as the physical manifestation of staff facilities. The appearance of the company is what is tangible, this includes equipment, infrastructure, and the design of spaces. Vrontis (2014) argues that tangibly helps to communicate a quality image of the company. The physical appearance of the company is important to create favourable impressions and to ensure people can feel safe. If the company does not have better tangible materials but promises to deliver better service, then customers might not trust the company's values. There is therefore a need to make customers feel confident in services. If hospitals look like community halls, then patients will not feel confident about their treatment.

Similarly, hospitality businesses prioritise physical facilities as part of the overall service offer (Andaleeb, et al., 2007). Research conducted in the Malaysian public transportation sector found that customers using public transportation attached more importance to the tangibility of transport, including its cleanliness, and the comfort of physical facilities (Zaim, et al., 2010). Further research was conducted on Nigerian airlines using the Servqual model and found that participants focussed more on interpersonal quality over tangible qualities (Chickweed et al., 2012). The Servqual model of service quality mainly focuses on human behaviour and physical facilities in terms of service delivery. Ladhari (2009) suggests that the Servqual model is ideal for measuring service quality, and it can be applied to various service settings. To get a reliable and valid result, researchers or service providers must choose the dimension that best fits the research area.

Perceived service quality is another important dimension that needs to be addressed by service providers to drive customers satisfaction. Perceived service quality is measured by the organisation's ability to meet the needs and expectation of customers. The importance of service quality has grown sharply, and this has encouraged research into similar topics (Khan, 2010).

According to Meesala and Paul (2018), customer satisfaction depends on the level of quality in the organisation. Organisational performance is judged by differentiating real service perceptions from customer satisfaction. Service quality has become important for health care providers and several authors and researchers have considered it in the context of hospitals using various service quality models to measure customer satisfaction (Ahmed, et al., 2017).

Using the Servqual model, service quality is evaluated based on an assessment of service outcomes and service delivery procedures used by customers. Service quality which meets or exceeds the expectations of customers gives clues as to the quality of service available (Parasuraman et al.,1991). The model has been widely applied by several researchers in the health care sector (Pai and Cherry ,2013). Some researchers have modified the model to suit specific situations. The Servqual model is useful to measure the difference between perceptions and expectations of patients using healthcare services (Kumar, et al., 2009). The model is useful for measuring the various dimensions of service quality from the perspectives of customers and business owners. Expectations and perceptions are key to measuring service quality and customer satisfaction. The level of customer satisfaction depends on the positive and negative effects of expectations and perceptions (Zeithmal, et al., 2009).

Several arguments have been made by various researchers in relation to this model. Cronin and Taylor (1992) argue that an evaluation of service quality based on the difference between performance and expectations as measured by the SERVQUAL model is not enough to measure service quality. Similarly, the main drawback of Servqual is that it fails to address other aspects of service such as technical quality. Indeed, it focuses more on service delivery quality (Kang and James 2004). Buttle (1996) argues that the SERVQUAL model has been used by several researchers to measure the quality of different service provider organisations. Ladhari (2009) recommends the model, arguing that it can measure service quality very effectively. Despite the theoretical and operational criticisms that are levied at SERVQUAL, the model remains popular amongst academics and researchers (Caruana et al., 2000, Cronin and Taylor,1992).

In addition, Buttle (1996) offers further critical commentary on Servqual. He suggests that it is not universal, and not based on any grounded theories. Others suggest that the model pays little attention to measuring the technical quality and outcomes of the service process. Some suggest that the dimensions of Servqual are unstable, and much depends on the industry they are

applied to (Buttle,1996). Carman (1990) addresses the practical difficulties of using the model to measure expectations of reliability. This author considered customer expectations in particular and argues that the Servqual model does not fit as well as expected in the four different service industries he examined.

Furthermore, some researchers have criticised SERVQUAL for failing to measure perceived service quality (Cronin & Taylor, 1992). Similarly, the model fails to identify customer attitudes to service and satisfaction. Furthermore, Coulthard (2004) argues that the model is not suitable in non-western cultures. The model is suited to European culture and was, after all tested in European markets. Some Asian academics saw this criticism as a challenge and conducted research in an Asian context. Abdulla et al., (2013) applied the model to the tourism industry in Asian markets and found it had a more universal relevance (Sultan & Simpson, 2000). Raidh (2009) argues that the Servqual model is useful for measuring service quality dimensions despite criticisms of its reliability and validity dimensions. However, researchers like Cronin & Taylor (1992) and Francis (1995) reject the model in its original format and propose the revised Servperf model as an alternative.

2.7.2 SERVPERF MODEL

Cronin and Taylor developed this model based on an attitude paradigm which contrasts with the disconfirmation paradigm of SERVQUAL (Cronin and Taylor,1992). It is mainly based on the ‘perception’ paradigm. The Servperf model was introduced to replace the Servqual model and addresses criticisms of the disconfirmation paradigm. It sought to avoid the validity problem in the measurement of expectations. Gronroos suggests that the model is “easy to administer” and “easier to analyse” when looking at perceived service quality (Gronroos,2007, p.88). Servperf covers the same dimensions as Servqual, but it does not measure expectations (i.e. the ‘experience’ gap).

Cronin and Taylor (1992,1994) concluded that the use of SERVPERF offers some variation to the SERVQUAL paradigm to measure the quality of service. They argued that looking at results alone is not sufficient if expectations are not measured. They suggested what they saw as a better approach. These researchers therefore challenged the construct proposed by Parasuraman et al., (1985,1988). The two models approach service perceptions quite differently. Kelkar (2010) states that the model is heavily based on performance rather than on performance and expectations, which can help to determine quality service. Moreover, Kelkar

(2010) argues that the expectations of customers are built around performance, so it is not necessary to measure customer expectations separately.

In contrasting the SERVQUAL and SERVPERF models, researchers have suggested that service could be measured using a performance monitoring tool. Sanjay and Gupta (2004) reason that “the psychometric soundness and parsimoniousness of the instrument” make SERVPERF suitable for research that focuses on evaluating the standard of service quality of a company or business. Likewise, the use of SERVPERF provides managers with valuable knowledge in designing quality and management plans. They propose that SERVPERF is appropriate to evaluate the level of service. Marco (2001) hypothesized that SERVPERF is related to customer satisfaction rather the quality of service. Similarly, Juan and Zornoza (2000) report that SERVPERF has greater reliability and validity, and effectively describes heterogeneity variance to a greater degree than SERVQUAL. Similarly, some of the researchers have justified servperf model stating that this model provides the important information to the organisation managers to develop strategies for the quality improvement and said that this model is sufficient to measure the service quality of the organisation (Gilmore & McMullan, 2009) . Where Francosis & Mulki (2007) have analysed to measure the validity of both model Servqual and servperf, they have researched for seventeen years on 42 study which concludes that both models equally can be used to measure the service quality.

Both the model Servqual and Servperf are quoted equally by the researcher at same level (Carrillat, et al.,2007).They agreed that both scales are accurate and similarly relevant for assessing the quality of service, although they indicate that Servqual focusses mostly on users. Several researchers have used both models in various service industry settings. The findings have not been applicable to all service contexts and all service perceptions { (Dabholkar, et al., 2000); (Negi, 2009)}.

2.8 CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

Administering customer satisfaction has become an important function of organisations. Customer satisfaction is about meeting the needs and expectations of customers. Satisfaction can be evaluated by assessing the customer’s experience of services and perceptions of service experiences (Jandavath & Byram, 2016). Indeed, satisfaction has become one of the main goals of organizations since it can drive profits and provide organisations with a competitive advantage. However, ensuring customer satisfaction is a complicated task. According to Kotler

& Caslione (2009, p190) “...to a person’s feeling of pleasure or disappointment resulting from comparing a product’s performance in a relation of his or her expectations”. Kotler & Keller (2009, p91) observed “the summary psychological state resulting when the emotion surrounding disconfirmed expectations is coupled with the consumer’s prior feelings about the consumption experience.” Customer satisfaction indicates the customer’s psychological situation which includes their optimistic or derogatory emotions or behaviours about their experience, and other basic elements of the service interaction. The concept of customer satisfaction holds that businesses must satisfy customers if they want to be sustainable and profitable in the market (Raghav, et al., 2020).

Focusing on customer satisfaction has become fundamental to the success of the business for the long term and is a key aspect of influencing the future intentions of customers to use services. It provides an important connection between post purchasing anomalies and cumulative purchase concerning the loyalty of brand repeat-purchasing, and changes of attitude and behaviour (Dortyol, et al., 2014). It is believed that if the customer is happy and satisfied, they will pass on a version of their perceived experience to friends, family, and relatives. These customers therefore play a vital role as a reference point through word of mouth recommendations which can influence other potential customers to purchase from a company that has provided a high level of customer satisfaction (Lai, 2004). Similarly, there is a disparity between customer preferences and the service provider’s performance. However, researchers suggest that satisfaction and quality remain key. Parasuraman et al., (1991) argue that satisfaction is gained from an experience after the service is received. Satisfaction is the feeling of pleasure associated with receiving great service, however quality can be perceived as the service as it is delivered. Customers are always selective about the products or service they prefer, so the expectations of customers remain high for the services / products they seek out. Kotler and Armstrong (2012, p254) described satisfaction as “...the feeling of fulfilment of needs or unfulfillment arising from the contrast of perceived result from service received.” Zeithmal, et al., (2009, p88) suggest “satisfaction in customers is the degree of competence of services”. Thus, if service users are satisfied with service providers, they remain faithful to them, and customer retention is more likely. Indeed, customer retention tends to lead to more customers, a higher market share, a greater yield in terms of revenue, and other benefits (Jani & Han, 2011 & Simon, 2012). Berry and Parasuraman (1991) argue that the provision of quality customer service has become a major concern for all business. Customer satisfaction is a post-consumption evaluative process that contrasts pre-purchase expectations with

perceptions of performance during and after the consumption experience. Oliver (2010) suggests customer satisfaction is about the emotional response of customers. Similarly, a study conducted by Kotler and Keller (2013, p. 110) concluded “*customer satisfaction as a state of mind in which the customer’s needs, wants and expectations throughout the product or service life have been met or exceeded resulting in subsequent repurchase and loyalty*”. Moreover, Schiffman and Kanuk (2010, p.478) argue that customer satisfaction is “...*the individual’s perception of the performance of the product or service concerning his or her expectation.*” Moreover, “*customer satisfaction is one of the most important issues regarding the business of all types, which is approved by the customer-oriented philosophy and the principles of continuous improvement in the modern enterprise* (Arokiasamy, 2013, p. 1535)” The concept of marketing suggests that if customer expectations are met by service firms, then the customers are more likely to be satisfied and to repurchase in the future. They are more prone to positive WOM in such cases. The opposite is true of dissatisfied customers. Therefore, satisfaction in terms of buying behaviour is a key element of the long-term objectives and strategies of service firms. Retaining existing customers is easier and cheaper than attracting new customers. As such, customer repurchasing will benefit organisations and can reduce marketing costs. It can also help organisations to develop more predictable sales targets (Ali et al.,2015).

There is no universal definition of customer satisfaction. It has been described as “a consumers post-consumption evaluation of a product or service” (Mittal et al., 2010). Satisfaction “occurs if the perceived performance of a product or service meets or exceeds customers’ prior expectations” (Kotler & Keller, 2009). Similarly, Zeithaml et al., (2013) argue that customer satisfaction works as a key component of the long-term success of business. Satisfaction in customers can be interpreted in two ways: process and outcomes (Pappas, et al., 2014). In this competitive market, organisations can provide high-quality services to elicit customer satisfaction which can lead to greater market share and the ability to compete for competitive advantage (Tsoukatos & Rand, 2007). The organization needs to understand the needs and requirements of customers, and the impact of these on the delivery of service (Lertwannawit & Gulid, 2011). If the company succeeds in understanding its customers’ needs, it will be easy for them to determine the actions they must carry out to fulfil these.

In the context of health care, a cure and better treatment is the basic need, and expectation of every patient. The key elements of patient satisfaction are the quality of treatment the hospital provides, and the patient's relationship with the doctors and staff who patients communicate

with. If doctors understand their patients, they can provide the correct treatment which will result in customer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction enhances the financial performance of the private hospitals, and it helps to build the good image of the hospital which is favourable to its reputation (Naidu,2009). Competition has increased between hospitals in the current market, so they must keep track of the factors that can affect patient satisfaction. Feedback from customers, and surveys carried out by hospitals help stakeholders understand the perceptions of customers towards services (Al-Neyadi, et al., 2016). Customer satisfaction has become a key indicator that determines the performance of hospitals, and the quality of service that it provides. It helps hospital managers to prioritise the needs of customers by understanding demand. Several theories have been proposed in relation to customer satisfaction including discrepancy and transgression theories. These underscore customer satisfaction when service conditions and preferences are consistent. The patient satisfactions are grouped into the five dimensions of physician care, availability of emergency care, supportive and reliable staff, good nursing care and convenient visiting hours (Patayawati, et al., 2013). Research has been carried out on patient satisfaction in health care service industry and some researchers, like Linder Patayawati et al., (2013) argue that patient satisfaction is important to evaluate service quality in hospitals. In contrast, patient satisfaction can be mediated by the beliefs of patients and their previous experiences with health care. Furthermore, Murti et al., (2013) addressed the importance of patient satisfaction in hospitals as a measure of the quality of care the hospital provides, and the continuity of services received by patients in future (Murti, et al., 2013).

Previous research on the health care industry has identified various factors which can determine patient satisfaction in hospitals, and differences in the way patients perceive health services across different cultures. For example, Patayawati et al., (2013) describe an interrelationship between medical staff and patients and suggest this is a key determinant of patient satisfaction. Similarly, a good relationship between doctors, nurses and patients has a huge impact on patient satisfaction. Based on these findings, it is clear that patient satisfaction is the perceptions that are formed by customers about services. Service can be technical and interpersonal. Thus, the health care provider who can deliver the technical and interpersonal benefits regularly can influence patient satisfaction (Gill & White, 2009). Satisfied patients play a key role in spreading positive feedback about hospitals and this impacts on its brand image. Therefore, patient feedback can help hospital management design a strategy that can enhance satisfaction levels (Rajguru, 2018).

Figure 7 Satisfaction-Profit Chain (*Anderson & Mittal, 2000*)

2.9 CONSUMER PURCHASE INTENTIONS

Consumers buying decisions are very complex. Consumers, after all, ultimately decide whether to buy products or services. Wu et al. (2011) define purchase intention as the probability of the consumer being willing to purchase a product in future. This idea links in with the consumer's attitude, perception and buying behaviour. Chen & Chen, (2010) observe that purchase intentions are a key factor for consumers when they are making purchase decisions. Consumer purchase intentions are considered to be very complex decisions, affected by several factors. Purchase intentions are mainly related to consumer behavioural perceptions and attitudes. Purchase behaviour is an important key element for consumers when considering and evaluating certain products (Keller, 2009). Once consumers decide to purchase products, they will be driven by their intentions. However, purchase intentions can be altered by elements like price, quality, and value perceptions ((Lee, et al., 2011)). Organisations need to understand the products or services that consumers need and want and must understand which consumers are likely to transact. They must also understand what influences purchasing and consumption behaviour (Karbala & Harimukt, 2012) . Purchase intentions are said to be a success when the consumer is attracted towards a specific brand. Consumers can choose a particular brand based on its positioning (Cho, et al., 2014). Researchers considered purchase intentions to be helpful in identifying consumer purchase behaviour.

Schiffman and Kanuk (2010) argue that product images are clearer if customers need to purchase the item, and this is an example of an idealistic purchase intention. A customer becomes more educated about product and style trends from particular previous experiences of purchasing the product. Purchase intentions can be investigated to understand attitudes towards buying. Michael et al., (2009) suggest that purchase intentions are the individual's intention to buy a specific brand which they have chosen for themselves. Costa et al. (2010) suggest that purchase intentions can be defined as the consumer's willingness to consider buying. The term repurchase is used by Wand and Tadisina (2008) and Chaniotakis et al., (2010) to specifically describe purchase intentions. Here, intentions are referred to as consumer decisions about purchasing or repurchasing. According to Halim & Hamed (2005), and Kincaid (2003) purchase intentions are defined as the probability of purchase associated with buying the product. (Palmatier, et al., 2007)state that positive purchase intention leads to increased sales and customer share. This can reduce costs and can capitalise on marketing efforts.

Similarly, purchase intention is addressed as the individual's intention to buy specific products

or brands which they have chosen for themselves after making an evaluation. Service quality and satisfaction play an important role in customer purchase intentions (Black, et al., 2014). Purchase intention as the willingness of consumers to buy products (Chaniotakis & Lymeropoulos, 2009), whereas authors like Wand and Tadisina (2008) and Blackwell et al. (2001) use the term repurchase when describing purchase intentions. Similarly, Al-Ekam et al. (2012) view purchase intentions as the individual's willingness to purchase a certain product or service. Purchase intentions, they suggest referring to the decision-making process when making a purchase from a company. Some researchers argue that purchase intentions are an important predictor of the purchasing behaviour of customers. Understanding purchase intentions can help organizations to decrease their marketing costs, reach new customers, increase revenue and pursue competitive advantage (Jani & Han, 2011). To make decisions when it comes to purchasing life insurance products, customers tend to be concerned with the financial aspects, yet the service-related elements are of equal importance. There are several factors which influence customer purchase intentions, and these are discussed below:

Product quality: Providing good quality service to customers is key. Excellence in terms of service can satisfy the wants of the customers. Perceived quality refers to the consumer's evaluation of the service or products offered by the organisation. Providing quality products can enhance competitive advantage in the market to enhance the benefits for the organisation (Andaleeb & Conway, 2006).

Brand image: The brand image of the company helps customers to view a company or product. (Hsieh & Liljander, 2009) defined brand image as the mental perception of the customers based on an association towards a brand. Organisations seek to create a strong brand to help customers recognize their product. As well as prioritising brand recognition, many organizations want their product to convey a specific image. Brand image is the overall impression created in the consumer's mind, formed from previous interactions with the organization. The brand image can outline how products are launched. The origin of the product, such as the country in which it is produced can affect brand image perceptions (Koubaa, 2007). A positive brand image helps to exceed the expectations of customers and increases the brand value of organizations (MSG, 2014).

Socioeconomics: Socioeconomic conditions are vital considerations for customers considering their purchase ability. The most critical factor in terms of socioeconomics that affects purchase

decisions is the income of individuals. Indeed, the income of individuals divides people into social standings by estimating the source of their revenue (Schiffman & Kanuk, 2010). Consumer purchase decisions are based on characteristics like age, occupation, and financial ability. These factors have a direct impact on customer buying behaviour (Kotler & Keller, 2009). In contrast, the socio-economic conditions of buyers influence their purchase decisions to an even greater extent. As such, marketers should consider a range of socioeconomic factors when designing products.

Social influences: Social influences refer to actions, feelings, thoughts, attitudes, or behaviours of individual change through interactions with other individuals or groups. Crucial here is the concept of socialization, peer, and family pressures. In social psychology, this idea is often related to the impact of social norms towards the changing of individual behaviours and attitudes (White et al., 2009). Buying decisions are related to social values that derive from a need to be respected and to acquire a desirable social status (Delre et al., 2008). Peers, family members and other groups exert strong influences on the buying decisions of individual.

In health care industries customers are referred to as patients. The buying intentions of the patients depend on their expectations of services, and their attitude towards the service experience. If hospitals can understand the expectations of their patients, they are more likely to provide quality services to end users. The buying intentions of service users in hospitals are influenced by positive WOM recommendations, personal experiences, price changes and service perceptions (Wu et al., 2008). A previous study conducted by researchers in health care found that positive word of mouth, a willingness to recommend, and trust were the key measures of purchase intentions (Ozdemir & Hewett, 2010). The more the experience of patients is positive, the more likely they will be to use the service again in future, and to recommend the service to others. The quality of services has affected patient loyalty and future purchase intentions. In terms of health treatment, people believe more about the experience of other when it comes to making decision. Experiences of services influence customers in their assessment of services.

2.10 INTERRELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SERVICE QUALITY, CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AND CONSUMER PURCHASE INTENTIONS

Service quality has a strong positive connection with customer satisfaction, customer loyalty and purchase intentions (Siu & Cheng, 2001; Cronin et al., 2000). The literature on service quality shows that customer satisfaction depends on the expectations and perceptions of high-level service quality (Zeithmal, et al., 2009). Better, and high levels of service quality are key factors that can be useful for measuring organisational performance and improving services based on an understanding of weaknesses in competitive markets (Namukasa, 2013). Service quality ultimately drives customer satisfaction. In competitive markets, customers have become more demanding and businesses that fails to meet the needs of customers are more likely to fail and to lose revenue. The relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction has received much attention from organisations and researchers (Zineldin, 2006). A strong relationship between customers and service providers helps organisations to achieve a profit over the long term. The higher the level of satisfaction the greater the chance that customers will use these services in the future. This can drive the numbers of returning customers to use services at a later date. This process will benefit the organisation financially and reputationally. This can be achieved by providing services which match the expectations of service users based on an understanding of their needs and expectations (Kotler & Armstrong, 2012). Various authors have argued that service quality is the only factor that can contribute to the satisfaction of customers. In health care sectors, service quality is a critical factor that has a significant impact on customer loyalty and purchase intentions. Most health care sectors provide similar services, so providing high-quality service is a means to differentiate offers from those of competitors in the market (Lopez, et al.,2007; Shanka, 2012).

Service quality and customer satisfaction share a clear cause and effect relationship, which helps organisations to exist, compete and become successful in today's highly competitive market. Kotler & Keller (2012,p. 128) notes "*the quality of service is antecedent to customer satisfaction, irrespective of whether the constructs are transaction-specific or cumulative.*" It is useful therefore to evaluate customer perceptions of the functional and technical dimensions of service. At the same time, satisfaction is greatly influenced by the quality of products, by perceived factors, and by interpersonal and technical factors (Parasuraman et al., 1995). Service quality and customer satisfaction have much in common, but service quality tends to emphasize the dimension of services, whereas satisfaction is a broader concept (Wilson et al.,2008).

Previous researchers have demonstrated a relationship between service quality and satisfaction. Andaleeb (2012) found that service quality has a significant impact on customer perceptions, and customer satisfaction. Similarly, quality services can positively influence the level of trust customers invest in the organization. Ultimately, trust undoubtedly impacts satisfaction. This implies that service quality can determine the satisfaction of customers at various levels. Customer satisfaction increases where service quality is conformed. As such, perceptions of service and satisfaction generally depend on the service quality level that is experienced (Parasuraman et al.,1995). Kashif et al., (2015) argue that customer satisfaction, service quality and future purchase intentions can create a competitive advantage for business. Hence, service providers must focus on strategies to build a lasting relationship with customers. Satisfaction with services can increase loyalty in customers (Caruana,2002) and can strengthen brand-customer relationships (Amin,2016). Several studies have found that customer satisfaction is a key determinant of the extent to which customers repurchase products. Highly satisfied customers are more likely to repurchase and encourage others to purchase (Jamal & Anastasiadou, 2009). Such customer spread positive WOM recommendations about services (Picon, et al., 2014)

Parasuraman et al. 1985 argue that quality in organisations has been the subject of considerable interest by both practitioners and researchers in recent years. Many researchers regularly use the term service quality and customer satisfaction in their research. Although service quality and customer satisfaction dominate the marketing literature, it is common to find no clear link between the two. Zeithmal et al., (2009) consider that service quality and customer satisfaction represent the same concept, while Dabholkar (2003) suggests that service quality and customer satisfaction converge over time to describe the same thing. The relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction remains an important issue in the services marketing literature (Muhammad, et al., 2015). Service quality is an important tool for measuring customer satisfaction (Choudhury, 2013) and helps to build a relationship with customers. As service quality is improved in the organisation, the probability of customer satisfaction increases, which can lead to behavioural outcomes such as commitment, customer retention, increased customer tolerance and positive word of mouth (Mehta,2011). While other researchers and authors have mentioned the importance of service quality for satisfaction, service quality has had a positive effect on satisfaction. Service quality it is a key factor for customer satisfaction and the future purchase intentions of customers. Various studies have applied quantitative and qualitative methods to demonstrate that service quality is a predictor of customer satisfaction

(Zeithmal, Bitner & Gremler, 2006; Ramseook - Munhurrun and Naidoo,2011;Shanka, 2012). Satisfaction, according to research occurs in the presence of high-quality goods and services which can create specific levels of perceived value for customers. This keeps customers engaged with organizations (Wicks & Roethlein, 2009).

Product quality has a significant impact on customer buying behaviour. (Olorunniwo, et al., 2006)conducted a study into the quality of hotel service quality and suggested that this fundamentally affects the behaviour of customers and shapes their intentions to revisit. Hence, service quality has both a direct and indirect effect on satisfaction and purchase intentions. A number of researchers argue that service quality directly influences the buying behaviours of customers (Tsaur, Lin & Wu, 2008; Basheer, 2012). Some have noted the indirect influence of service quality on customers (Chen,2008; Zabkar et al.,2010; Simon,2012).

Organisations that provide services to customers struggle to meet the needs of customers because their efforts may impact on the organisation's performance and profits (Ryu, et al., 2012). According to Bitner et al., (2010) satisfaction is considered to be the consumer's fulfilment response. Similarly, another study conducted by Anderson and Srinivasan (2003, p.125) argues that *"Satisfaction may be best understood as an ongoing evaluation of the surprise inherent in product acquisition and or consumption experience."* To develop upon this idea, Oliver (2010, p.13) describes customer satisfaction as *"a judgment that a product or service feature provides a pleasurable level of consumption-related fulfilment, including the level of under or over fulfilment."* Satisfaction is a key aspect of positive buying behavioural intentions which include future repurchase intentions and long-term loyalty towards service providers (Anderson and Srinivasan,2003; Hsu et al.,2012). Oliver (1993) developed a model to explain the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction. He stated that service quality is improved by comparing performance perceptions and ideals related to the dimensions of quality, and satisfaction contradicts expectations. Oliver's model was later tested by Spreng and Mackoy (1996).

Furthermore, the relationship between service quality, customer satisfaction and purchase intention has been addressed in several studies and in difference contexts. Doran and Smith (2004), Moghadam & Amiresmaili (2009), Alborie and Daanhour (2013), Voon and Abdullah (2014), Mitropoulos et al (2018) conducted studies on the impact of service quality on customer satisfaction and purchase intentions, where the key dimensions of service quality were found

to measure patient satisfaction in hospitals. (Mitropoulos, et al., 2018) carried out a study in a public hospital in Greece to identify the service quality dimensions relating to patient satisfaction. They identified that communication is a key dimensions of satisfaction, followed by physical facilities and hospital administration procedures. Communication between patient-doctor and patient nurses is key to understanding the expectations and perceptions of services by patients. As such, clear communication with patients helps them to express their needs in relation to treatment, and vice versa. This results in patient satisfaction and can lead to greater patient purchase intentions towards services. Similarly, Patayawati et al., (2013) found a direct relationship between service quality and patient perceptions. This relationship has a direct impact on the patient's commitment and trust towards the service provider. Patient trust can be profiled by understanding the needs of patients through the clear and understandable communication processes.

Some have argued that customer satisfaction is a short term, transaction-specific measure, whereas service quality is an attitude formed by a long-term, overall evaluation of performance (Huang, 2012). Some authors believe that customer satisfaction leads to perceived service quality, where others believe that service quality leads to customer satisfaction. The foundation of true loyalty lies in customer satisfaction, where service quality is a key input. If the customer is very satisfied, then they are more likely to become loyal towards the organisation and also spread positive word of mouth. Dissatisfaction drives customers away and is a key factor in switching behaviour (Lovelock & Wirtz, 2007, p.371). The continuous improvement of service quality and customer satisfaction is required due to the strong correlation between the two topics. Further, excellent service, and a high level of satisfaction are important goals to enhance the performance of any organisation. As a process in time, service quality takes place first and leads to overall customer satisfaction. Therefore, service quality is a key indicator of customer satisfaction.

The following tables illustrate some of the findings pertaining to the relationship between the quality of service, satisfaction and the buying behaviours of customers in different service settings. Various researchers are cited.

Authors (Year)	Constructs	Contexts	Findings
Doran & Smith (2004)	Service quality and customer satisfaction measurement in the clinic of Scotland	Clinic in Scotland	Customer satisfaction indicators are patient safety, clinical procedures, administrative procedures, waiting for time, price, information availability.
Moghadam & Amiresmaili (2009)	Measurement of service quality and patient satisfaction in the Hospital of Iran	Kerman University of Medical Sciences, Iran	
Bedi (2010)	Service quality, customer satisfaction and purchase intentions.	Banks in India	Customer satisfaction is influenced by service quality and is more influenced by word of mouth.
Chen et al. (2011)	Service quality, customer satisfaction and behavioural intentions	Taiwan National park	Customer satisfaction is influenced by service quality. High-level service quality provides satisfaction which helps to influence the long-term purchase behaviour of customers.

Cho and Rutherford (2011)	Value, purchase intentions and Word of Mouth	Service firm	Value and word of mouth more likely to influence repeat purchase intentions amongst customers.
Huang (2012)	Service quality, value, satisfaction, Image & Behavioural intentions	Golf event tourists	Service quality influences the expectations and satisfaction of customers (tourists) which results in a good picture, and this leads to confidence in buying products
Alborie and Daanhour (2013)	Evaluation of patient satisfaction with service quality in hospital	Hospital of Saudi Arabia	Service quality and customer satisfaction
Voon and Abdullah (2014)	Identification of dimensions of service quality for patient satisfaction.	Malaysian Hospital	Clinical procedures, waiting time, empathy, and patient safety were the key dimensions for service quality.
Lai (2015)	Service quality, Value, perceived quality, Commitment and Truthfulness towards the service.	Hong Kong, Restaurant	Service quality influences satisfaction, perceived value and loyalty.
Kondasani & Panda (2016)	Analysis of the impact of the patients' perception of service	Hospital	Physical setting, dependability, security, and privacy.

	quality on their behavioural.		
Yavas et al (2016)	Assessment of the impact of service quality on patients' overall perception about hospital service quality and their buying intentions for theregarding future use and recommendation	Hospital	Communication, Trust, Empathy, Responsiveness
Mitropoulos et al (2018)	Identification of the dimensions of the hospital service quality to determine patient satisfaction.	Public hospital of Greece	Doctor communication, Physical environment, discharge information, waiting time.

Table 2: Study on service quality, customer satisfaction and consumer purchase intention

2.11 CONCEPTUAL MODEL FOR THIS STUDY

The conceptual model that best resonates with this study is the Gaps Model of Service Quality (Parasuraman et al,1985). The Servqual model has become the most popular tool for service quality measurements in the service industry and has been widely used by the health care

industries (Al – Neyadi et al., 2016; Peprah & Antarah, 2012). The Servqual model helps to identify gaps between service providers and customers in the health care settings of Nepalese Hospitals. Expectations and perceptions of these services by customers can be measured by the SERVQUAL model. This model mainly focuses on Gap -5, which is the service expectation and service perception dimension that relate to the service that is delivered. The majority of researchers have measured service quality using Oliver’s disconfirmation paradigm which proposes that satisfaction is a function of the disconfirmation of performance from the expectation (Dabholkar et al.,2000, Duggirala et al.,2008). The model developed by Parasuraman et al. (1988) has benefitted many researchers seeking to understand and measure perceived service quality. Perceived service quality has been considered in the health care sector (Duggirala et al., 2008) and has been one of the most ideal approaches to measure service quality in the health care sector. When the scale was developed at first, 100 sets of questions were written to invite consumers to rate service in terms of expectation and performance. These ratings reflect the dimensions of the model. Later, the questions were revised and decreased to 44 in total. In terms of a ratings, a seven-point Likert scale was applied, where 1 is “strongly disagree” and 7 is “strongly agree”. The participants were asked to rate their expectations and perceptions of service on the seven-point Likert scale. The results were used to identify gaps in expectations and perceptions. After gaining popularity and widespread recognition, the SERVQUAL model was criticised by different authors (Carman,1990, Cronin & Taylor,1992, Lee et al.,2000). Cronin & Taylor (1992) argued that it was flawed, inadequate and disorganised. They developed an alternative tool: SERVPERF and suggested that there are no universal factors which are relevant to the service sector. Murti et al., (2013) argued that the service quality constructs developed in one culture may not be applicable to another. Others argued that the SERVQUAL model fails to connect psychology and economics together (Kang, 2006). Despite receiving such criticism, the model remains popular amongst businesses and academics (Mukherjee & Nath, 2005). For this study, Servqual is suitable for developing a set of research questions that will help the researcher to develop a substantial interview schedule to measure service quality in hospitals in Nepal. The Servqual model was therefore applied by the researcher in the health care industry. Tucker & Adams (2001) used the Servqual dimensions to measure service quality in US hospitals, whilst Sohail (2003) applied the model to measure services in Malaysian private hospitals. Likewise, Rohini and Mahadevappa (2006) used the Servqual model in Bangalore hospital to measure the quality of services. By using the model, they were able to understand the service perceptions of patients and hospital

management. The study found a gap between the expectations and perceptions of service amongst patients and management in the hospital. Ramsaran – Forward (2008) carried out a study in a private hospital in Mauritius, and subsequently modified the Servqual model. The thinking here is relevant to the current study and has helped the researcher to develop a conceptual model with fewer dimensions to measure service quality. Similarly, Ahmed and Samreen (2011) used the Servqual model to measure patient satisfaction in public-private and semi-public hospitals in Karachi. They measured the gaps between three hospitals and found that reliability, responsiveness, tangibility, empathy, and professionalism were the key predictors of patient satisfaction. Similarly, Kansra & Jha (2016) used the model to measure service quality in Indian hospitals. They applied the model to measure the quality of service to help managers understand the expectations and needs of patients. The Servqual model thus provides the basis for the research reported in this thesis, and it has been used to analyse the difference between customer expectations and perceptions in the health care sector of Nepal. The conceptual model for service quality, customer satisfaction and purchase intentions is produced below.

Figure 8 Conceptual Model of the Study

2.12 CHAPTER SUMMARY

The main aim of this chapter was to examine service quality in the service industry. In competitive markets, in order to grow, businesses cannot ignore the benefit of service quality. This section therefore discussed various theories, models, and framework which all relate to the service quality. The literature review, discussion and conceptualization were concerned with knowledge about service quality as produced by various researchers. This chapter also addressed the different models of service quality applied across a range of service sectors. The Servqual model was explored as a useful tool to measure quality. The literature review highlighted the Gaps model of service quality as a suitable tool to measure the gap between expectations and perception of services. This is seen as relevant since it will support an analysis of customer needs in relation to satisfaction. The literature review also focussed on refinements to the Servqual model made by different researchers, and it informed the conceptual model that was introduced for use within this study.

Service quality is important for organisations in competitive markets. In terms of health care, service should always be the main focus of organisations. Health care organisations must realise the importance of quality service for customer retention and loyalty. Focusing on the needs of customers can improve the delivery of quality services for customers. To measure service quality, the health care industry must follow an appropriate service quality model, to measure the expectations and perceptions of patients when it comes to quality services. To satisfy customers, it is important to understand their needs and wants. After receiving service, and if needs are met, then the chances of future purchases remain high. Most researchers have acknowledged the positive relationship between service quality, customer satisfaction and purchase intentions. Therefore, examining this relationship can provide the organisation with more knowledge about the subject, and can help them to identify the importance of customer relationships for profits.

The next chapter outlines the research methodology and discusses the research methods that were used to answer the research questions. Further, a justification for selecting these methods for data collection is provided. Similarly, appropriate methods for sample selection are identified, and ethical considerations are explored.

3 CHAPTER THREE RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

Any research study starts with the choice of the research topic and research methodology. Hence, the main purpose of this chapter is to explain the research methodology that was chosen for this research. The overall aim of the chapter is to review literature on types of research approaches, methods and research designs that have been applied, and to describe the process that was used to gather and analyse data. The research design is therefore identified, and a justification is provided for the choice of methods. A discussion of the strengths and weaknesses of the methods is also developed. Furthermore, this chapter reflects on research reliability and validity, and it examines the research tools, data collection methods, data analytical methods and ethical considerations that are necessary to develop a research strategy. Similarly, the rationale for using the research method and design that are chosen is discussed, and the limitations are also described. A conclusion reflects on these choices and sets the scene for the next chapter.

3.2 RESEARCH PARADIGM

A paradigm is “the *basic belief system or world view which will guide the investigation*” (Guba & Lincoln, 1994, p105). This derives from the Greek word which means ‘pattern’ (Kivunja & Kuyini, 2017). In research, the paradigm identifies the process of the research. It examines aspects such as research beliefs, and the decision-making process that influences how knowledge is shaped through research. The methodology and paradigm were differentiated by Sarantakos (2005) who argued that the method is the strategy of the research, which translates ontological and epistemological principles into guidelines, and underscores the process for conducting the study. It also speaks to data collection and analytical instruments. The research paradigm is an overall conceptual framework of the research process (Heal & Perry, 2000). Collis & Hussey (2009) suggest that the researcher should choose a research philosophy that suits the research objectives.

This study is based on qualitative research methods with a focus on an in-depth interpretation of patient satisfaction in Nepalese hospitals. Qualitative analysis is realistic, and naturalistic and can be interpreted as “an approach for exploring and understanding the meaning the participants ascribe to the problems” (Creswell, 2014). Furthermore, Merriam and Tisdell

(2016) argue that the main aim of qualitative research is to reveal an experience of the world. Braun and Clarke (2013) suggest that qualitative research uses words as data which are collected and analysed. The study focuses on collecting data based on the experiences of participants, whereby the researcher constructs the experience of participants into knowledge through interpretations and reflections. Guba and Lincoln (1985) further argue that the research paradigm relates to ontology, epistemology, and methodology. Hitchcock & Hughes (1995, p.21) contend that “*Ontological assumption gives rise to epistemological assumptions which will have methodological implications for the choice of the precise data collection methods*”. Similarly, the epistemological underpinning of the research is limited by the ontological interpretation, whereby the methodological description is defined by both the epistemology and ontology of the study (Lincoln & Guba, 2013).

Ontology refers to assumptions about the nature of existence or reality (Bryman, 2012). The ontological assumptions shape the quality of the study. Epistemology provides a philosophical basis for valid and legitimate knowledge (Maynard, 1994). Epistemologies help the researcher to know the truth and reality of the study. The methodology is the process for conducting research (Antwi & Hamza, 2015), and includes reasoning around the choice of methods to meet research outcomes. The methodological choice researchers adopt is determined by the ontological and epistemological assumptions, and the research question that guides the study (Collis & Hussey, 2003). This study follows a constructivist paradigm, and knowledge is recognised as socially constructed. Crotty (1998, p.9) defines constructivism as “*The view that all knowledge, and therefore all meaningful reality as such, is contingent upon human practices, being constructed in and out of the interaction between human beings and their world and developed and transmitted within an essentially social context*”. The main purpose of qualitative research is to provide a deeper understanding, rather than to examine the surface, so the researcher follows constructivism to achieve the objectives of the study. Using constructivism, the researcher supports social constructivism; and this helps researchers to explore their personal knowledge. Constructivism accepts reality; therefore, reality is perceived as subjective.

Where there is no single method or methodology or research paradigm that can be applied to accomplish a study, the main research paradigm which is mostly followed by the researcher is positivism and interpretivism (Creswell, 2009; Smith et al., 2002; Mallet, 2007). This will help to shape the research design and the knowledge produced. Those two paradigms are described

below:

Positivism	Interpretivism
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aims to produce quantitative data. • Many samples are used for the research. • Mainly concerned with hypothesis testing • Data is highly specific and precise. • Research is reliable. • The location is artificial. • Validity is low. • Generalised from sample to population. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This tends to produce qualitative data. • A small sample is used for the research. • Mainly concerned with generating theories. • Data is rich and subjective. • Reliability is low. • Location is natural. • Validity is high. • Generalised from one background to another.

Table 3: RESEARCH APPROACH (Collis & Hussey, 2003 & Amaratunga et al., 2002)

Collis & Hussey (2014) view the positivist paradigm as a naturally evolving method which originated in natural science. It is based on a deductive approach, and assumes that reality exists independently of humans. Similarly, Veal (2006, p.61) defined positivism, "...as a framework for the research where the researcher sees the object of study as a phenomenon and used the theory and model developed by the researcher." Positivists believe that reality is stable, and that it can be observed and explained from an objective viewpoint (Levin, 1988). Positivism is said to involve the manipulation of reality. The ontological positivist believes that the world is external, and there is only one single objective reality for the research circumstances (Hudson & Ozanne, 1988). The positivist researcher does not connect with the participants of the research, and they make a clear distinction between reality, personal experience and judgement. The quantitative researcher uses positivist approaches because statistical and mathematical techniques are the key to their ethos (Carson, et al., 2001). Hence, quantitative researchers usually adopt a deductive approach for to research. In terms of data collection, questionnaires

observations and experiments are used and data are analysed using statistical software like SPSS, and AMOS. The result is presented using numerical values. Collis and Hussey (2014) characterize positivism as a deductive approach with the aim to quantify data based on a structured methodology for research.

Interpretivism was originally rooted in the fact that there is no universal method that can be used to understand knowledge related to humans and social sciences, because humans interpret their worlds, and act on these interpretations (Hammersley, 2013). Interpretivists believe that reality is multiple and relative, and these numerous realities depend on other functions to form meanings. This makes these relativise more difficult to interpret as fixed facts (Newman, 2001). The knowledge generated in this process is socially constructed, rather than objectively decided (Carson, et al., 2001). Using the interpretivism paradigm, the researcher avoids structural frameworks like positivist researchers follow. They prefer personal and flexible research structures (Carson, et al., 2001). While conducting investigations, interpretivists have some prior knowledge for the research context. They assume that experience is insufficient in developing a research design for the study. Using this method, the researcher remains open to new knowledge throughout the study process, because the goal of interpretive research is to understand human behaviour and interpret meanings, rather than to generalize and predict results (Neuman, 2000). This method is based on an inductive process to provide an interpretive understanding of social phenomena within a context. This is referred to as a phenomenological approach (Collis & Hussey, 2014). This approach interprets everyday experiences for research, and social structures and values are attached to the research process. Furthermore, interpretivism follows a relativist ontology where there are multiple interpretations for original research rather than a single accurate result that can be determined by a measurement process. Therefore, using interpretivism, the researcher will have a better and deeper understanding of the phenomenon and its complications, rather than just discovering knowledge within a community (Creswell, 2014). The advantage of using interpretivism is that it not only describes objects, but also thoroughly figures them out in a social context. Similarly, using this method, the researcher can use grounded theory, ethnography, and case studies to develop deeper knowledge and provide more 'real' information out of analysis (Tuli, 2010).

Some terms associated with positivism include quantitative, objectivist, scientific, experimentalist, traditionalist, or empiricist. In contrast, the interpretative approach is based on qualitative, subjectivist, humanistic, interpretivist or post – positivistic thinking (Saunders, et

al., 2012). Both Paradigm have their strengths and weaknesses, which have highlighted by several researchers (Tuli, 2010).

3.3 RESEARCH APPROACH

The research approach is a plan and procedure which consists of a number of steps that follow the assumptions of the methods of data collection, analysis, and interpretation. The research approach is, therefore based on the nature of the research problem being addressed. There are two general approaches which can be used for conducting research, and these are the deductive, and inductive approach (Mangan, 2004; Saunders et al., 2007). These methods indicate the overall nature of the link between the research and its underpinning theory (Bryman,2004; Collis & Hussey,2003). Saunders et al., (2009) acknowledged that both approaches are linked to a number of different philosophies. Deductive reasoning is related to positivism, whereby inductive approaches are linked to interpretivism. Understanding both approaches is important, and makes it easier to support choices in terms of research approaches.

A deductive approach is concerned with developing a hypothesis based on existing theory, and then a research strategy is designed to test the hypothesis. Using this approach, the researcher deduces assumptions, and translates these into operational terms. These are then checked using statistical methods (Bryman,2004;Sunders et al.,2007). In other words, the deductive approach is concerned with deducing conclusions from premises. The deductive approach analyses a known theory, and later tests if that theory is valid as per the circumstances.

The inductive approach proceeds from a set of observations to build a theory. Using this approach, a theory is introduced by making a few general suggestions concerning what has been observed during a given timescale. The researcher does not apply any theories or hypotheses at the initial stage of the research, and is free to change direction whenever they want after the research process is completed. Generally, the inductive approach is associated with qualitative data collection methods, whereas the deductive approach is related to quantitative methods. As per Saunders et al., (2007) using such approaches in research will make it easy to estimate logical and correct results. However, the researcher needs to choose the right methods for the research. This study is based on qualitative research, so an inductive approach is followed. In contrast, each of the paradigms has both advantages and disadvantages, and each is unique in terms of supplying research using comprehensive tools.

3.4 RESEARCH METHOD

A research method is a strategy to implement a research plan. Research methods can be defined as process and techniques that are used to obtain and analyse research data following processes such as interviews, observations, and questionnaires. (Saunders et al., 2007). The most commonly used research methods are quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods.

3.4.1 QUANTITATIVE RESEARCH METHOD

According to Bryman and Bell (2005, p.154), quantitative research entails "...the collection of numerical data and exhibiting views of the relationship between theory and research as deductive, a predilection for natural science approach, and as having an objectivist conception of social reality". This approach is about quantifying the relationship between variables and evaluating quantitative results. Based on the samples, the variable is measured. The interaction between variables is regulated using statistical methods such as mean, standard deviation, ratios, correlation, regression, and other concise tools (Bryman & Bell, 2011).

The researcher also conceives of quantitative research as providing a conceptual framework in which theories decide the problems that researchers answer in the form of hypothesis extracted from general methods. Both quantitative and qualitative research have equal importance in social sciences. We can see the application of quantitative analysis in subjects like economics to measure supply and demand. Qualitative research generates hypothesis- based evidence (Creswell, 2013:155) where quantitative approaches assist in the study of theory and the data gathered to produce sufficient findings to test if the chosen hypothesis is valid or false. In summary, quantitative approaches accompany qualitative research, as the former allows the latter to quantify how often individuals react, perceive, or behave in a certain way concerning a certain topic. When there are factors to be evaluated, quantitative analysis may also work in social scientific studies. The researcher tends to apply a quantitative methodology if the sampling method is random or simple, and researchers use quantitative analysis to make their experiments reliable. Quantitative research is seen as more accurate as it is data-based (Smith et al.,2008:234). This approach is, however, expensive as compared to qualitative research, because statistical tools or other models are required to check hypotheses.

3.4.2 QUALITATIVE RESEARCH METHOD

Qualitative methodologies, as explained by (Corbin & Strauss, 2008) seek to understand people and their frame of reference. They examine why subjects experience reality as they do. "A qualitative study is appropriate when the goal of the research is to explain a phenomenon

by relying on the perception of a person's experience in a given situation” (Stake, 2010). Furthermore, “qualitative research helps in developing concepts and understanding from a pattern in the data rather than collecting data to evaluate theories Quantitative researchers emphasize precisely measuring variables and testing hypotheses that are linked to general causal explanation” (Neuman, 2001). Qualitative research is a form of social scientific research that gathers and works with non-numerical data. It interprets significance from the data gathered and helps to explain social life by observing target groups or places (Smith et al.,2008:172). This research relates to unquantifiable methods of collecting results. Qualitative work lets the researcher understand more about the phenomena, and gain insight into the behaviours, motives, history, expectations, and attitudes of individuals (Merriam,2009:13). The techniques used in the gathering of data in qualitative research vary from brief responses to clear questions or lengthy, detained open-ended questions. Interpretation and immersion are key, and methods such as in-depth interviews, open-ended polls, focus groups and topic analysis are carried out. Yet qualitative analysis also involves evaluating some unstructured content like customer criticism forms, and report clips (Gummesson,2000:1). Qualitative work takes place in a post-structuralist context. The five areas of qualitative research are case studies, ethnographies, phenomenological studies, grounded theory, and content analysis. Qualitative research focuses on inductive, rather than deductive logic to construct its boundaries. The close association between the observer and the evidence is a notable deviation from quantitative analysis, in which the subject is purely beyond the phenomenon of being considered. Compared to conventional studies, this research study conducts research in a particular way. They allow a few predictions or conclusions logically to generalise related findings (Creswell, 2003). They tend to operate over a longer period because it requires time to get familiar with the social world being analysed.

Quantitative analysis excels in producing very detailed statistics that can have both detrimental and beneficial impacts. One of the strengths of this approach is the ability to investigate more thoroughly the experiences of individuals being observed using qualitative data. Where the researcher may be adversely biased when choosing a sample, they might miss out on raw data, and then the research is less directive. Errors can then occur if the research is difficult to determine (Onwuegbuzie & Leech, 2004).

3.4.3 MIXED METHODS

Mixed methods involve triangulation: an expression used to explain how many types of research are applied to determine data legitimacy (Bryman & Bell, 2011). This method uses both methodological approaches (qualitative and quantitative) during the study phase of data collection and the evaluation procedures (Saunders, et al., 2012). This approach was first applied by Campbell and Fiske (1959), in their work on social sciences and psychology (Schimmack, 2010).

The mixed-method methodological approach to research is an extension of the quantitative and qualitative approach, rather than a substitution, since both research methods remain relevant and significant (Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004). The key goal for the researcher to apply the mixed method tactic in research is to build on the benefits on the research by adopting both methods to investigation to decrease the limitations of the study (Onwuegbuzie & Leech, 2004). The researcher can then conduct study experiments using both quantitative and qualitative approaches that incorporate data collection or data processing techniques. Researchers are now able to validate and develop hypotheses in the same research, and they may also employ deductive and inductive reasoning. Mixed methods allow researchers to design a single research study that responds to questions about both the dynamic nature of the phenomena from the point of view of the participants, and based on the connection between measurable variables (Creswell, 2014).

3.5 JUSTIFICATION FOR QUALITATIVE METHOD FOR THE STUDY

This study was conducted by using qualitative research methods since the aim was to study the issues in depth and in detail. Many researchers have argued that human learning is more accurately researched using qualitative data, and qualitative methods are more accurate than quantitative methods for understanding human behaviour and participants' perceptions of experiences. Qualitative research methods are more realistic and natural and provide detailed information (Maxwell, 2013).

To assess perceptions of service quality in health care, two hospitals in Eastern Nepal were selected. By using qualitative research methods, the researcher had the opportunity to carry out open-ended questions, and create an in-depth understanding to seek answers to the research questions (Berg & Lune, 2011). This method is an effective measure for studying behaviours and perceptions amongst patients (Babbie, 2004). Qualitative research is concerned with in-depth and illustrative information to understand different dimensions. For this study, a deep understanding was needed to obtain results so qualitative research was seen as useful to measure reality, rather than using a quantitative measure.

Quantitative research mostly focuses on objectivity, and this is appropriate if the data are collected from samples of populations. (Moriarty, 2011) notes the successful use of qualitative research in social care. Similarly, Mori & Nakayam (2013) used qualitative studies in health care. Noble & Smith (2015) measured the effectiveness of qualitative methods for service care delivery and examined issues like validity, reliability, and generalizability. Qualitative research has been used in different ways in studies of healthcare systems. In this study, the qualitative design was influenced by the researcher's assumption that a case study style would be the most appropriate research strategy to meet the aims of the study. Compared to quantitative research, qualitative research methods are more powerful and useful to generate in-depth knowledge about the perceptions and experiences of participants. It is possible to then examine behaviours, emotions, and feelings. This is why the researcher chose a qualitative research method to evaluate patient perceptions and satisfaction with hospital services. Hence, qualitative research methods were seen as appropriate to achieve the study aims and objectives.

3.6 RESEARCH DESIGN

The research design is a framework to conduct research. It is the masterplan aspect of the research that shows how the investigation will be done. Factors like philosophical, social, and pragmatic choices can influence the research design. Sekaran (2006) notes that the research design involves identifying specific procedures to obtain results. He adds that it can be either exploratory or conclusive, and this will depend on the quality of the study. The research design guides the researcher as to the collection of data, data analysis and data interpretation (Stiles, 2003). Quantitative research design methods are used to create new knowledge from the data. This is highly objective and uses tools to analyse data.

Qualitative and quantitative research methods are based on different paradigms. Bryman (2016) states that quantitative methods are positioned around objective data, whereby qualitative research is based on rich, deep data. This study aims to measure service quality in Nepalese hospitals relating to patient satisfaction. As such, deep and rich data were required to obtain results. Therefore, a qualitative method has been applied. Qualitative research uses various interpretive paradigms such as positivism, constructivism, critical and feminist and post-structural approaches (Denzin & Lincoln, 2005). For this study, the researcher has selected an interpretive paradigm.

Qualitative research is holistic and follows an inductive approach. The qualitative researcher is highly involved with the subjects involved in the study in order to collect, analyse, and interpret data. The researcher can use several qualitative approaches. Indeed, there are four major models which are commonly used: case study, grounded theory, ethnography, and phenomenology. Which one is used depends on the researcher. For example, case study methods are useful if the researcher wants to reach a solution to a little-known situation. Case studies are based on observations, interviews, and discussions with participants. Ethnography is similar to the case study method as it is used to observe, and spend time with an entire team who shares common values. This method is also based on observation and interviewing. Grounded theory is useful to derive a theory from the views of participants in a study, and this method uses observation and interviewing to build the approach. Phenomenological methods drive at understanding the experiences of participants, as well as their points of view and perceptions. This study applies a case study research design because this allows for an in-depth study of the issues.

Qualitative research uses in-depth interviews to discover underlying knowledge and the

motives of human behaviour. Creswell (2009) argues that qualitative research methods involve collecting data from multiple sources to produce reliable and trustworthy results. Qualitative research methods in health care enable the researcher to provide a descriptive explanation of the experiences and knowledge of participants (Al-Busaidi, 2008). This study was designed to understand patient satisfaction in a hospital in Nepal. Thus, qualitative research provides an in-depth analysis of service quality in Nepalese hospitals. The data in this study were based on in-depth, semi-structured interviews with service users. In-depth interviews are useful to discover the dimensions of service quality in relation to patient satisfaction in Nepalese hospitals. The output is knowledge-data which is based on themes that were developed after the interviews. Previous researchers have used semi-structured interviews in their research, because they offer a range of data due to their unstructured and open-ended nature (Kvale, 2007).

3.7 CASE STUDY

The case study is one of the most frequently used qualitative research methodologies, although it does not have a well-defined structure and protocol. Yin (2003, p.13) defines a case as “a contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context, especially when the boundaries between a phenomenon and context are not clear and the researcher has little control over the phenomenon and context.” The most common definitions used are those advanced by Yin (2014), stake (1995), and Merriam (2009).

A case study is an in-depth study of research questions, rather than a static survey. Using this method, data are gathered from different sources using various methods like observations and interviews. This method helps to test scientific theories to understand if they work in the real world. Yin (2009) suggests the case study is an empirical investigation of the case or cases. According to Yin, the case study follows several approaches; it can be single or multiple in terms of cases. Wilson et al. (2008) suggests “...*case study research is an in-depth analysis of a single or multiple units like the person, or the organisation to provide in-depth data for analysis (p.61).*” Some researchers criticize the case study method, and they believe that studying a small number of cases will not result in reliable and unbiased findings. Some point out that it is useful only as an exploratory tool. Yet a number of researchers continue to use the case study research method to study real situations, issues, and problems. According to Yin (2009) a case study research approach helps to resolve ‘why’ and ‘how’ problems when investigating through research. This presents a strong argument to adopt a case study approach

for this research since the research questions are mainly ‘why’ and ‘how’ in nature. For example, the aims is to discover ‘why service quality is important in hospitals’ and ‘how service quality is important in influencing customer satisfaction and future purchase intentions’ (Yin, 2009).

Furthermore, there is very little literature available on the context of hospitals in Nepal, which in itself creates a research opportunity. According to Luck et al., (2006), in the context of health care research, case study research is a “bridge across paradigms”. Simons (2009), Stake (2006) and Stewart (2014) note that case study methods can be used to study various topics for a range of purposes.

The first step using this method is to determine and define the research questions (Ozuem et al., 2008). To establish the case for this study, it pays to follow Yin’s (2009) advice, and to explain the question which the case study aims to answer. The first research question for this study is ‘why is service quality important for health care and customer satisfaction?’. This research question is about investigating service quality, and the functional and technical quality of the hospital. The case aims to examine customer perceptions of the service quality dimensions. The second research question is ‘how is service quality perceived by customers in the health care sectors of Nepal’?. This research question aims to investigate customer perceptions of service and attitudes towards the service provided by hospitals in Nepal. This research question will help to illuminate the importance of service quality in hospitals.

This research adopts an interpretive assumption using qualitative research methods because of the nature of the research question. As such, a case study methodology was seen as an appropriate approach to obtain in-depth knowledge of the data. Thus, the aim is to investigate the relationship between service quality and satisfaction in terms of health care. Therefore, to refine the theory, an explanatory case study method was chosen, which will help to extend more knowledge about service quality in health care in Nepal.

3.8 PILOT STUDY

Qualitative interviews deliver detailed information to understand the experiences of people. However, it can be difficult for new or inexperienced researcher to adequately perform interviews. Discussions are used to collect most of the data in qualitative research which will help the researcher to understand the phenomenon from the point of view of participants

(Merriam, 1998). A pilot study can be defined as a “small study to test research protocols, data collection methods, sampling strategies, and other techniques for research to be prepared for a large study.” The pilot study has become one of the most important stages in a research project. Conducting a pilot study helps to identify potential problem areas using research methods before starting the ‘live’ study. It can also help researchers to become familiar with the procedures of the study and the interview process. The pilot study is generally carried out on different people with relevant experience, but not on those who will be part of the final interviews (Patton, 2015). A pilot study was conducted in one of the hospitals of Nepal before the collection of data took place. The study was undertaken on a sample of 10 individuals possessing the same characteristics as the main participants. A pilot study aims to test and evaluate interview questions, and to test the suitability of research tools. After the pilot study interview, a short discussion was carried out with the participants to obtain feedback on the research questions and to listed to experiences of the process. Some of the participants suggested alterations for some of the issues, and merging questions around themes. Some of the questions which appeared less important were deleted.

3.9 SAMPLE STUDY

As with any study, the selection of the sample is an important process during data collection, as a target population, community or area of study must be identified first before commencing data collection. Sampling is the process or method which helps the researcher to determine the number in the population, and to reduce the amount of data, rather than selecting the entire community for the research process (Saunders, et al., 2012). Sampling is mainly grouped into two types: probability and non – probability sampling. Probability sampling is commonly used by quantitative researchers where there are standard methods and criteria for the selection of the population, and the participants have an equal opportunity to get selected (Bryman & Bell, 2011). Non–probability sampling method is mainly used by qualitative researchers. Non – probability sampling is about selecting samples on the basis of the subjective judgment of the researcher. This represents the group of examples which will help the researcher to choose the units from the population which are experienced and interested in the study. In this case, the possibility of being included in the targeted sample is unknown (Saunders & Townsed, 2016). In qualitative research, a typical method of sampling is purposive, where the aim to generate an in-depth understanding of the research topic and questions (Patton, 2002). Purposive sampling helps to select or identify participants who can provide rich information and are

knowledgeable or experienced with the phenomena of interest (Creswell, 2014). In addition to the experienced and knowledgeable groups or individuals, Bernard (2002) and Spradley (1979) note the importance of the availability of participants, and their willingness to participate. They also discuss the importance of their ability to communicate their experiences and opinions and ideas in a clear and reflective manner. (Morse & Niehaus, 2009) argue that regardless of whether the research methodology is quantitative or qualitative, sampling methods help to maximize efficiency and validity.

Patton (2002) describes several strategies for purposeful sampling, which are intended to serve different purposes. These strategies are summarised below:

TABLE 4 SAMPLING STRATEGY

	Sampling strategy	Illustration
1	Extreme or deviant sampling	Learning from highly unusual conditions involves selecting illuminative cases.
2.	Intensity sampling	Involves selecting studies which are an excellent or rich example, but not extreme cases.
3.	Maximum variation (Heterogeneity) sampling	Maximum variation cases are selected, which vary from each other as much as possible.
4.	Homogenous sample	Picking a similar and homogenous sample which helps to understand and describe the subgroup in depth.
5.	Typical case sampling	Typical cases are mainly selected with the cooperation of key informants or using statistical data.
6.	Critical case sampling	One case is chosen, which is important for the study.

7.	Snowball or chain sampling	Involves seeking information from key people about the details of others who are informatively rich for the case.
8.	Criterion sampling	Involves reviewing and studying the cases which meet some predetermined criterion of importance.
9.	Theory-based, operation construct and theoretical sampling	This is similar to criterion sampling, but it is more conceptually focused. People or incidents are samples based on whether or not they represent the study.
10.	Confirming and disconfirming cases	Involves exploring the emerging pattern and then looking for other examples that fit the emerging model.
11.	Stratified purposeful sampling	Similar to stratified random sampling, where the sample is based on a characteristic. A sample is a group of below average, average, and above average cases. Different groups of the population are included in the sample.
12.	Opportunistic or emergent sampling	A further sample is chosen at the process of data collection where the researcher is opened to sampling a group or person which they may not have planned to interview.
14.	Purposeful random sampling	This involves choosing a sample randomly.
15.	Sampling politically important cases	This involves sampling a politically important case.
16.	Convenience sampling	Involves choosing a sample which is fast and convenient.

17	Combination or mixed purposeful sampling	Involves a combination of different sample strategies.
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TABLE 5 : SAMPLING STRATEGIES {PATTON (2002)}

This study follows a qualitative research approach, so the researcher has chosen nonprobability and purposive sampling as part of the strategy. Most qualitative researchers use purposive sampling as this means it is easier to select participants which are “information-rich” (Patton, 2014). Despite its regular use, there are some challenges associated with identifying and applying an appropriate purposeful sampling strategy. According to Robson (2002), the main limitation of this sample is that there is the possibility of bias while choosing the sample, as they are chosen without using a standardised method. As such, the validation and generalisability of the research are quite controversial (Bryman & Bell, 2011).

For this study, a mixed purposeful sampling approach was used as the sample population was selected based on their experience of using the service provided by the hospital. Many qualitative studies adopt nonprobability purposive sampling, since this procedure involves selecting participants using judgement (Miles, et al., 2014). For this study, a form of purposeful sampling was applied. Participants were selected based on the experience they had gained using the service provided by the public and private hospitals in the study. The researcher tried to eliminate bias in the sampling process by approaching a number of hospital users and discussing their experience with the hospital.

The main advantage of using nonprobability purposive sampling is it can provide a higher response rate of participants and it is a less expensive method. This method follows an easy process to choosing a sample, and it is useful for in-depth interviews. As such, the researcher decided to use this method due to the nature of the study linked to the sampling method. This sampling method means it is possible to select a sample that will fit the needs of the research.

3.10 SAMPLE SIZE AND DATA COLLECTION METHOD

It is important to take an adequate number of participants into account in research as this is an important feature of any empirical study. Samples for qualitative studies are generally lower

compared to samples used in quantitative studies (Ritchie & Lewis, 2003). This is because qualitative research methods mostly focus on obtaining an in-depth understanding of the research, which is mainly centred around how and why answers to research questions. Qualitative research is mostly used purposefully or based on a criterion-based sampling strategy where quantitative analysis works for random sampling strategies (Patton, 2015). In qualitative research, it is difficult to identify the precise number of participants required for data collection, which can lead to bias decisions (Patton, 2015). However, in qualitative studies, it is important to find a saturation point for data collection. At this point, the researcher realises that conducting more interviews will not add any new information to the study (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2010b; Lincoln and Guba, 1985). In qualitative research, the sample selection for an interview depends on the nature of the study. As qualitative research normally uses mixed sampling strategies, this makes it possible to access an informative sample. The size of the sample depends on the types of answers required as well as the purpose of the research and what data will be useful (Patton, 2014). Many researchers have pointed out that it is important to identify saturation in the process of data collection. Saturation is when further data does not add new findings to the research (Charmaz, 2011). In qualitative research, the average number of participants is between 30 and 35 (Saunders & Townsed, 2016) where Creswell (2009) suggests no fewer than 10 participants for in-depth interviews.

3.10.1 SIZE OF THE DATA

For this research, the sample size consists of 27 semi-structured interviews with service users of hospitals, and five in-depth interviews with hospital employees. The total number of participants for this research was 32. Out of the 32 participants, 17 were male and 15 were female. The Fig (9) diagram shows the number of male and female participants for the study.

FIGURE 9: DIAGRAM OF NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS

The samples were chosen from 1 private hospital and 1 public hospital from the eastern part of Nepal. Each hospital represents 16 participants, and this is based on non-probability random sampling. The below diagram Fig (10) shows the participants from respective hospitals.

FIGURE 10: DIAGRAM OF PARTICIPANTS OF EACH HOSPITAL

There were three age categories which were 18-30 years, 31-45 years and 46-60 years. The figure 11 shows the maximum number of participants were from the 31-45 years age group (15 participants). There were 13 participants aged 18-30 years, and 4 participants aged 46-60 years.

FIGURE 11: NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS ACCORDING TO AGE GROUP

The focus of the interview was to understand the types of service provided by the hospitals. All interviews took place in hospitals at a place and time of the participant's choosing. The meeting durations varied 45 minutes to 60 minutes. Following each of the interviews, the researcher noted that the length of the conversation did not dictate the quality of information received. All interviews were summarised in a notebook and recorded in a digital format. Informed and written consent was gained from the participants before each interview.

The list of participants who took part is reproduced below. The interviews were conducted in both private (BIRAT) and public hospitals (KOSHI) as categorized below:

No	Age	Gender	Occupation	Hospital	Code
1	31-45	F	Housewife	Koshi /Public	P1
2	18-30	M	Businessman	Koshi /Public	P2
3	18-30	M	Office Worker	Birat/Private	P3
4	18-30	M	Sales Manager	Birat/Private	P4
5	31-45	F	Housewife	Birat/Private	P5

6	31-45	M	Teacher	Koshi /Public	P6
7	18-30	F	Nurse	Birat/Private	P7
8	31-45	F	Teacher	Birat/Private	P8
9	18-30	F	Student	Koshi /Public	P9
10	31-45	M	Farmer	Koshi /Public	P10
11	31-45	M	Factory Worker	Koshi /Public	P11
12	31-45	F	Nurse	Koshi /Public	P12
13	18-30	F	Bank Staff	Birat/Private	P13
14	31-45	M	Factory Worker	Koshi /Public	P14
15	31-45	F	Housewife	Birat/Private	P15
16	46-60	M	Teacher	Birat/Private	P16
17	46-60	M	Health Assistant	Birat/Private	P17
18	18-30	F	Nurse	Koshi /Public	P18
19	31-45	M	Teacher	Birat/Private	P19
20	31-45	M	Professor	Koshi /Public	P20
21	31-45	M	Bus Driver	Koshi /Public	P21
22	31-45	F	Professor	Koshi /Public	P22
23	46-60	M	Farmer	Koshi /Public	P23
24	18-30	M	Nurse Student	Birat/Private	P24
25	18-30	F	Student	Birat/Private	P25
26	31-45	M	Fashion Designer	Birat/Private	P26
27	18-30	F	Nurse	Birat/Private	P27
28	18-30	M	Health Assistant	Birat/Private	P28
29	31-45	F	Head Nurse	Birat/Private	P29
30	46-60	M	Senior Health Assistant	Koshi /Public	P30
31	18-30	F	Nurse	Koshi /Public	P31
32	18-30	F	Nurse	Koshi /Public	P32

All discussions were recorded successfully and it has been suggested (Brymann & Bell, 2011) that recoding interviews provides plenty of time for the researcher to analyse results. Moreover, recording the interviews makes participants feel more important, and their views can be taken seriously (Berg, 2007). Audio recording is also more time consuming than writing.

3.11 SEMI-STRUCTURED IN-DEPTH INTERVIEW

The interviews were semi-structured in nature. This method of interviewing is based on both open and closed questions, because of the semi-structured nature. Questions for these interviews are attached as appendix 5. Semi-structured in-depth interviews are commonly used to conduct qualitative research (Robson,2007). This method consists of a dialogue between researcher and participant. This is also a useful way for researchers to collect open-ended data to explore participants' feelings, thoughts and beliefs in relation to the topic. Using this approach, it is possible to explore personal and sometimes even sensitive issues (Gioia, et al., 2013). The main purpose of semi-structured interviews is to understand the experiences of participants with the research problem to uncover the deeper meaning of the research problem (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2009). Based on a semi-structured interview, the researcher has greater power to focus on the in-depth issue of the research problem than in an unstructured interview. The researcher can use different probing questions to elicit more knowledge around the research problem. The researcher needs to undertake background research and identify the aims of the study before conducting in-depth interviews (Kvale, 1996). To make the interview successful, the interviewers must have the right skills to ask questions that will produce relevant data for the case study (Berg & Lune, 2011). Interviewers must know what and when to ask, and when to listen. It is also important that the interviewer shows an interest in the participants, regardless of what they are saying.

The interviews were conducted in private and public hospitals in Eastern Nepal. The timeframe (up to 60 minutes) helped to capitalise on the concentration of the interviewees (Robson, 2002). All the interviews conducted were rendered down into themes. The recordings were made with the permission of the participants. One of the hardest parts of conducting the interviews was setting up and arranging these. The process for setting up the interviews was to identify appropriate participants, arrange a suitable time and location for the interview, and to reassure the participants about confidentiality and anonymity. For the purposes of interviewing, some 32 participants were selected, 28 of whom were patients who had used the services of this hospital. A further 6 were hospital staff: 3 from each hospital. These included hospital staff who helped the researcher to understand the perspectives of hospital management towards patient perceptions. Furthermore, interviews helped the researcher to understand the personal experiences of participants. The interview result helped the researcher to analyse problems with Nepalese hospitals in terms of delivering quality services.

After the participants who agreed to participate in the interview were told about the process of the interview, they were asked to sign a consent form to indicate they were happy to take part. The consent form is attached in the appendix 4. After signing the consent form, the participants were asked to indicate a location where they would be comfortable being interviewed. It is important to choose a convenient location since this can have a positive impact on outcomes (Saunders, et al., 2012). Most participants preferred the garden area of the hospital, as well as canteens. All of the interviews were conducted in the hospital at a time that was convenient to the participants. Interview times varied for each interview, and each interview lasted between 45 minutes to 1 hr. All interviews were performed in the Nepali language, and all interviews were recorded with the consent of participants. The length of conversations did not influence the volume and quality of the data collected. All the interviews were recorded, and notes were taken by the researcher. Bryman and Bell (2011) suggest that recording interviews helps interviewers to concentrate on the interview, and recording the interviews will make participants feel that they are being taken seriously (Berg & Lune, 2011). The interview questions were semi-structured, so the researcher adjusted some questions and added new questions where this was felt necessary.

The advantage of using semi-structured interviews is to attempt to understand the life story of participants and to uncover the deeper meaning in terms of the research problem (Kvale, 2007). An interviewer should dig deep for information if needed, and the most important thing is that the interviewer must practice “active listening”, which is listening carefully to participants and evaluating research questions and the answers given by participants (Morgan, 2006).

Some researchers criticise semi-structured interviews and see these as time consuming and challenging (Brinkmann, 2013). Indeed, it is challenging to find an interviewer with the right amount of knowledge to conduct interviews. Sometimes, the interviewer will interpret the result, which can lead to biased findings (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2009).

After completing the interviews, and to gather more data and double-check data, the researcher organised focus groups discussions with hospital medical staff which were doctor nurse and hospital management, and some participants to get a deeper understanding of the topic. Focus group discussions helped the researcher to elicit more knowledge about the problems the participants had experienced (Saunders, et al., 2012). Howell (2013) argues that focus group discussions help researchers to understand participants more. Customers are influenced by their

experience and by recommendations about services, so their perceptions revealed much about the quality of the services they received. The discussion took around 60 minutes, and the researcher was able to receive sufficient data for the study. During the discussion, the researcher found that perceptions of service quality varied greatly. Focus group discussions helped the researcher to obtain in-depth insight into Nepalese hospital service quality. The attitudes and opinions of the participants were captured nearly in this way.

3.12 RESEARCHER REFLEXIBILITY

The term reflexivity describes the process by which the researcher reflects upon the collection of data and the interpretation process. Research reflexivity is an important factor in qualitative methods. While conducting qualitative research, the researcher's thoughts and feelings can change and so reflexivity helps them to think about what change has occurred, and whether this is good change. Thus, reflexivity is an important part of any research findings. During the research process, the researcher often finds themselves in deep thought about their aspirations, characters, values, experiences, belief, and commitment, and they frequently reflect on how these have shaped their research. Reay (2007, p. 611) argues that reflexivity is "about giving as full and honest an account of the research process as possible, in particular explicating the position of the researcher about the research." One of the most important lessons for me is that research is subject to both the power and limitations of social change and development.

In this study, reflexivity helped me with my role recognition. I was working in the hospital for two years when I was doing my Bachelor's degree in Nepal. Therefore, I was inspired to carry out research into the quality of service provided by hospitals in Nepal. My experience of working in hospitals helped me to understand research problems, and the problems that Nepalese hospitals encounter in terms of service quality. I was working under hospital management, for this reason I became familiar with the procedures that Nepalese hospitals follow in providing treatment. This encouraged me to ask participants further questions during the interviews which inspired confidence in the participants. Various researchers have argued that participants feel confident and comfortable to talk with researchers if they think that they have some knowledge of the topic (Perry et al., 2014). I was born and brought up in Nepal, so to carry out research in Nepal was easy and convenient for me. The interviews were conducted in the Nepali language since that is that language that is spoken in Nepal. Interviewing in the native language also helps to build rapport and it was also easier for me to understand the

expressions, feelings, and thoughts of participants during the interviews. While conducting the interviews, I was continuously writing in my diary. Many researchers have mentioned the importance of keeping notes for qualitative research (Bryman & Bell, 2011).

3.13 VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY IN QUALITATIVE RESEARCH

Validity and reliability in qualitative research are essential factors which need to be considered by all qualitative researchers in developing a study, and when analyzing the results. These are also important when judging the quality of research (Patton, 2002). Furthermore, Patton (2001) states that the two most important factors are reliability and validity. These should be considered by all qualitative researchers while conducting the study, analyzing the result, and remarking on the quality of the study. The accuracy, dependability and credibility of the research depend on reliability and validity. In quantitative analysis, the term reliability refers to the ability to replicate the results of the study, whereas in qualitative research, there is no chance of any replication. Terms like quality, rigor or trustworthiness are about more than just validity and dependability, and also include reliability (Davies & Dodd, 2002; Lincoln & Guba, 1985; Mishler, 2000; Seale, 1999; Stenbacka, 2001). The term validity and reliability are explained in the next section.

3.13.1 RELIABILITY

Stenbacka (2001, p. 551) defines “reliability as the extent to which results are consistent over time and an accurate representation of the total population under study is referred to as reliability, and if the results of a study can be reproduced under a similar methodology, then the research instrument is considered to be reliable.” Reliability is the consistency of the measurement of subjects in the same way again, and again and it is also known as the repeatability of the analysis, while reliability is estimated rather than measured. The approach of reliability as a criterion through which qualitative research can be judged based on the positivist or postpositivist paradigm (Guba, 1981). According to Bryman and Bell (2011), reliability in research checks the consistency of the research method. According to Krippendorff (1980), reliability can be assured in three ways: “1) stability – measures the extent that the same coder is consistent over the time, 2) inter-coder reliability – the same results are produced even by the different coders for the same content, 3) accuracy – the extent to which the grouping or categorization of text corresponds with set criteria or standards.” These three principals were introduced and used by several qualitative researchers.

3.13.2 TRUSTWORTHINESS:

According to Golafshani (2003), examining the trustworthiness of research is key to maintaining reliability in qualitative research. The researcher has tried to maintain trustworthiness in this research by sharing the results with the administrative department of the hospital to make it more reliable. Guba (1981) proposes four criteria which he believes must be considered by qualitative researchers seeking to carry out trustworthy studies. The four methods to maintain trustworthy for the research are credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability.

3.13.3 DEPENDABILITY:

Dependability is more important than trustworthiness as it establishes consistent and repeatable findings in research studies. Dependability in qualitative research was described by Guba (1981) in preference to reliability in qualitative research. Dependability can be established through several techniques like an external audit. In this study, to maintain dependability, the researcher used the phone to record interviews, and a diary was kept for notetaking. A computer was used to preserve the data.

3.13.4 VALIDITY IN QUALITATIVE RESEARCH:

Validity is the important factors which needs to be considered by the researchers for the qualitative study during the designing of the study and interpreting the results. Validity in qualitative research means that the research question of the desired outcome (Patton, 2015). Previously, some qualitative researchers have argued that validity does not apply to qualitative research, but it is accepted now that there is a need for quality checks in qualitative studies (Creswell & Miller, 2000). According to (Merriam, 1998) validity is concerned with whether the researcher has measured the right concept or not. It is about the appropriateness of the choice of methodology for the research question, the design of the methodology and the data analysis and sampling process. It is also about scrutinizing the result and the conclusion in the context of the study. The extent to which the result drawn from the research gives correct information about the study is key (Yin, 2009). The researcher carried out interviews after making appropriate time for the participants. Then, the researcher conducted a pilot study, which was carried out to measure the reliability and validity of the study.

3.13.5 CREDIBILITY:

Credibility in qualitative research is the confidence to find the truth. Previously, the term credibility was identified as a goal for the internal validation of qualitative research (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). Guba (1985) stated, “credibility in qualitative research for the internal validity of the study.” Furthermore, it was mentioned that assuring credibility relates to efforts to bring confidence into an authentic analysis of the data. Credibility in qualitative research can be established through prolonged commitment, constant observation, triangulation, negative case analysis, and members checks. Credibility in qualitative research can be assured by adopting well-established practices. In this study, a case study method was applied to conduct research. Furthermore, (Yin, 2009) argues that it is important to adopt an appropriate approach to maintain internal validity in research. Similarly, credibility helps to provide a holistic and contextual context (Bryman & Bell, 2011). Another method to maintain credibility in qualitative research is described by Shenton (2004) who suggests making sure that you have earned the trust of participants while conducting interviews. This can be achieved by giving participants that option to refuse to participate.

In summary, reliability and validity are the key indicators for the measurement of any study. Reliability focuses on the consistence of results over time, and the accuracy of the sample size whereby validity determines the depth of research, and whether it is on the right track or not. It is important to measure the truthfulness of research results (Kazi & Khalid, 2012). Validity is about the trustworthiness of the methods used to produce findings that accurately reflect the data. Patton (2002) argues that qualitative researchers should not neglect the concept of validity and reliability when designing a study. Analyzing, and judging quality is instrumental. For qualitative research, trustworthiness is crucial to ensure reliability.

3.14 DATA INVESTIGATION

The collection of data and analysis are two separate steps in research. However, they are interrelated with each other in a circular process. Analyzing qualitative data is challenging due to subjective interpretation. It is also complicated to conduct research and communicate. If the interviewer misrepresents the respondent's answers during the analysis process, this could lead to issues with reliability and trustworthiness. After the interviews were completed, the recorded data were manually transcribed and were kept safely in Word files. For data analysis, the guidelines established by Braun & Clarke (2006) were followed. The themes can be initially produced inductively from raw data or can be produced deductively from a theory or previous research { (Boyatzis, 1998); (Braun & Clarke, 2006)}. Using an inductive approach, the themes generated are clearly linked with the data themselves, and bear little relation to the questions that are asked during interviews. In contrast to the deductive approach, the themes are generated from the researcher's theoretical interest, and less explanation of the overall data tends to be produced (Braun & Clarke, 2006). For this research, inductive thematic analysis was used to interpret data to understand the process of the quality of services in hospitals in Nepal (Ozuem, et al., 2015).

To develop codes from the qualitative data, NVivo software was used. NVivo helps to build systems and themes for thematic analysis. This software was used to filter words which were said frequently during interviews. The initial data analysis was carried out by reading the transcript line recorded during interviews and by then generating the codes. The aim of re-reading each line of transcribed data, and examining the data was to become familiar with the data so the initial codes could be generated. After completing the 32 interviewees, some of the codes generated were repeated; therefore, NVivo was used to filter the codes. After the initial stage, the second phase was to reduce the data and generate detailed and selective coding. A data reduction process was carried out until the logic matched with the research problems and objectives. The data were examined and matched with the research objectives and question to ensure the generated themes could provide a clear pattern of research questions. The generated themes and data were stored on the computer, and a word processor, which made it easier to assign, delete and reassign the codes easily. The six steps followed by Braun and Clarke (2006) to analyze data are illustrated below. DeSantis and Ugarriza (2000) define themes as “*abstract entities that bring meaning and identity to a recurrent experience and its variant*

manifestations. As such, a theme captures and unifies the nature or basis of the experience into a meaningful whole.” The following figure shows the data analysis process.

Phase	Procedures of each step
1. Familiarising with data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reproducing and interpreting data, • Reading and re-reading the raw data, writing down initial codes.
2. Developing Initial Codes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coding interesting features of the data in a systematic fashion across the data set, • collating data relevant to each code. • Code generation was guided by the type of questions that were asked. • Codes are extracted based on the ideas.
3. Searching for the Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collating codes into potential themes, gathering all data relevant to each possible theme. • Mind mapping and visualisation of codes into the themed. • Creation of the themes from the data and creating a thematic map.
4. Reviewing the themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reviewing the main themes, Sub-themes, and other extracts. • Checking if the themes work concerning the coded extracts and the entire dataset. • Deleting the no related themes. • Generate a thematic map. • Coding of the data if missed in the beginning.

<p>5. Defining and Naming the Themes</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ongoing analysis to refine the specifics of each theme and transcript. • Arranging the main themes • generation of clear names for each theme. • Understanding the named themes.
<p>6. Generating Report</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The final opportunity of analysis selecting appropriate extracts; discussion of the investigation, relating the produce report with research question and literature. • Reporting on the selected main themes and extracting the logical data from the conveyed story.

Table 7: Data Analysis Process (Source: Adapted from Braun and Clarke (2006))

Phase 1 – Familiarizing with the data:

This is the first step of thematic analysis. During this process, the researcher prepares the verbatim transcript (Poland, 1995). The researcher reads and re-reads the notes and listens to the recorded interviews to get ideas and to elicit meaning, themes and codes.

Phase 2 – Developing Initial codes:

The second step begins when the researcher is familiar with the data. This stage involves the production of initial codes for the data. Coding can be done manually, or the software program can be used. The researcher used NVivo for coding.

Phase 3 – Searching for themes: This stage focusses on the wider level of the themes and involves sorting the different codes into potential themes. During this phase, the researcher used mind maps to type codes. At the end of this phase, the researcher was able to collect the items and sub-themes.

Phase 4 – Reviewing Themes: This phase involves the refinement of themes. Some themes are collapsed into other themes, whereas others are broken down into smaller components.

Phase 5 – Defining and naming themes: This phase captures the essence of what each theme is about, and what aspect of the data each theme captures. During this stage, the researcher officially names the themes that are generated. The researcher was able to identify which themes were not clear. After the themes are reviewed a final thematic map was produced. The researcher was able to describe each theme at the end of this phase.

Phase 6 – Generating a report: The last step of data analysis involves the final review of themes and writing up a report. The report should be logical and should present an interesting story based on the data, and they should be coherent and within the context of the study. The researcher should convey the data logically.

3.15 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Ethical consent is vital to protect both the participants and the researchers. Several researchers have noted that the protection of human rights is mandatory in health care research (Kvale, 1996). It protects the dignity, rights, and safety of the participants and it also supports the right to carry out ethical research. As Saunders et al, (2009) state, ethics are an important element that need to be followed when conducting the study, and it is important to consider ethics throughout the research design. The basic ethical principles in the process of data collection are that there should be no harm caused to participants because they participated in the research (Ozdemir & Hewett, 2010)). Denzin and Lincoln (2000) argue that researchers should take extreme care to avoid harm to participants and researchers should respect the participant's dignity, privacy, and confidentiality.

For this study, ethical approval was obtained at two levels to conduct the study. First, an ethics application was approved by the board of ethics of the University of the West of Scotland. The correspondence letters (Appendix 1) provided by the University of West of Scotland was sent to both hospitals in Nepal to get permission to conduct interviews for the study. Secondly, an approval letter from the hospitals where the study was conducted (Please see Appendix) was obtained. Permission to conduct the study was granted by both hospitals before starting the study. The ethical considerations addressed by this study were concerned with providing adequate information about the study. A signed informed consent form was obtained to maintain the participants' privacy and trust. Before the research was conducted, an information

sheet and consent form was provided to participants. The purpose of research was explained to them. Before starting the research, participants were told about the research problem and their role within the research process.

In addition, the researcher told the participants that they had the right to withdraw from the study at any time if they felt uncomfortable. They were reminded their participation was voluntary. To maintain this, each participant was provided with a consent form and asked to sign this before taking part in the study (see appendix 4). Informed, and written consent was obtained from the participants before commencing.

This research focuses on service quality in Nepalese healthcare. Interviews with the service users was performed in their preferred location, whereas in the case of the health workers, discussions were held at their place of work. The meetings were held in a quiet place, and formal consent was obtained to record the interview. Each participant was informed about the recording of the interview before the start of the interview. All recordings were coded and saved securely to maintain confidentiality. The principle of confidentiality and anonymity was followed by the researcher for the participants throughout the process (Oliver,2003; Babbie, 2004). The interviews were conducted in the way how participants want. Permission from the participant was obtained to state their job titles in research.

3.16 SUMMARY OF THE CHAPTER

This chapter has identified the research design, and research methodology that was undertaken. Other factors like the sample size, research community, sampling process, research tools and data interpretation methods used for the study were also identified in this chapter. The chapter also presented a detailed account of how the research was undertaken. It identified the study population and sampling, software used for data processing. A discussion of ethical considerations was provided that defined the process of obtaining ethical approval from the university. Qualitative methods have been identified as a suitable methodological approach for this study. The chapter identified a suitable research strategy based on qualitative methods. This research explores the problems and experiences of patients in hospitals of Nepal, so qualitative methods were seemed as effective methods to understand the real experiences of these customers through interviews. Face to face semi-structured in-depth interviews were conducted to collect data and identify themes from the participants using a sampling strategy. Semi-structured and in-depth interviews reveal the root causes of problems by generating

questions about the situation. The interview data were analysed using NVivo qualitative data analysis software, whereas thematic analysis was used to generate themes to address the research questions.

A pilot study was conducted before gathering data and this was useful to identify some issues with reliability and validity, which are often associated with qualitative research. Finally, the chapter identified various ethical considerations and explained how these were addressed in the research process. The next section discusses the qualitative findings of the study and identifies the major themes identified after conducting interviews with hospital service users and providers. The themes were generated using a method described by Braun & Clarke (2006): thematic data analysis. The six-step process described by Braun and Clarke is widely embraced within qualitative data analysis. The major themes are identified in the next section.

4 CHAPTER FOUR QUALITATIVE FINDINGS

4.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter contains a discussion and analysis of the themes that emerged from face-to-face semi-structured interviews conducted with 32 participants. It presents a study of the responses from interviews around service quality in hospitals in Nepal. The results are presented as thematic codes which were generated after the completion of interviews. In this chapter, the themes and sub-themes are described in detail. The study mainly focuses on the six major issues that emerged from semi-structured in-depth interviews. The six themes represent patient perceptions of the quality of services provided by hospitals in Nepal.

The researcher describes thematic analysis, and its attendant processes using Braun and Clarke's (2006) suggestions. The main themes are presented in a table alongside the subthemes, and keywords used by the participants in the interviews. Data analysis was carried out by thoroughly examining the narrative transcripts from the interviews. The researcher also used NVivo qualitative data analysis software to filter the codes and themes. The researcher used paper and notes to write ideas that emerged during the process of data analysis. Further, the researcher broadly explains the meaning of the themes, and has identifies the keywords that are related to the themes.

To support the themes of the study, direct quotes from participants are introduced. The researcher explains the feelings of participants using story narrative. The section also explains the perceptions of participants based on the interviews. Although real-world experience is different from written accounts of experience, the researcher decided to produce all of the experiences in story form. The chapter ultimately addresses the research questions.

4.2 RATIONALE FOR THEMATIC ANALYSIS

This study uses thematic analysis to analyse data (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Qualitative interviews were the main method used in this research to obtain answers about service quality in hospitals in Nepal. Qualitative interviews provide new insight into a social phenomenon because they allow the participants to reflect and reason on multiple subjects in multiple ways (Folkestad,2008, p.1). For this research, interviewing service users and providers was seen as a convincing option. Since the interviews were the primary measures for data collection, it was important to be mindful of the types of data analysis. Thematic analysis is the most widely used approach to analyse qualitative data.

The term thematic analysis was introduced by Gerald Holton in the 1970s (Merton,1975) since a number of researchers had developed a version of thematic analysis to analyse qualitative data (e.g., Aronson,1994, Boyatzis 1998, Joffe & Yardley,2004). No single version had achieved brand recognition. However, in 2006, critical Psychologist Virginia Braun and Victoria Clarke proposed an approach to thematic analysis. Thematic analysis is a method for identifying and analysing patterns of meaning or themes in qualitative data (Braun & Clarke, 2006). They presented TA as an analytical method, rather than a methodology. They sought to avoid prescribing theoretical assumptions and identifying ‘appropriate’ research questions or ways of doing data collection.

Based on this research, inductive thematic analysis is adopted to analyse the data generated from interviews to understand the importance of service quality in hospitals. Qualitative interviews were carried out to obtain a proper perspective on the research questions. Such an approach gives new insight into a social phenomenon as it allows respondents to reflect and reason on a variety of subjects in different ways (Folkestad,2008, p1).

For this study, an inductive thematic analytical approach is adopted to interpret the interview data (Boyatzis, 1998); (Tuckett, 2005)) and to interpret service quality in Nepalese hospitals. Using an inductive approach, the identified themes are strongly connected to the data themselves (Patton, 2015). Based on this approach, when data are collected through the interview process, the themes identified from the interview may be connected to a distinct research question asked of participants. As such, inductive analysis is, therefore, “*a process of coding the data without trying to fit it into a pre-existing coding frame.*” Customer service quality is a psychological process, and therefore, it is important to analyse human behaviour to

provide better quality. In this study, the interview is the main source of data collection, and the interview questions were created based on both theoretical and experiential knowledge. Semi-structured and in-depth interview methods were adopted to explore the issues and to obtain rich data. During the interview process, participants were guided throughout the conversation. The data analysis was conducted inductively using a bottom-up approach (Patton, 2014). The data themes were identified after analysing the transcribed interviews, and the data analysis process followed the guidelines which were established by Braun and Clarke (2006). This method was chosen to become more familiar with the data. Indeed, the thematic approach complemented the research questions by facilitating an analysis of interview data from two perspectives: the data-driven perspective, and the research question perspective. Transcripts of the interviews were read in detail and were examined to check if the data were consistent with the research question, and to see if they provided sufficient information.

Therefore, after completing twelve interviews, some of the codes were generated, and NVivo software was used to filter these. NVivo software makes analytical work more efficient. The words which present key ideas about the data were grouped as thematic codes. After conducting the interviews, the interview transcript was re-read to better understand the key points that participants talked about most. Codes were grouped with the use of a thematic map. After that themes were identified, the researcher doubled checked the data analysis to improve its trustworthiness, credibility, and validity. The themes identified are presented below.

Themes	Definition	Codes	Keywords
Environmental quality	Environmental quality refers to the appearance of physical facilities, equipment in the hospital, the atmosphere of the hospital and patient safety in the hospital.	1. Hospital Physical facilities 2. Atmosphere 3. Patient safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hospital building • Physical facilities at the hospital • Equipment • Technology • Employees • Waiting room • Check-up room • Hospital beds • The clean and comfortable environment of the hospital. • Enough beds and chairs for patient and visitors. • Tools and equipment used to perform the service.

Interpersonal quality	Interpersonal care refers to the personalized care provided to patients with respect and empathy.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Manner 2. Empathy 3. Responsiveness 4. Courtesy 5. communication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Care • Manner • respect • the clear connection between the service provider and patient. • understanding • Courteous and respectful to the patient • Indifferent to patients • Arguments with patients • Access to staff, services, information • Clear appropriate and timely communication • Applicable service for customer needs • Individualized attention
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<p>Technical service quality</p>	<p>Technical quality in the hospital refers to reliable service, the process of care, expert staff, and better treatment.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reliability 2. Process of care in hospital 3. Outcomes 4. Expertise 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check-up • Treatment • Emergency service • Ambulance service • Prompt service • Prompt attention to patients on request • Problem resolution • Handling the complaint of patients and their visitors • Flexibility while providing service.
<p>Trustworthiness in the hospital</p>	<p>Trust in hospitals is the ability of the hospital to provide the promised service dependably. The availability of skilled doctors and staff in the hospital, and their ability to inspire trust and confidence.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Assurance 2. Patient confidence 3. Courtesy 4. Trust 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge and courtesy of staff. • Experienced staff. • Experienced and qualified doctors. • Competent staff • Respect for patients

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Confidential • Safety and secure environment • Less costly • Patient safety • Effective treatment provided by the hospital to the patient. • Treatment provided on time.
Administrative Procedures	Administrative Procedures in hospitals include the admission process, staying in hospital and the discharging of the patients after using hospital services	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Service delivery process 2. Waiting time 3. Punctuality 4. Timeliness 5. Operation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reasonable waiting time • Ease of consultation with doctors • Ease of getting check-ups and treatments. • Clear information on hospital rules and regulations. • Assistance by staff for additional care

Table 6 :THEMES (Major themes reflecting the service quality of the hospital)

4.2.1 ENVIRONMENTAL QUALITY OF THE HOSPITAL

Environmental quality consists of the hospital's physical facilities like a hygienic environment, safe and organised equipment, bathrooms, clean beds, and signs. Intangible facilities like the atmosphere of the hospital can also influence the impressions patients form. Physical facilities, atmosphere, and patient safety were the key sub-themes of environmental quality.

4.2.1.1 Physical facilities

physical or tangible aspects of the service industry influence customer purchase intentions. The physical attributes are the first thing seen by customers; hence, the service provider can use visible elements to increase customers numbers and improve customer satisfaction (Swan, Richardson & Hutton,2003, Wu et al., 2016). Boshoff and Du Plessis (2009:248-249), suggest that physical evidence or tangible aspects comprise the environment in which the service is delivered. In a hospital, the visible elements are mainly the appearance of the building, accessibility, parking, the general condition of equipment, medical facilities, a waiting room for the patient, an adequate number of seats and patient beds, canteen services, clear directional signs written signage and the cleanliness of the building. These are the key factors which are linked with the tangible environment of a hospital. Hence, hospitals require modern facilities, and equipment and adequate seating and furniture for patients. This facility somehow affects the way we see, and judge service quality standards. Ceelik & Sehirbanoglu, (2012) and (Senarath, et al., 2006) argue that physical aspects such as the environment, the cleanliness of the hospital, the seating, technology and equipment have a greater impact on perceptions of service quality in hospitals in Turkey and Jordan. Similarly, Narang (2010) states that in hospitals in India, tangibility is the most important dimension for defining overall service quality. Sohail (2003) found that patients who visited private hospitals in Malaysia have high expectations of physical facilities such as modern equipment, and a professional appearance. Tangibility is thus a good predictor of service quality in terms of patient satisfaction.

A key issue that emerged in terms of the tangible aspects of the hospital is the design and cleanliness, as noted by a 45-year-old housewife, *"I preferred to go to the clean hospital, I think hospital building must be kept clean, and the types of equipment and machine should be available. I find it comfortable for the treatment if the hospital atmosphere is clean and fresh*

this will make me feel good.” (P1)

This respondent makes reference to the external features of the hospital. The respondent considers the design of the building, its surroundings, and other features. These were part of her needs. The respondent considers these as examples of service quality.

Similarly, another participant from Biratnagar stated, *“the physical substances in the hospital are very old and need to be changed. They need to get new and modern equipment like a digital thermometer to give the best temperature figures, the thermometer they are using now sometimes does not give the correct figure after the second use.” (P2)*

This participant (P2) considers technologies and types of equipment as physical facilities. He sees devices and equipment as key aspects of service quality. He further suggests that technology needs to be changed when it is outdated, and this will help to improve the accuracy of medical examinations which will improve service. Service is about measuring quality healthcare. Alrubaiee et al.,2011, (Yousapronipaiboon & Johnson, 2013) and (Ramez, 2012) confirms that an improvement in perceived quality raises the quality of care, resulting in patient satisfaction. They concluded that the physical environment has potential connections to patient satisfaction.

“I have been waiting from morning to get the empty bed so I can move from emergency ward to normal ward, but the staff member still has not confirmed about the vacant bed in the normal ward.” (P3)

Based on this reasoning, the number of beds available in the hospital are fewer as compared to the amount of the people who visited the hospital for treatment. The hospital is crowded, and typically filled with large numbers of patients attending appointments, but the bed facilities available in the medical ward are insufficient so patients have to wait longer. This respondent suggests that the hospital must add extra beds to the medical department which will help to minimize the waiting times for patients. He also believes a bed with a warm mattress, and clean sheets are important facilities which need to be provided by the hospital.

A key issue to emerge in terms of physical evidence was small waiting rooms, beds, medical equipment, and the design of the hospital building. The findings from the interviews reveal the tangible elements associated with the service quality of hospitals in Nepal; especially in the districts which have inadequate numbers of beds and which lack medical equipment and clean

toilets. Similarly, a shortage of drinking water has been reported.

Similarly, another participant mentioned that *“the bed linen provided by the hospital is very dirty as they are not washed properly and still can see the bloodstain, I was so uncomfortable to use the bedsheets than I asked my husband to get a new sheet for me.”* (P4) Another respondent also addressed the same issue regarding the cleanliness and availability of beds in the hospital. (P1)

One participant, who was the regular visitor said *“I am a pneumonia patient when I was in the hospital, I found the bedsheet was not changed daily though they were dirty and smelly, I even requested one of the nurses to change. Still, she denied changing sheet and asked me to wait one more day as also confirm it was okay to use for more one day.”* (P5)

Both respondents P1 & P5 were more focussed on the cleanliness of the hospital. They explained how important it is to provide clean bed sheets and blanket for patients, as the beds and sheets are used by patients suffering from different illness. There is therefore a high chance of transmitting diseases to others if the beds and sheets provided are not cleaned thoroughly and made sterile.

Similarly, another participant noted *“I was admitted in the emergency service of the hospital, I found the room where I was kept was not better equipped with the facilities and even the machine used are very old and needs to be changed.”* (P6)

This respondent wanted hospitals to have fully equipped rooms with modern machines to perform medical check-ups and treatment.

“The toilet in the hospital is very uncomfortable and unhygienic to use, so I prefer to go outside rather than using the hospital toilet. I found it is very difficult for the patient to use the toilet, the floor of toilets is slippery and are not mopped to dry. Some of the toilets even do not have water supply which makes difficult to use it as we need to carry water in a bottle. The bad smell coming from the toilets are spread all over the building and waiting area, which makes it difficult for patients to stay near the toilet area.” (P7)

The respondent focussed on the toilets, and explained how important it is for hospitals to provide clean and comfortable toilets for patients. She suggests that every hospital must have a convenient bathroom in a convenient place, which will be easy for the patients to use.

Hygiene teams should focus on cleaning toilets. Patients might fall if the bathrooms are slippery and illnesses can be transmitted if toilets are not clean. Water must be supplied constantly in the toilets, and the bathroom needs to be cleaned with detergents, which can help to control smells coming out from the bathroom.

For the service provider, tangibility is a significant predictor of customer satisfaction. (Ramez, 2012) also notes that tangibility is an important element in health care. He recommends that hospital management should focus more on the physical structure of hospitals, as this can promote confidence amongst patients. Similarly, Boyer et al., (2014), and (Al-Neyadi, et al., 2016) confirm that tangibility is a key factor for patients in assessing quality healthcare.

4.2.1.2 Patient safety

The majority of participants raised issue relating to patient safety. Some participants believe that the hospital was more concerned about safety, hygiene, cleanliness which attract more patients. Every organisation needs to make their customers and employees feel safe and secure while using their services, because insecurity in either area will have a detrimental effect. Safety in hospitals is a critical factor which needs to be addressed almost all the time and the process of care is carried out while providing the service. If customers do not feel safe they will leave with a poor impression. In a study conducted by Poon and Low (2005) the issues of safety and security is addressed as a critical factor in health care. To provide quality services, hospitals must look after critical issues where service action takes place. Giving importance to safety helps to provide quality services to patients because the main purpose of patients is to receive quality treatment which can improve their health. Hospitals can take precautions around patient safety by using elevators for patients who cannot walk and analysing allergic reactions that must be guarded against (Pai & Chary, 2013).

Further, patients that need ramps and elevators should be considered. Physically challenged and older people who visit hospitals need special care. This must be considered by any hospital as it improves the satisfaction of patients, and they are more likely to enjoy the service. Safety indicators were also one of the themes which were raised regularly while conducting interviews. Some participants criticised the lack of interest in patient safety in the hospital.

“The hospital does not show much interest in patient safety in term of cleanliness. The toilet inside the general ward is very stinky and dirty. No one can stand near the bathroom. I wonder how patients are staying near the bathroom. I told staffs many times if they can ask cleaners to

clean the toilet using a disinfectant, but they did not show much interest in my words.” (P8)

Similarly, another participant who was a student complained about the same issues as the previous participant, *“I stay with my mum in the general ward for a week. The toilet inside the department for patients is very dirty and stinky. It was very difficult to stay there, and the mosquitos bite whole night I used to wake up the whole night.” (P9)*

Both these participants (P8 & P9) raised issues relating to the cleanliness of the hospital and criticised the lack of interest of hospital management towards cleanliness. Hospital management are not aware of the phycological impact on patients because of the fear of diseases.

Other participants also expressed negative thoughts about the cleanliness of the hospital, *“I had an accident, so I was admitted in the hospital, I had to stay 15 days as I had stitches on my leg. My bed was near the toilet, and the toilet was so smelly that I used to cover my face and sleep. Even though the cleaners use to clean frequently, but it looks so unhygienic, I even felt like not using it, but I had no option because I could not move much. They used to give food on the bed itself due to the smell of the toilet I could not eat my food, and at night I could not sleep because of the mosquito’s bite. I even have a mark on my face that I got from the bite of the mosquitos. I think the hospital should also focus on the cleanliness, thousands of people visit the hospital every day, so hospital administration needs to have a plan on how to keep clean the hospital.” (P10)*

This participant (P10) sees it as important for hospitals to keep their surroundings clean. Hospital management must focus on cleaning toilets and disinfecting these to mitigate diseases. Some patients will fear contamination, which can lead to illness. Whereas hospital management have different perceptions towards the environmental quality of hospitals. One respondent mentioned *“they try to keep the hospital surrounding clean and the cleaning team were focused on keeping the hospital building clean. When I am here, I keep asking a cleaning team member to clean properly I believe we are focused on keeping the hospital clean. (P29)”*. A member of management from Koshi hospital management noted *“we are cleaning hospitals bathroom, toilet, and floor continuously by using disinfectant, but it is patient who makes it dirty by not following the rules and throwing garbage wherever they like to. (P32)”*

4.2.2 INTERPERSONAL QUALITY

Interpersonal quality refers to the behaviours and attitudes of those providing healthcare to patients. Such professionals require to have empathy, a suitable manner, and respect for patients. This refers to the three sub-themes of manners, understanding and communication which summarise the interview data around interpersonal quality in health care.

4.2.2.1 Empathy and Manner

Empathy refers to sympathy, attention and understanding provided by service providers while providing personal care and mental support to patients and their families. Compassion is about caring, and providing for customers, which includes giving access to service, communicating and understanding customers by offering them individualized attention. Using such an approach, customers are treated in such a way that they feel special and important, and their needs are then valued (Zeithmal et al., 2009; and O’Neill & Palmer, 2003). Manner refers to the behaviour and attitude of the service provider. Manner was also one of the most criticised issues during interviews with participants. Some participants criticised what they saw as a negative attitude amongst staff towards patients while providing services. In the case of the hospital, this can be seen in the interaction between the teams of hospital staff and patients. Empathy plays a vital role in patient satisfaction and is a key component for hospital staff and patient relationships. When patients visit hospitals, they are typically in need of medical help and may be experiencing mental emotions like anxiety, fear, and apprehension. Empathy goes beyond medical diagnoses and treatment, and is about making a connection with patients, and understanding their needs. It is a highly effective and powerful communication tool between patients and doctors, which helps to create trust between them. This improves the health outcomes of patients and affects patient loyalty, and their satisfaction with services (Talib, et al., 2011) .

A respondent from Itahari described the behaviour of nurses towards him during his stay in the hospital, *“I had an accident and stay in the hospital for 25 days during my stay at the hospital I found the doctors were relatively polite and treated me well, but there were several nurses who are rude and often grumpy. They were not friendly and very impolite to the patients.”* (P11)

A similar issue was mentioned by another respondent, *“Whenever I saw them, I just saw their gloomy and sullen faces, they were not caring what the patients want. They even do not bother to answer the queries of the patient, and they just do not answer.”* (P12)

Both respondents P11 & P12 criticized what they saw as negative behaviour and attitudes on the part of nurses towards patients. They failed to address the state of mind of these patients, and their poor manner could lead to patient discomfort with services. A positive attitude towards patients helps them to heal faster, and it is also important for the service provider to get positive vibes from customers to ensure their service are used in future.

However, some respondents gave positive feedback on the empathy they encountered during their stay in the hospital.

One of the respondents noted *“my mum was admitted in hospital as she was a cancer patient, she was treated for a month and the way they treated her was very good, they provide good care and support to my mum and their attitude towards me was good they were friendly and understood my problems what I was going through. They took good care of mum hygiene, foods and medicine and managed to keep her clean and tidy till we were in the hospital.”* (P13)

This respondent was happy with the service and care provided by the hospital. He noted how important it is to receive proper care from hospitals for patients with severe illness. A positive attitude, and positive behaviour towards patients and their families is key for mental health, and makes them feel happy, valued and respected. It is important for hospitals to address patient concerns and requirements with a caring attitude. This helps to improve customer satisfaction.

However not all the respondents had the same experience, and some were quite dissatisfied with the attitudes of the staff.

One participant noted *“I was admitted to the hospital after having an accident with the truck. I found the attitude of doctor and nurse was not good towards me. When doctors are on the round they used to be always in a rush, I cannot properly discuss my condition to them if I bother to ask them their reply were, I will be fine rather than explaining what I am going through. Nurses were rude and cold towards, and maybe they found I am not a rich person, so they were ignoring me. If I called them for help, they used to get angry and get annoyed and complains that I am calling them frequently, they act like a boss rather than a nurse. I was not happy with the behaviour they show towards me, and maybe I come from a poor family, so their attitude towards me was different as compared to other patients. It makes me feel sad about my appearance and poverty.”* (P14)

“I was feeling dizzy and had problem with sleeping. When I went to the hospital for a check-

up, I think the doctor was not very. Interested in what I was telling him, he just told me it is nothing and gave me piece paper asking to get medication at the pharmacy. I think he was not happy the way I was looking. I am a poor lady and cannot afford nice clothes.” (P15)

Both these respondents (P 14 & P 15) remarked on what they saw as discrimination between patients. They noted the attitudes of the nurses and doctors varied from patient to patient. Each of these participants came from poor families and were receiving medical treatment from someone else from their village who are funding them for treatments.. The negative attitude of doctors and nurse towards them affected their mental health. One of the participants felt unwanted and less important as compared to other patients. He also explained how much concern and respect patients want from doctors and nurses.

Another responde noted *“I do not like the way they treated patients, it's inhumane where patients are neglected, they have no rights to express their feelings, they even cannot say no, cannot ask questions and discuss their concerns and feelings with doctors and nurses. I felt I have seen a heavy burden rather than a customer.” (P16)*

This respondent noted the lack of empathy and negative attitudes towards patients as per his personal experience. He added that it is important for hospitals to provide good care and empathy towards patients as this can lead to a better relationship between doctors and patients and nurses and patients. He said many patients who use hospital wanted to feel care and respected by doctors and nurses to help them to feel trusted. Empathy also enhances communication and trust between service providers and service users. He also added that many doctors do not understand the emotional needs of patients as a core aspect of care, and this could be due to time pressure as they must treat so many patients. He also suggested that a warm welcome, good treatment and attention and care is what all patients need.

4.2.2.2 Communication

Communication is a vital indicator of service quality. A good connection between a service provider and service receiver is important while providing services, so the service provider can understand the needs of their customers. As with the two themes of manner and empathy, the participants also saw communication as an important interpersonal quality. In today’s modern business world, effective communication is very important. Communication can take any form from speaking or writing through to body language. To provide better service, communication plays a vital role because businesses that can communicate better have more chance of getting

more customers. Therefore, the organisation needs to communicate with its customers at all levels. The organisation can use effective communication methods to meet the demand of customers and to solve their problems. The effectiveness of communication is also considered to impact on technical and functional quality (Gill & White,2009). Mehta (2011) and Naidu (2009) mention that communication is an important element for achieving service quality. Pai & Chary (2016) state that effective communication helps build trust in customers. Through communication, an organisation can obtain feedback from customers which can help improve service quality. Communication was also one of the most common words in the interviews.

A respondent who was working as a health assistant reflected on the types of communication hospitals have with their patients, *“Communication with nurses is okay they tried to communicate understandably but sometimes with the doctor, I do not understand what he is trying to say. Some doctors use medical terms to explain problems and solution during the examination, I found it difficult to understand what he is saying. I ask the pharmacy guy while buying the medicine what the doctor was trying to tell me.”* (P17)

This respondent (P17) complained about difficult terms used by doctors, and suggested they should communicate in simpler words with patients who may be less educated. So, doctors need to understand their patients and have better communication with them. He also added that communication is a crucial component in all steps of the hospital process whether it is between patients and staff or between staff groups. Communications means the right treatment can be given to patients, while poor communication can lead to wrong diagnoses and even tragedy.

Another respondent, a nursing student noted the importance of communication to understand patients' problems and to give them proper treatment. The respondent noted *“I am a nursing student so while doing my community project I found there are more than 50% patients who do not understand what their illness and what medicine they are having. I asked some of the patients and they say I went to the doctor to show my health condition and after some examination doctor said you have this condition; I have written down the medicine for you. I think this is critical for patients also if they are not properly communicated with their problems. Some of the patients are even taking medicine for a longer time than they are supposed to take. I believed this happens because of the poor communication between the doctors and the patients. So, both patients and doctor need to communicate effectively so each of them can precisely do their jobs.”* (P18)

Some participants were happy with the way they had communicated with the doctors and nurses during their visit for treatment. Respondent (P19) describes his experience while using the hospital' *"I went to have a check-up for my stomach pain as I was having pain for a long time. When I reached the hospital, I found all the staff were very helpful and the doctor who examined me was very calm. He listened to my problem very patiently and gave me the proper guidance for what examination needs to carry out to diagnose what is happening with me. After the diagnose we found out I had a stone in my gall bladder, after hearing this I was very scared, but the doctor communicates with me very nicely and explained to me what the problem is and how it can be treated. After hearing him I was very relieved."* (P19)

This respondent explained that it is important to receive counselling from the doctor about health conditions and effective communication is key.

Another respondent (P20) explained that poor communication had led to medical errors in the hospital. *"one of my neighbour's son was having fever for a long time, he was just given some paracetamol from the local pharmacy, but the fever did not go away than we decided to take him to the hospital. After reaching their doctor examine him and then he said he is fine it is due to hot weather his temperature is high, so we were sent back home but after week he was very critical than we call ambulance service and took him to the hospital. There I explained everything to the doctor about his condition, the doctor asks to do some test on his body. After the test it comes out, he was suffering from the Jaundice. I was very sad that the doctor should have done the test when he was brought the first time and he could not have got cured till the time. I think this occurred due to poor communication between the doctor and the patient family. Not only this I have experienced many errors in diagnosing the patients and describing the correct treatment and medicine to the patients."* (P20)

The respondent spoke about his encounter with medical errors due to poor communication. He explained how medical errors occur in the hospital; not only in one hospital, but in most hospitals in Nepal patients are facing issues with receiving incorrect medical diagnoses and receiving the wrong medicines for treatments. He also stated that many medical errors have occurred and will occur in future, and this leads to harm to patients and even sometimes to death. This kind of medical errors are commonly heard in news of Nepal, the recent case of medical error was death of new-born babe.(Subedi, 2019) .To stop medical errors the hospital should come out with the process of having effective communication with their patients, so

they can understand the problems of the patients and give them the right treatments.

Similarly, another respondent noted *“communication between the nurse and patients must be clear, I have treated different patient some of the patients do not understand the treatment procedures they are getting in that case I make them understand on their conditions and treatment they are receiving (P29). Furthermore, another respondent mention “when there is a long queue in OPD we cut down the time to explain the treatment. If sufficient time is given to the patient, they will understand the treatment but if the communication is less, they might think the doctor is not good and there are chances of not meeting the expectation of patient (P32).”*

This respondent felt that effective communication is important to help patients understand the treatment process, and their health conditions. A trip to hospital is very stressful for both patients and their families and some patients get scared or are intimidated to ask about the situation. In such situation, it is the duty of hospital staff to provide sufficient time to explain treatment to patients or risk negative perceptions about the service (Duggirala, et al., 2008). Effective communication within hospital teams can result in quality care delivery and can mitigate complaints from patients.

4.2.2.3 Responsiveness

Responsiveness is the willingness of organisations to understand customers and provide prompt services (Zeithmal et al.,2006; and O’Neil & Palmer,1998). The responsiveness of hospitals is about managing the expectations of the non-medical aspects of health care (Kamra, et al., 2016) and the environment in which patients are treated (Valentine et al., 2015). Responsiveness is an important component for the overall experience of patients while receiving medical care. Patients understand and judge the various aspects of service throughout their time in hospital (Alrubaiee & Alkaa'ida, 2013). Focusing on responsiveness should be an important goal for any health care organisation as patient responsiveness can directly affect patient welfare (Fatima, et al., 2018). The main dimensions of responsiveness are dignity, the confidentiality of information, prompt attention, choice of health care provider, autonomy, good quality surroundings, social support, and clarity of communication with the service provider.

One of the main issues in responsiveness was indicated by respondent as follows: *“I admitted my mother in the hospital and nearly stay there for 20 days, I did not get any support from*

hospital staff. Nurses are very rude and are not trained properly to treat patients. my mum was old lady aged 75 and could not move from the bed, I ask nurses to help her use the bathroom, but they mention they are busy and asked to wait for some time which is found it as a rude behaviour towards the patients. Even though the doctors when they are on a visit, they do not explain properly about the condition of my mother when I ask them, they could not explain clearly about the condition of my mum just say go and get this medicine rather than explaining how the condition and what treatment is needed further. I found the attitude of doctors is like that of an army. I want better and clear communication from doctors and nurses. Where, the basic amenities of the hospital better, I found the hospital is the cleanest in town and, I saw regular procedures for cleaning the room and surrounding of the hospitals.” (P21)

The emerging theme from the interview was the attitude, behaviour and cleanliness of the hospital. Respondents remarked on the attitude and behaviour of doctors and nurses towards patients and their visitors. Respondents preferred a good and calm attitude from nurses, and suggested the communication between them needs to be clear and understandable. To achieve patient’s satisfaction, the hospital needs to treat patients in the right way, and with a caring nature. They must provide good treatment and excellent service quality to patients (Mathur, 2011).

Some respondents were satisfied with the emotional care they received from medical staff.

A 35yr old, science professor noted “I visited the hospital to do a check-up of my daughter I found the staff were very helpful towards me. I am a regular visitor of this hospital, the communication between me and staffs in hospital and doctors are clear and understandable. They explain to me the procedure of admission and register, while doctors explain about the illness conditions what needs to be done and how the procedure will be carried out. I found the staff and nurses are helpful and always eager to help me. They took good care of my daughter until our stay in hospital. They were very friendly towards my daughter as well and show much love and care to her. I found the hospital cleanliness was very good and the beds are also clean and comfortable. I am pleased and happy with the quality of service I got from the hospital, I even did not have to wait longer to get admitted and the doctor was available quickly after the registration and doctors explain me properly about the conditions of my daughter and what treatment she needs to undergo.” (P22)

This respondent (P22) was happy with the service he received from the hospital. Patients

observed that the quality of hospitals depends on the performance of staff and doctors and their commitment towards tasks. The interviewer found that doctors and nurses were committed to the care of patients, and carefully engaged with them and their visitors in discussions about health.

Another respondent suggested waiting times are an emerging issues in hospitals. A 50 year old farmer noted that *“The hospital is too busy, I almost waited for 3 hrs in a queue to get register. Normally the hospital registration office opens at 9 am but I went at 6 am, if I go late than I may not get the chance to meet doctors on the same day. Even after registration, I waited nearly 3-4hrs to meet the doctor and even after meeting the doctor I was not able to understand the explanation given by the doctor regarding my illness. I do not if it was him or me who could not understand what’s the matter about. I found the doctor was quite rude and was not clear about the illness. The main concern for me is the procedures of the hospital which takes long and takes a whole day if I want to visit the hospital for a check-up.”* (P23)

A key concern was waiting times for treatment in hospitals. He suggested that waiting times count as part of service quality in hospitals. To satisfy patients, hospitals need to provide services on time. The interviewees suggested that the accessibility of services is important for patient satisfaction. Some aspects of accessibility include a convenient location, shorter waiting times, fast and easy admission and discharge procedures and appointment waiting times. These aspects should be considered by hospitals seeking to provide quality services to patients.

One of the respondents noted (P24) *“the information displayed on the wall and board of hospital is not up to date. It is very difficult to find the room as the name in the wall can be barley read and staffs in the administration counters are not confident enough to show the room or are too busy with their work, they ignore us. Once I asked admin staff about the doctors’ room, he said just to go this side but did not explain which side I am supposed to go left or right and which floor, which confuses me and other similar patients. I found it is important to put proper board and sign on the wall so patients can see and read so they will not get confused.”* (P24)

According to this respondent, information about hospital facilities should be display properly on the wall, and should be updated from time to time. This respondent wanted to be helped by staff properly and to receive guidance on the procedures of the hospital. Further, he added that staff working in hospitals should be knowledgeable about customer treatments, and should be

able to offer help to patients as needed.

Another respondent noted, *“I was taken to the hospital by my family because I was feeling very anxious and distressed, I every time felt I am may die though I was in good health. The doctor has taken the time to listen to my problems and reassure me. They also asked me to share my problem anytime I needed to and sure me about my problem will not be shared with any other people.”* (P25)

This respondent (P25) explained what she expected from doctors, and described their behaviour towards her as kind and helpful. Her doctor showed patience, and gave her plenty of time to understand her problems, before providing solutions. She found her doctors to be trustworthy and able to maintain her privacy. The key themes from the interviews in this regard were trust and comfort between patients and doctor. Doctors need to understand their patients, and try to provide treatment after diagnosing problems. In this way they can provide a better quality of treatment to patients and can build trust which influences customer satisfaction and the retention of customers in the future. As per Dawi et al., (2016), it is important to provide quality service in health care organizations to achieve patient satisfaction.

Similarly, another respondent addressed the attitude and behaviour of hospital staff in emergencies. A 35yrs old fashion designer from Biratnagar noted: *“I went to the hospital because I suddenly have pain in my stomach, I was in rush I forget to take my health care, the nurse in hospital shout at me for not bringing my card and not even ask me to sit down while registering even though I was moaning due to pain in stomach.”*(P26) This respondent said that nurses were rude to her, and were more concerned about her medical card than her illness. The nurse also lost her temper which is unprofessional. Some patients reportedly experienced verbal abuse and rudeness at the hands of nurses while visiting hospitals. This could be due to a lack of management support, or a shortage of staff. She also added that nurses must support patients to promote healing, and minimise the stress and suffering of patients. Nurses must form a good relationship with patients (Chakravarty, 2010).

Similarly, another female participant had a similar experience with staff in the hospital, *“I visited the health care centre at a time when the centre was very crowded. The patient in the hospital was very impatient to get their treatment on time and are reluctant to queue and wait for their turn to come. Where the nurses working in the hospital were very patience most of the time and were asking the patient to wait for their turn, but occasionally they were angry on the*

patient for breaking the queue.” (P27)

The interviewer remarked on the behaviour of nurses and suggested that the hospital is always overcrowded. She complained of no systematic process to the admission procedure and suggested that admissions processes make it difficult for patients to be attended to. She also explained that nurses are under pressure, although they do show patience. She suggested they sometimes feel irritated, and she suggested this is not unusual because of the circumstances in the hospital. She added that nurses were doing their jobs well and providing prompt service.

Similarly, hospital staff said, *“Sometimes the patient load is more, the doctor might be busy he cannot give that much time as the patient expects.”* This may be one reason for the gap between quality and satisfaction (P32, P28).” Furthermore, another respondent mentioned in an in-depth interview *“If a rush is less, then more quality work is done, and patients feel satisfied if they are examined thoroughly.” (P29)*

Hospital staffs noted that the time they allocate to patients plays a crucial role in providing effective care. Investing more time in patients means it is easier to understand their needs and to perform treatment effectively. Providing effective treatment can lead to patient satisfaction (Blair, 2015).

4.2.3 TECHNICAL QUALITY OF THE HOSPITAL

Technical quality of hospital refers to the clinical procedures which are carried out by the hospital. It mainly describes the expertise, professionalism, and reliability of the organisation with a focus on outcomes. According to Duggirala (2008), technical quality describes the performance of doctors and patient care with implications for the quality of service the patient experiences. (Kocher, et al., 2010) argue that hospitals should prioritise to provide high-quality care to effect good customer satisfaction. The technical quality of the hospital was evaluated based on the sub-themes generated after interviewees. The sub-themes that emerged were expertise, reliability, and outcomes.

4.2.3.1 Expertise

Expertise is referred to as skills. In terms of this study, expertise means the qualifications of service providers, as well as their skills, confidence, and capacity to comply with high standards of service delivery. It is about the professionalism of doctors. Some participants identified skills, professionalism, and competence as indicators of expertise. There were some

concerns raised around this topic, and specifically the lack of accurate diagnoses. The inefficiency of doctors and other staff in the hospital were also mentioned. Some of the interviewees focussed on the lack of qualified staff which resulted in poorer quality medical services in the hospital. This also impacted on the confidence of patients in doctors.

Respondent (P6) noted *“There is lack of qualified doctor in the hospital if something gets serious, they will refer us to Kathmandu (Capital city of Nepal) which is expensive, and all of the patients cannot afford. Sometimes I prefer going Siliguri (India near to Nepal) there we can rely on the doctors as they have specialized doctor for the treatment.” (P6)*

This respondent discussed the qualifications of doctors and argued that many doctors in Nepalese hospitals are under-qualified. He therefore preferred to travel abroad to receive treatment. He was therefore dissatisfied with the service provided by hospitals in Nepal. He wants hospitals to employ more qualified doctors so that they can rely on them for treatment, rather than travelling to other countries which can be more costly.

Other respondents described the story of his cousin’s brother who was given the wrong medication by a doctor when in a critical conditions: *“My cousin brother he went to the hospital with a complaint of joint pain in September 2017, after initial investigation doctor prescribed medicine, after taking the medication he started having rashes and itchiness in his skin, then he went back to the doctor as the doctor assumed the signs are the side – effects of medicine and are normal. But the condition was not improved so I suggest him to check with a different doctor. After the check-up doctor diagnosed medicine reaction and the test confirmed he was given the wrong medication by the previous doctor, the doctor even said if he were late for the check-up he could have died. I was so shocked that even the experience and well-known doctor neglect the patient symptoms and prescribe the wrong medication what can we expect from the new doctor.” (P20)*

This respondent suggested that negligence towards patients is quite common. Patients visit hospitals to receive health care, but he suggested that it is difficult to trust doctors if they do not provide the correct treatment. He suggested this can be so dangerous as to pose a risk to the lives of some patients. In this case, the doctor failed to provide accurate treatment which compromise the image of the hospital and its management team. This may have the effect of repelling customers and making them afraid to attend hospital.

There were other examples of similar cases from the different respondents. Numerous patients in Nepal have become the victims of medical errors. Neglecting patients is serious, and can be attributed, in some cases to inexperienced doctors (Subedi, 2019).

Another respondent reflected, *“My four-year son died due to the negligence of an on-duty nurse. My son was under the intensive care she removed his oxygen pipe without consulting to the main doctors. When we complain to them the hospital administration accepts the fault and promised to act against the staff, but it never happened.”* (P6)

Similarly, another respondent said *“my brothers' son died due to the wrong medicine given by the nurse; he was 3 yrs. old. He had a fever and diarrhoea, so we took him to the hospital. The doctor first tried to give the preliminary treatment, but the efforts were failed then the doctor on duty order nurse to inject the Diclofenac. After some time of injecting Diclofenac his conditions started to get worse, his kidney and liver were failed after seeing the conditions the hospital referred to the bigger hospital, but our child was declared dead before we reach to the hospital. The doctors at other hospital said that he died due the injected medicine which was not supposed to administer (P10).”*

Hospital staffs in Birat nursing mentioned: *“sometimes medical error occurs but we make sure that it does not, and we provide training to the hospital employees from time to time (P28, P27).”* Providing training is essential to minimise errors. Training, and the provision of regular feedback is essential to improve the performance of staff in hospitals. Training provides an opportunity to expand the knowledge base of all staffs, and this can drive performance.

4.2.3.2 Reliability

Reliability refers to the extent to which a service provider delivers services as promised (O'Neill & Palmer, 1998; Buttle; 1996). Kondasani & Panda (2015) argue that reliability is about the ability of an organisation to deliver services as expected according to standard. This is about performing the right service at the right time, and maintaining an error-free record for customers. It is also about providing services to customers within a promised timescale. Providing services on time is an important area for hospitals, e.g., a promise made by doctors and staff to patients in hospitals plays a major role in the perceptions of patients.

“The main problem in this hospital is waiting time, I have even waited for 6 hrs for the doctor,

they say the doctor was held in the traffic the truth was he was busy in his private clinic so could not come on time, hospital administration needs to be strict on doctors' time as waiting long can affect patient's health conditions.” (P6)

This respondent shared some concerns regarding waiting times in hospitals. The doctor was not available at the time to treat patients, which made him feel that the hospital's services were not reliable. He felt that he waited longer than needed, and also said that waiting times should not be longer than 1hr.

“I have sudden pain in my stomach, and I was rushed to the hospital by ambulance, when I reached the hospital, I was admitted to the emergency ward, the doctor was there to do check-up after completing the check-up I was requested to take the x-ray, the doctor found I was suffering from a kidney stone and I need an operation as soon as possible to remove the stone. After the doctor explained to me the procedure my operation was done within 3 days and I was recovered and went home after 10 days. I think the treatment was done on time; I did not have to wait for operation for a long time.” (P23)

Overall, this respondent felt that the service provided to him was accurate, and on time. He noted that the doctors were helpful and provided effective treatments. He added that service is more accurate and reliable if it is performed in a given period.

Another respondent noted, *“I was admitted in the hospital for surgery in my leg, after the surgery I was transferred to the general ward where doctors come to see twice daily, as I was operated by one doctor but the one who came to check me up inward was the different doctor, I found he was not much aware of my situation. I asked him if I can see the same doctor who operates me than he said he is busy and cannot attend me now.” (P15)*

This respondent could not rely on the doctor, as different doctors were involved in her case. She wanted only one doctor to look after her to be more confident about her treatment.

Similarly, another respondent noted *“sometimes I come very early travelling an hour by bus hoping to have treatment early on the first hour but the nurses in the hospital take longer time to set up the OPD section. sometimes, the staff in the hospital brings their relatives and friends out of the queues to serve them first which results from us to wait for a long time, it is too bad for patient.” (P1)*

Most participants had similar experiences of waiting times. One of the respondents shared details of an experience that resonated with those of participants P15 & P1.

Participant (P6) explained, *“doctors and other medical personnel are not dedicated to their working hours, when I go to the hospital for the treatment, I have to wait more than normal waiting time. There is the frequent absence of doctors and delays in check-up this result in increased waiting time for patients. some of the doctors even fail to do the job as expected.”* (P6)

Both respondents P1 & P6 had encountered long waiting times. They had travelled far to receive their treatment and did not appreciate the additional delay. A longer waiting time is dissatisfying for patients who will not want to use the same services again. Long waiting times are a challenge for patients and hospitals. Waiting a long time for a treatment can make patients frustrated and irritated with services. Murti et al., (2013) argue that if the waiting times are reduced, there is more chance that patient satisfaction in health care will suffer. Similarly, Atinga et al., (2011) argued that waiting times can be important tools to measure the quality of health care perceived by patients.

4.2.3.3 Outcomes

Outcomes refer to the service outcomes experienced by the patients during the process of receiving a service. The codes that emerged out of the interviews were the perceived quality of services, patient satisfaction with services, and medical errors that occurred during service delivery.

Participants made several comments in relation to their perceptions of service. Many participants believed that hospital service quality had not reached a level that matched the standards the hospital expects of itself. Some of the interviewees confirmed that neighbouring India provides a higher level of service, and this motivates patients to travel there for treatment.

“I think the quality of care provided in the hospital is below average level, my sister was kept for medical treatment as she was suffering from pneumonia. Whenever she needs help, she used to ask help for her personnel care, but the nurse used to be very busy, and they have a thousand different things to do so they could not give her proper care on time. She also mentioned she ask them to change her bedsheets immediately, but she had to wait the whole day long to get it changed.” (P22)

This respondent (P22) believes that staff in hospitals should not provide better services to inpatients. It is important to keep patients clean and healthy, and to give them proper attention when they need it to satisfy their needs.

Another respondent had a different experience and was very pleased with the service he had received from the hospital. Respondent P16 noted: *“I had a kidney stone when I went for a check-up doctor suggest me to do the operation after he examined me. I am diabetic, so it was quite risky for the operation as diabetic patients wound does not heal quickly. But the doctor was very friendly and helpful he explained to me all the process they will do on me before and after the operation. And after the operation was completed, I stayed in the hospital for a week, all the staff members like nurses and doctors were very caring and supportive emotionally and physically towards me.” (P16)*

This respondent described the care he received in hospital. He was very happy and pleased with the service he received from the hospital. He found the doctor to be qualified enough to understand what he must do to treat his illness. He also found the nurses were very kind and caring. His overall experience with the hospital was pleasant, and he enjoyed his stay. This suggest that participants were satisfied by some service aspects, both mentally and physically.

Some other participants had a different experience of service , perhaps because a different medical team looked after them. In such cases, hospital administration must focus on providing the same kind of service to all patients. They should provide training to their employees in terms of how to treat patients.

4.2.4 TRUSTWORTHINESS WITH THE HOSPITAL

Customers need to be able to trust organisations. It is important to build trust to satisfy customers and to maintain them for the future. A sense of security and safety can both be measures of the trustworthiness of hospitals. Feelings of safety and wellbeing influence the confidence level of patients in hospital services. It is useful to make a holistic evaluation of services provided by hospitals. Bahadori, et al., (2015) view “perceived trustworthiness as a component of service quality which could help in determining customer satisfaction.” It has become vital for organisations to provide the services they promise to customers (Parasuraman et al. 1985). Maintaining trust is important in health care, and levels of trust vary from patient to patient. Trust in patients is based on the patient’s confidence in the service provider (Padma,

et al., 2010).

4.2.4.1 Trust

Trust is an important theme in Nepalese healthcare, because health care is about preserving the lives of people. This theme was identified by many participants during the interviews. A high level of trust in the organisation has been linked to many benefits, like perceptions of better care, reduced anxiety, patient satisfaction and recommendations about treatment. Patients are more likely to relax if they trust healthcare professionals, and this can help drive the quality of interactions between health professionals and patients. This can result in in greater patient autonomy. Various factors influence the trust of patients in hospitals such as honesty, confidentiality and caring, showing respect to patients, and good communication skills. Some participants mentioned trustworthiness during interviews (Padma et al.,2010).

Respondent P8 noted: *“I have seen staffs are not respecting their work schedules in the hospital, doctors are frequently late or absent from the work and doctors they do not delegate their work to other doctors or staff if they cannot come to work. I feel this is very unfair to the patients who will be waiting long to see the doctor.” (P8)*

This respondent had encountered problems with the service delivery of the hospital in that staff and doctors do not always keep to time. He explained how this effects patients as they must wait a long time to see doctors. This means service is delayed, which results in reduced trust amongst patients with implications for future use.

Similarly, another respondent had a different experience of service in the hospital, *“the nurse was very efficient and caring, and the doctors were always on time on my follow up, and he gives plenty of time for the check-up and discussion for my health condition.” (P13)*

This respondent was satisfied with the service he received. The hospital was able to win his confidence by providing quality service and so a level of trust was established.

4.2.4.2 Assurance

Another key issue that emerged in terms of trustworthiness was assurance. Assurance refers to the degree of confidence and trustworthiness the organisation can instil in the customer, based on interactions between both parties (Zeithmal et al.,2006; O’Neil & Palmer,2003; and Buttle, 1996). The trustworthiness of the hospital from the patient’s viewpoint can be evaluated through the feelings patients have towards the service. Perception of service quality play a

major role in measuring quality in hospitals. The ability to deliver services as promised is necessary for the care industry and can do much to establish high trust relationships between providers and users. The level of trust between patients is hard to categorise because we cannot expect the same perceived level of trust amongst the different age groups. Indeed, perceptions of service vary, and the needs and requirements of individuals and groups are different. The most salient themes in terms of assurance were prompt service upon arrival, strong communication between patients and doctors, trust, and confident.

One of the respondents noted, *“from my point of view, the quality of service is adequate. I had cut on my knee once and went to the hospital for treatment, and the action and treatment from the doctor were very prompt, they were so quick they rushed me in the room clean my wound first and did the check-up. They gave me the best treatment as expected for which I have a confident regarding their quality of service.” (P10)*

This respondent was impressed with the promptness of service in the hospital. He found that the service provided by the hospital was accurate and prompt. The staff were able to establish trust with their patients, and he was happy with the service they provided. Akbaba (2006) and Spencer et al., (2014) note that happy and satisfied patients are more likely to revisit hospitals, whereas Nwankwo et al., (2010) said that if the service provided is unsatisfactory, this could have the opposite effect.

Similarly, another respondent (P6) remarked on his experience of service in hospital, *“my wife was pregnant, and her delivery date was due, suddenly she started having pain at midnight, I call the hospital for an ambulance the service was very prompt, an ambulance came and took us to the hospital immediately which was very appreciable, and the doctor sees my wife straightaway without making us wait. I am happy with the service of the hospital. This helps me to build confidence towards the hospital, and I would prefer to use the hospital for a future visit as well.” (P6)*

He had experienced prompt service from the hospital and noted that the ambulance service in particular was efficient. For this respondent, prompt service in an emergency is key, as it can help to save lives. Some participants were satisfied with hospital services and were convinced to use the same services in the future. This interviewee was clearly very satisfied with the service he received from the hospital.

A 45-year-old respondent was also happy with the level of concern shown by the doctor during his visit to hospital. His stated *“the doctor was more aware of my illness when I visited hospital doctor asked me the problem I am currently having on my health, I explained to him I have a problem in breathing he then ask to do the x-ray of chest and enquiry about my conditions in detail. He had knowledge about my illness which build the trust towards him, and I was sure he will identify my illness and will give correct medicine as some of the doctors in another hospital could not identify my illness and provide me simple medication which could not make me better.”* (P21)

This respondent trusted the doctor since her received effective treatment. Trust is necessary if there is any uncertainty or level of risk (Badri, et al., 2009). Another respondent, noted of Birat nursing home: *“building trust with patients is important because they rely on us for their treatment so if we are unable to build the trust with patients than they will get scared to do the treatment (P29). Similarly, next respondent mentioned “patient believe doctor for the treatment so to maintain the trusted doctor has to diagnose the root cause of the problem and provide correct treatment (P30)”* This is important in health care as patients wholly rely on doctors and nurses for their wellbeing. Building trust with patients is critical as the experience can be fragile and fleeting. Trust can be heavily influenced by previous experiences as this respondent notes.

4.2.5 ADMINISTRATIVE PROCEDURE OF THE HOSPITAL

Administrative procedures in hospital involve the process of admission, staying in hospital and discharging patients from hospital. Some participants reported that they were not happy with admissions and complained of long waiting times for diagnosis, medical health check-ups, and treatments. Many studies of health services have reported the same issue. Some participants also made points about the availability of hassle-free ambulance services for patients. Other factors mentioned by participants were the availability of appointments, and the process of admission and discharging which need to be quicker and simpler. Efficient administration processes in hospitals improvise the level of service offered to patients. Therefore, to provide better services to patients, hospitals must standardize the quality of their service delivery process so that patients can receive hassle-free service (Sureshchandar et al., 2009).

It is important for hospitals to show that they care about their patients during a visit to hospital. Medical staff must be careful about protecting the hospital’s reputation as it takes longer to

build a image and reputation, therefore they must do everything possible to gain the confidence of patients. Gaining patient confidence can enhance the hospital's reputation and make customers feel safe while using services (Padma, et al., 2010).

A recurrent problem mentioned while conducting interviews about the hospital administration process was delays to service at various levels in the hospital process. Hospitals need to create well-structured policies and procedures for patients to make their stay pleasant (Duggirala, et al., 2008). Some issues addressed by participants while interviews were as follows.

Respondent (P6) described his experience of waiting for treatment from the right doctor. *“I came at 8 am before the hospital administration is open ed to get the admission for OPD. After queuing for 1 hr, I finally got a chance to get the token number to get queue to see a doctor. After getting the number, I still must wait for 2 hrs to get my turn. I was so frustrated with the long waiting time to be seen by the doctor. On top of that, I was hungry and could not even leave to eat as I do not know what time they are going to call me for a check-up. And if the doctor goes on a lunch break, then we have to wait for more longer.”* (P6)

This respondent had an issue with the long waiting times he encountered for treatment. It is difficult for patients to wait for a long time without eating. The respondent added that the processes of admission and treatment should be quicker. It is important for doctors to be punctual to avoid delays. Doctors should not overlook the importance of punctuality. This can occur due to poor management and a lack of organisation in the hospital and it can significantly affect waiting times in OPD (Outpatient Department) and other situations.

Another responded (P3) described the inconvenience of the discharging process after staying in hospital for two weeks *“I was admitted in the hospital to remove the stone from my kidney, I nearly stay for two weeks. During my stay in the hospital, I found some of the administrative processes took quite long. I was already told by a doctor that I can go home tomorrow when the day comes for the discharge, and they took the whole day to discharge, which I found quite annoying.”* And the similar experience was shared by other participants, *“My dad, was admitted in the hospital, he had jaundice. He was hospitalized for a week; on the discharge day, we had to wait for a whole day to get the sign from doctors. I keep going and ask the nurse when my dad reports will be ready, so I can take him home, but the staff keep saying doctors need to sign the logbook and he has not arrived on time. I found this quite depressing as we have to travel 4hrs by bus to reach home.”* (P12)

Both respondents raised issues relating to administration procedures and discharging. They found the discharge process took longer than expected. Hospitals need to discharge patients simply and quickly, to provide patients with a hassle-free service. This helps to fulfil customer satisfaction.

One of the respondents raise the issue on favouritism, *“it is easy to get treatment on time if someone knows one of the staff members of the hospital. I have seen many of them get medical examination on time and even get access to a bed or surgical procedure easily, but if you do not know any staff members or you do not have connection through anyone than you have to wait longer to get the service.”* (P21)

This respondent described how favouritism can be seen in hospitals and how it can influence waiting times. He believes that patients who have any kind of relationship with medical staff are given priority or easier access to medical services. He also added that there are too many patients, and everyone wants to go first. Some do not have the patience to wait, and will begin to panic. Hospitals must properly manage the administrative process to provide better services to patients.

Other issues were raised by another respondent (P6) who noted *“whenever I come to the hospital, there is always a long queue and many patients for the appointment at the same time. This led to congestion and crowded in the hospital. I think this occurs due to the poor organisation of the hospital. They should not give the appointment to large numbers of patients at the same time.”* (P6)

This respondent was concerned about large numbers of patients queuing for check-ups. He believed that such congestion could be attributed to poor organisation and coordination by the hospital management team. This respondent suggested it is important to have well-coordinated services so that all patients get the chance to see a doctor without making the hospital crowded. The hospital should change its administrative procedures by introducing the online and phone appointment system to address long waiting times for a medical consultation.

Another respondent (P8), was happy with the hospital’s visiting policy, noting: *“I like the way the hospital has decided the particular time for the visitors and the number of people who can visit. The hospital does not have a separate room for each patient in the general ward, and sometimes a single patient has 5,6 visitors at the same time, which will disturb other patient’s*

silence. Patients will feel irritated with the noise of other people, and some of them might feel insecure having lots of people around.” (P8)

This respondent suggested that hospitals must make visiting patients a priority. Allowing fewer people to visit at once could help to maintain a peaceful environment when other patients are resting. This will also ensure the privacy of patients. Some patients may feel insecure after seeing lots of people at once, so controlling footfall can help with patient confidence.

Another respondent (P6) noted *“I easily got the diagnostic test done; I was here a month ago for my diagnostic of the chest, the doctor asked me to do the x-ray. When I went for the x-ray, the process was so quick, and staffs were very helpful. they performed the x-ray and gave the result within 30 minutes, which was very surprising for me, infect it took less time to complete the check as I have expected.” (P6)*

This respondent wanted services to be easy and simple to use, and he does not want to wait for longer than necessary for an examination. He was happy with the service the hospital provided and was mad to feel at home. As such, hospitals need to provide simple and easy services, and this will help to build satisfaction in patients. Hospitals can improve their services by changing their administrative procedures in a simplified manner, and they need to provide services promptly. The admission process must be simple, clear and understandable to patients. They should make procedures easy so that even patients who cannot read and write can understand information. Hospital administrative staff should assist patients who cannot read and write.

Respondent (P4) said, *“the admission process of the hospital was easy, and staff helped me if I did not understand the process.” (P4)*

This respondent was in hospital for a check-up and found the admission process of the hospital was quick and easy. He felt that if he did not understand, staff were ready to help him. Staff play a major role in building trust with patients. The respondent believed that the quality of service provided by hospitals in term of administration procedures is satisfying. This meant his needs were fulfilled, and he felt he could recommend the service to other patients.

Most of the participants were happy with the administrative procedures of the hospitals. The hospitals were able to fulfil the needs of customers with their systems. This made more customers satisfied. Participants also raised the issue of punctuality. Organisations needs to offer services on time. Morale in the workplace is higher if all staff members are punctual.

When someone is late, then tension and resentment between staff may rise. To provide better services for the patients, hospital staff must be punctual.

“I have received everything as I have wanted in terms of care, attention and treatment. The medical staff are friendly and happy to help me. They are punctual about their work which is good to see her.” (P3)

This respondent described the attitude and punctuality of hospital staffs. He also suggested that it is important for hospital staff to be punctual so they can provide quality services to patients. The patient was satisfied with the kind of service he received in the hospital. From the first day, he felt better with the service, and everything around him.

Another respondent (P31) noted: *“I believe it is important to become punctual at work, especially in hospital you cannot be late on your timetable that’s why I am always early but never late for my shift. It is important to keep records of each person and perform duties on time.” (P31)*. Similarly, another respondent mentioned: *“I am very punctual in the service I have never come late and leave early. I generally come 30 mins early before my shift start to check the records of the patients and try to make sure the previous staffs have done the job correctly (P29).”*

These respondents were staff nurses, and they saw punctuality as one of the more important factors in providing quality services to patients. They also thought medical staff should be committed to meeting the needs of patients and should help them with their medical conditions. One staff member gave the example of Florence Nightingale as a perfect example of a nurse. Medical staff need to be punctual, and the shift changes must occur seamlessly to deliver patient care. Without punctuality, it will be difficult to meet the needs and requirements of patients.

4.3 SUMMARY

This chapter has outlined the various themes, and subthemes that arose from the interviews conducted by the researcher with participants who had used hospital services in the past, and who were thus qualified to comment. The researcher tried to identify problems in Nepalese hospitals based on this data. Patient satisfaction is important for hospitals in the long run. To satisfy patients, hospital management need to understand their needs and expectations. Qualitative research was conducted based on 32 participants that were interviewed. The study explained the themes and subthemes that were generated. The study gave detailed information as to the perceptions of service quality amongst participants. The experience of patients in hospitals in Nepal were captured. Nepal is a developing countries in the world, and the type of care and service provided there cannot be matched by the service provided in a developed country like the UK or USA. The study described five major themes that emerged in the process of carrying out interviews. The five major themes were the physical facilities of the hospital, interpersonal qualities like empathy, manners, and communication as well as technical excellence, trust and policies and procedures within hospitals. The study made several observations about the health services delivered by medical officers to patients in Nepalese hospitals. Participants raised issues as regards the type of service they receive from hospitals.

From the themes identified, the environmental quality of the hospitals identified the physical facilities available, and the atmosphere of the hospital according to service users. Other sub-theme included environmental quality and patient safety. The second theme was the interpersonal theme taking in empathy, communication, and responsiveness. The third theme was technical quality, with the subthemes of expertise, outcomes and reliability. The fourth theme was trust, which is one of the most important themes for customer satisfaction. The sub-themes for trust were patient confidence, trust, and assurance. All these themes were identified repeatedly by participants during interviews. These themes were the key indicators of service quality in Nepalese health care. The researcher created a story about perceptions of patients using the themes that emerged from interviews. The next chapter will discuss the key findings of the thesis in order to address the research question and research objectives.

5 CHAPTER FIVE DISCUSSION

5.1 INTRODUCTION

Chapter four outlined the main investigation of the study and discussed the generation of main themes and sub-themes based on semi-structured, in-depth interviews. This chapter discusses the themes and keywords that were perceived by participants.

This chapter will focus on answering the research questions and research objectives. Service quality in hospitals has become one of the most important topics in recent years. This chapter will discuss the findings of the research, and it will relate these to the literature review, and research objectives of the thesis. The fundamental purpose of the research was to examine patient perceptions of service provided by Nepalese hospitals, and the main objectives were.

- To identify the key indicators of quality service which are vital for patient satisfaction in hospitals of Nepal.
- To review existing conceptual models and theoretical issues related to service quality, customer satisfaction and consumer purchase intentions.
- To identify the extent to which service quality dimensions influence patient satisfaction in the hospitals.
- To identify the relationship between satisfaction with hospital service quality, and the impact of this on future purchase intentions.
- To progress the framework to measure service quality for health care centres leading to customer satisfaction with service quality.

5.2 DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The literature review provided a general conceptualization of service quality, and qualitative thematic analysis generated themes to measure service quality as perceived by patients in Nepalese hospitals. The qualitative findings were determined after conducting face-to-face in-depth interviews with 32 service users of Nepalese hospitals. The findings were grouped into major themes and sub-themes after a thematic map was created. The interview findings reveal that perceptions of service quality vary from customer to customer. Expectations of service quality are based on the needs and desires of customers (Al-Neyadi, et al., 2016). In health services in Nepal, the expectations of patients related to a desire to receive treatment at low prices, and to save the lives. The hope of customers is also based on their previous experience

with services. The thematic findings are discussed below separately. The discussion will address the research objectives of the study. The relationship between service quality, customer satisfaction and purchase intentions are also discussed below based on the service quality indicators from the data analysis.

5.2.1 PERCEPTION OF ENVIRONMENTAL QUALITY OF THE HOSPITAL

The environmental quality or physical facilities of the hospital were one of the major themes that emerged in the interviews. The subthemes spoke to the physical facilities, the atmosphere of the hospital and patient safety. The following diagram shows themes of the environmental quality of the hospital

FIGURE 12 THEMATIC MAP OF ENVIRONMENTAL QUALITY

Physical facilities are one of the key measures of customer satisfaction , and most affordable hospitals in Nepal lack a modern look. They also suffer from a lack of advanced equipment for medical purposes such as to diagnose, to carry out surgery and to give therapy. Most participants believed that hospitals lack essential physical resources such as equipment, beds, and chairs. Most hospitals in Nepal do not have sufficient equipment to treat patients. Based on previous studies, participants want to see clean buildings and appealing surroundings so that

they feel calm and relaxed while having treatment (Kamra, et al., 2016). Most participants described the type of building and surroundings they had in mind.

Most researchers that have looked into service quality in hospitals in developing countries have found physical facilities are the most common themes that are mentioned. The key issue that arises around physical facilities for hospitals are the buildings and the surroundings. Some participants complained about the locations of buildings, and some wanted hospital buildings to be located in quiet places with plenty of parking.

One participant said, *“I do not get parking whenever I visit the hospital, and all the cars and bike are normally parked in front of the hospital gate, and sometime there will not be the place to walk for the pedestrian.”* (p8)

This participant complained about parking at the hospital that she attended. He wanted the hospital to offer suitable parking so that visitors could avoid hazardous traffic jams and danger to pedestrians. Hospitals should therefore be located in convenient places with plenty of parking.

The second issue that was raised was the lack of sufficient beds in hospitals. This participant had to wait quite a long time for a bed and to be admitted to hospital. The hospital sees a large amount of footfall and so they need to have sufficient beds for patients to be admitted. This participant also suggested there were too few chairs in the waiting rooms. Some patients had to sit on the floor, since there were insufficient chairs in the waiting rooms, and one respondent complained of outdated equipment in the hospital. He suggested that some of the machinery was old and looked rusty. It is important to upgrade such equipment frequently. This will help the hospital to provide better service to patients. Patients were unhappy with some of the physical features. The physical facilities in hospitals have a remarkable effect on patient satisfaction. For some patients, physical facilities are often the deciding factor when selecting which hospital to attend for treatment (Pai & Chary, 2013).

Atmosphere was another feature in relation to the environmental quality of the hospital. Patients prefer a pleasant environment when staying in hospitals yet most Nepalese hospitals are unable to provide such an environment. Some respondents complained about dirty toilets, including beds, and dirty flooring. Many respondents remarked on the poor cleanliness of

toilets inside the general ward of the hospital. One respondent noted “*the toilet smells very bad, and it is very uncomfortable to use the toilet as it is not clean properly*”. (P6)

Patients prefer clean toilets, and so hospitals must focus on the cleanliness and sanitation of such facilities. Most respondents prefer clean and comfortable bathrooms, and a clean atmosphere was identified as an aspect that can impact on the health of patients. Many feel unsafe if the environment is not clean.

Patient safety was one of the key sub themes generated in relation to the environmental quality of hospitals. Patient safety and security is a vital element of quality service in hospitals (Poon & Low, 2005). Feeling safe and secure has a significant impact on patient satisfaction. Respondents were concerned about cleanliness and the implications for patient safety. Many thought that cleanliness might impact on the health of patients because of a fear of contamination from disease on account of poor hygiene practices. Patient safety is critical, as it relates to the health of patients and it is one of the very basic needs of individuals. Hospitals must therefore address safety concerns to provide quality service. Many of the patients visited hospitals to improve their health. If hospitals fail to create a safe and secure environment. Such patients might think twice about using these hospitals (Pai and Chary, 2013).

Based on the above findings it can be concluded that physical facilities and the surroundings of hospitals should have sufficient facilities and modern looking equipment. Hospital should provide adequate seating for patients so that they do not have to sit on the floor. These facilities also influence judgements as to quality standards in hospitals. Many of the participants felt that physical facilities were very important to improve service quality. Some researchers have previously noted that physical facilities matter (see Al-Hawary, 2011; and Senarath et al., 2014). They have found that physical facilities, cleanliness, adequate numbers of seating and modern equipment have a great effect on patient perceptions of quality in hospitals. Thus, analysis suggests that the environmental quality of hospitals is a reliable predictor of service quality perceptions in Nepalese hospitals.

5.2.2 PERCEPTIONS OF INTERPERSONAL QUALITY

Interpersonal qualities in relation to hospitals were identified as another key theme. The accompanying sub themes were manners, empathy, responsiveness, and communication, and these are illustrated in the diagram below.

Figure 13 Thematic Map of Interpersonal Quality

This section therefore discusses perceptions of interpersonal quality according to patients, based upon their experiences of hospitals. According to the literature, interpersonal quality is a key factor that determines service perceptions amongst patients. Interpersonal quality is about the behaviour and attitude of staff members in hospitals towards patients. The four major sub themes in relation to interpersonal quality are manners, empathy, responsiveness, and communication. These were the most salient themes identified by respondents during interviews.

The participants identified empathy as a key element of service quality which relates to care and the courtesy of staff towards patients. Empathy is perceived by patients as involving the extent to which medical teams look after the needs of patients and provide services that are appropriate. Some of the respondents remarked upon how caring staff were towards patients and how interested they appeared in taking care of patients. Analysis suggests that empathy is an important factor that relates to patient satisfaction in Nepalese hospitals. Zaim et al. (2010) have confirmed that understanding is a key service quality measure in Turkish hospitals when

it comes to patient satisfaction. Similarly, (Yousapronipaiboon & Johnson, 2013) found that empathy is one of the key dimensions which has a significant influence on patient satisfaction.

Many of the respondents were concerned about empathy and the professional manner of medical staff. Empathy refers to the extent to which medical staff give due care and attention to their patients. Empathetic care, attention and responses are required by all service users. This is why interpersonal quality was one of the most salient themes that emerged from the interviews. Many respondents wanted hospitals to provide patients and their families with affective physical and mental support. In terms of the qualitative findings in relation to empathy, analysis suggests there are varying perceptions. Many of the participants were happy with the empathy that they perceived of from hospital staff, but others were not. *“whenever I visit the hospital, I would love to get a warm welcome by the staff, this will make me feel more welcome and relax” (P10)*. This respondent highlighted the impact of a warm welcome by the organisation on their customers. A warm welcome will give a good sense of influence for the satisfaction of service. From this statement, it is found that patients are emotionally involved when they come for the treatment in the hospital. They want to be taken care emotionally and physically by the medical staff.

The interview data highlight a number of issues relating to empathy. Some respondents complained about a lack of empathy and attention. Some medical staff also confirmed that there is a lack of empathy for patients in the hospitals in which they work. Patients, they suggest are not treated equally, and some are left unattended. Ill treatment and ill-tempered staff performing duties were seen as problematic. Participants experienced rudeness from staff during their stay in hospital. Quality, and effective treatment is essential, but it is also important to give due care and attention to patients in order to deliver quality service. Empathy towards patients should be a priority in order to provide excellent service. Kocher, Emmanuel & Deparle (2010) emphasised the importance of providing high-quality medical care and suggest that it can impact on patient satisfaction. Many studies have highlighted the importance of empathy and service quality. Alghamdi (2014) found that understanding is one of the most positive aspects of customer satisfaction. Another study conducted by Ahmed and Samreen (2011) in Karachi found that empathy was a statistically significant aspect that influences patient satisfaction. Resnick and Griffiths (2011) found that perceptions of service quality can be

enhanced if staff are empathetic towards patients. Nepalese hospitals should therefore provide the right level of care and attention to patients to drive patient satisfaction.

Communication was another of the qualitative themes that emerged around patient services. Communication was perhaps one of the most important factors that influenced the satisfaction of patients in the study. Analysis suggests that patients considered communication central to service provision. Indeed, communication between patients and medical staff can help patients engage with staff, and this means that health problems can be discussed effectively. Based on discussion, staff are also able to advise patients how to make the right choices about treatment. Some studies identify the importance of communication in patient satisfaction and suggest that communication between doctors and patients is key to quality healthcare, and can ensure greater satisfaction amongst patients (Kumar, et al., 2009). (Lehtinen & Lehtinen, 1991) illustrate that communication is about sharing information between provider and customer. This finding suggests that communication is a vital for understanding the needs of patients. Some participants were dissatisfied with the communication they had encountered when dealing with medical staff. Some felt that the conversation was a little one-sided and technical, and some of the communication experiences with doctors had been poor because patients felt they had not been understood. Some patients shared more positive experiences.

“I want the doctor to tell me clearly about the side effects of medicines and how long should I take medicine.” (P22) In this case, the respondent wanted to receive a clear message about the treatment he was going through, and he wanted the information to come from the doctor. Indeed, this was a common observation from within the findings chapter. Communication plays an important role where the aim is to ensure a high-quality health service. Many of the hospitals’ goals involve delivering the best care to patients in order to drive satisfaction, and reduce medical errors (Wang, et al., 2002). Analysis suggests that communication is essential for exchanging information between service providers and receivers, so that both understand each other. In such instances the service provider can understand the situation and requirements of the patient and they can provide the necessary treatment to the full satisfaction of the patient (Wu, et al., 2008). Service providers must let patients know what sort of treatment they should receive and what it costs so that they are clear about the service they are providing. Effective communication between patients and service providers is therefore important and will influence the level of trust that is established between patients and medical staff. It is not

possible to create a healthy relationship with patients in the absence of effective communication (Lehtinen & Lehtinen, 1991). (Pai & Chary, 2016) argue that effective communication between patients and medical employees can influence customer satisfaction in healthcare. Effective communication means that employees have a sound knowledge of the needs of patients, and this will lead to satisfaction.

Similarly, Duggirala et al., (2008) found that friendly and kind behaviour towards patients gives positive trust to customers, which can lead to customer satisfaction. Similarly, some studies view communication as an “an integral ingredient for the success or failure of the organisation” (Murti, et al., 2013) These authors argue that it is important to study communication to drive the success of business. Communication is about articulating the goals, purpose, and outcomes of the organisation to customers (Murti, et al., 2013) and building mutual understanding and trust between stakeholders. Some researchers have shown that poor communication between health care staff and service users can be harmful to service users and can lead to misjudgements and mistakes. Specifically, poor communication can lead to medical errors and can pose a risk to life. Medical errors were the most cited issues in Nepalese hospitals by different participants and in newspapers. Poor communication between medical staff and service users can therefore lead to poor quality services (Subedi, 2019).

Responsiveness in hospitals is about the willingness of hospitals staff to understand patients and provide services promptly to them (Zeithmal, et al., 2009). Some researchers define responsiveness in their study as the non-medical expectations patients have regarding health care (Karami- Tanha & Fallah-Abadi, 2014). Valentine et al., (2015) argue that responsiveness is as key as the environment in which the medical services are provided to patients. Based on this study, it is clear that patients understand and judge the various aspects of services throughout the time they spend in hospital (Altuntas, et al., 2012).

Responsiveness emerged as another key determinant of patient satisfaction in Nepalese hospitals. Indeed, Nepalese healthcare should focus on responsiveness when thinking about the welfare of patients (Wu, et al., 2008). Based upon the interviews, a key dimension that emerged around responsiveness was dignity, as well as the confidentiality of patients. Other aspects included the level of prompt attention received, the physical surroundings, support for patients, and clear communication between patients and medical staff. Some respondents complained about rude behaviour from medical staff. Some staff were unable to provide help when it was

requested, and some were unable to provide help promptly, which meant that patients were kept waiting. One of the respondents compared the attitude of his doctor to a member of army personnel and suggested that they had provided insufficient information about their health condition. Others suggested that medical staff lacked strong communication skills when it came to dealing with patients. A number of participants were satisfied with the basic amenities and surroundings of the hospitals. They were happy specifically with cleaning procedures, and the level of commitment towards cleanliness within hospitals. Others were quite positive about the level of responsiveness in terms of the service they received. Some observed that medical staff were able to provide services promptly, and with empathy. Others were satisfied with the cleanliness of the hospital, and suggested that that staff were very helpful, particularly when communicating with patients. Most felt that, when it came to discussions about their health, that the level of communication was very strong between staff and patients. Other participants praised the performance of staff, and suggested that quality care depends on excellent performance. Therefore, staff should be committed to their duties and tasks in order to deliver quality healthcare. Some patients found that the medical teams were very determined to deliver excellent patient care and carefully engage with patients to understand their health requirements. The performance of staff in hospitals as an important factor in the delivery of quality healthcare since most patients perceive of quality care as something that depends on enthusiastic performance and a committed medical team (Swain & Kar, 2018).

Manary et al., (2013) argue that staff performance towards service delivery influences patient perception of quality service in hospitals. Furthermore, Al-Hawary et al., (2011), in their study of a Jordan based hospital argued that perceived quality service quality is linked with hospital staff performance. This suggests that staff performance is a key factor to measure quality healthcare. A study by Chimed-Ochir, Odgerel, (2011) on responsiveness found that staff members like doctors and nurses should respond immediately to patients and should be ready to help at any time. Waiting times in terms of service delivery should not be long, and this is particularly the case in terms of medicine. When providing services, medical staff should be respectful to patients and should provide them with adequate privacy during treatments. Fulfilling these factors can enhance the delivery of quality service for patient satisfaction.

5.2.3 PERCEPTIONS OF TECHNICAL QUALITY

The technical quality of hospitals was another key theme that emerged, acetamide by the sub-

themes of reliability, responsiveness, expertise, and outcomes. the following diagram (Fig: 14) shows the thematic map of technical quality of the hospitals.

Figure 14 Thematic Map of Technical Quality

Technical quality is strongly and significantly connected to service quality as it refers to the quality of care provided to patients (Dagger, et al., 2007). The respondents viewed reliability as a valuable feature of service quality. This refers to the delivery of service as promised to patients by the service provider (Duggirala, et al., 2008; Hegji & Self, 2009). Where hospitals fail in this regard, patients may not perceive of a quality level of service. The interviews underscore a mixed response to reliability in hospitals. Most respondents saw long waiting times as problematic. One respondent (P23) noted “some time we have to wait for more than 3 hrs to get the check-up done, I think it is very frustrating for all the patient who comes from far place for a check-up, (P23).” To provide service on time, hospitals should focus on decreasing waiting times for patient. Waiting for a long time can make patients anxious, and can affect their perception of service. Reliability in service delivery was also identified as an important factor. Many participants describe excellent service providers as hospitals which provide treatment, diagnostic tests, and other services in an acceptable timeframe. Hospitals should show a sincere interest in solving problems for patients, and should explain what and when they are planning to do with them. Some previous research identifies reliability as a key dimension of service quality for patients (Resnick and Griffiths, 2011; Alrubaiee, 2011; Ahmed and Samreen, 2011). Similarly, Dawi et al., (2016) define reliability as an important factor in health care, reliability is a task carried out by service providers by showing a genuine interest in patients. In hospitals, reliability is about performing the treatment right, first time and maintaining error-free records.

Some participants were satisfied with the service they had received during their time in hospital. Some observed that the hospital provided services on time, as promised, and consultations were undertaken very quickly. One respondent was satisfied that he had received feedback quite quickly on his health. Many of the participants expected service to be provided on time, regardless of the circumstances. The performance of staff was therefore important in terms of providing reliable services to patients. Delivering timely services can satisfy patients, and can lead to future usage.

Expertise was another sub theme which emerged regarding the technical quality of hospitals. Skills were identified in the context of this thesis as the qualifications and capacity of medical staff to provide high standards of services to patients. Some participants noted that doctors and nurses were very qualified and competent, as well as professional. They observed that the medical staff were skilled and accepted that this was an indicator of expertise. There were mixed responses when it came to the knowledge of staff. Some participants complained that under-qualified medical professionals had given incorrect diagnoses which had impacted on their views of service. Inaccurate diagnoses and treatments led to perceptions of poor service. Outcomes were another sub theme which emerged from interviews. This subtheme refers to the results of health services as experienced by patients. Understanding patient perceptions of services is important for various reasons since prioritising patients will mean that they evaluate services positively (Mehta, 2011).

The extent to which patients seek healthcare is directly based on their requirements. These requirements are influenced by physical, financial, access, and reputational issues in relation to services. If it is not possible to look after the needs of patients then they will not perceive of satisfactory services. Mutual trust between provider and receiver is an important indicator of service quality (Berg & Lune, 2011). Kocher, Emanuel & DeParle (2010) argue that providing high-quality care in hospitals and providing good customer satisfaction should be priorities for health care providers. Similarly, Kurtzman, Dawson & Johnson (2008) argue that patient satisfaction with medical care is a key indicator of patient satisfaction, and an important area of improvement in terms of providing better quality services. Respondents had mixed views about the outcomes of the hospital services they had experienced. Some were happy with the service the hospital had provided during their stay in hospital.

On the other hand some respondents complained about medical errors due to unqualified members of staff. Outcomes, as perceived by patients were negative in these cases. Some patients were afraid to use the services of the hospital in future. They felt they had little choice other than to continue with their treatment at the time. In such cases, they felt it necessary to travel, in future, to other countries to receive a better standard of treatment and accepted that this would carry additional cost. Analysis suggests that outcomes in Nepalese hospitals are difficult to define. The overall view is that quality service is an ambition that is not yet a reality for these hospitals. Many participants listed a number of reasons why they thought that the service quality they had encountered in Nepalese hospitals was poor. Poor service quality, according to the participants occurred as a consequence of a lack of equipment, and poor overall management. Some of the patients felt that they could not trust the service that they were receiving in the hospitals, and incidents frequently occurred which eroded their trust. Some patients thought that they had no choice other than to use the services of the hospital that was treating them, despite their reservations about service quality.

5.2.4 PERCEPTION OF TRUST IN HOSPITALS

The trustworthiness of hospitals was another major theme that emerged from the interviews, along with the subthemes of trust, assurance, and patient confidence towards the service provider. A thematic map for trustworthiness appears below (Fig 15).

FIGURE 15 THEMATIC MAP OF TRUSTWORTHINESS

The findings suggest that trust between the service provider and receiver is key to the long term success of business. Respondents provided mixed views as to the confidence they had in hospitals. Some respondents felt it is important for hospitals to build trust so that patients believe in them, and the service they are providing. The finding suggests that medical staff are not trusted as much as they might like to be. Some doctors are not able to commit the amount of time to patients that they are expected to. Some respondents had waited longer for a consultation that they had expected and these lengthy waiting times were due to a lack of staff dedication and punctuality. Some of the respondents were happy with their care. The behaviour, knowledge and skills of clinical staff tend to affect the service they provide, which can shape perceptions (Ahmed, et al., 2017). It is important to exhibit professional behaviours and attitudes towards patients. This not only satisfy them but also assists with customer retention. This research also emphasizes the importance of trust in service quality which was discussed in the literature review in the context of service quality dimensions. Trust is essential for both health care professionals and patients. Various researchers identified a range of reasons that identify trust as a vital indicator of patient satisfaction in health care. Parasuraman (1985) suggested that patients should be able to trust medical service providers, and medical service providers should ensure the service they provide is reliable and safe. Adrutdin et al., (2018) found a relationship between trust and satisfaction and argued that the higher the degree of confidence, the more patients are satisfied with services. Patients are generally more anxious about the type of service they receive. As such medical service providers have to build up trust in consumers in pursuit of patient satisfaction. Trust is a useful indicator of the health of doctor – patient relationships. There are many benefits associated with such a strong relationship including open communication when it comes to medical advice, and better patient perceptions of healthcare. Many organisations have begun to facilitate doctor – patient relationships by introducing patient centric approaches. They have also developed communications strategies and have worked on shared decision-making. In addition they have increased their consultation windows and provided patients with various choices when it comes to clinicians.

Assurance in hospitals refers to the knowledge that medical staff have, and their ability to inspire trust and confidence in patients (Abiodun, 2010). The findings suggest that there are mixed feelings as to the level of assurance provided by medical staff. In a hospital context, assurance refers to the extent to which medical staff are friendly and polite. It is about how

comfortable patients are with using services and how experienced and knowledgeable the management teams within hospitals are. Analysis suggests that many of the participants were comfortable using hospital services. However, some were much more pleased with the dimension of assurance in the context of service quality. Most participants were happy with the support they had received from staff, and they felt cared for when undergoing treatment. Some participants suggested that medical staff were very kind and polite towards them.

A number of researchers have discussed the importance of assurance in previous studies. Shahla Yousefi Dehbidia et al., (2014) identified the importance of assurance in service organisations and the results from that study demonstrate that courtesy and politeness towards patients are high up the agenda of customer satisfaction. Assurance can be useful to identify the gap between service expectations and perceptions of patients as regards the quality of service in hospitals. The interview data suggests that courtesy was an important element for patients who valued interactions and effective teamwork in hospitals. Respondents suggest that these attributes build strong relationships amongst team members and between patients and their families. Many of the patients were happy with the care that they had received in hospital. Caring was a key concern for patients who had spent time in hospital and most are happy with the way that he had been treated by medical staff. They were satisfied that they had received care, sympathy and respect, and so had their families. One of the respondents noted that one particular nurse had been very caring, and had tried to put him at ease by making him feel emotionally comfortable.

(Amin & Nasharuddin, 2013) suggest that patients who are happy and satisfied with services are likely to return in future. Nwankwo et al., (2010) note that, the provision of unsatisfactory service negatively impacts on service perceptions amongst patients. Many of the participants were happy with the treatment they received in hospital and confirmed that the hospital was able to create a sense of trust between staff and patients. They noted that many members of staff were helpful, and provided accurate and sufficient information about treatments. In healthcare facilities, patients expect to come across caring staff who are able to perform. In such a service environment, care is more important than in any other business setting. In hospitals, patients view care as absolutely central to the behaviour of staff, and they value the way that medical professionals interact with them and their families. Chahal & Kumari (2010) state that patients naturally expect love and care from medical staff when they are undergoing

treatment. It is therefore reasonable to assume that past experiences will influence expectations and perceptions of service. It is therefore important to measure the expectations of patients.

Qureshi et al., (2012) found that if the expectations of patients are not met, then dissatisfaction will occur. In addition Geletta (2018) state that taking customer expectations seriously can have a positive effect on customer perceptions. Qureshi et al., (2012) further noted that the service provider should deliver excellent service quality and this is possible if they truly understand customer expectations. Patient confidence is directly related to the development of trust. Trust is the consequence of exceptional service. Patient confidence occurs when there is a feeling of safety within service settings. Safety is, indeed, fundamental to the delivery of quality and essential healthcare. Indeed, every health centre must provide effective and reliable services to patients across the world. Health services must be delivered in a timely manner that is equitable and subject to efficient protocols. Building confidence in patients is important because this will create a culture of trust and security towards the organisation in which patients become emotionally attached. If healthcare providers fail to make customers feel safe and secure, they will feel threatened, and this can have detrimental psychological effects on them. Padma, et al., (2010) consider safety and security to be vital measures of quality in hospitals. . (Duggirala, et al., 2008) also view safety as a service quality dimension. As such, based on the findings in the study there is a need to improve patient confidence, build trust, and create a safe and secure environment which can facilitate patient satisfaction

5.2.5 PERCEPTIONS OF ADMINISTRATIVE PROCEDURE OF THE HOSPITAL

FIGURE 16 THEMATIC MAP OF ADMINISTRATIVE PROCEDURE

Administrative procedures in hospitals are the processes of admission associated with attending for treatment as well as staying and finally being discharged. The findings point to mixed views as regards the administrative policies and procedures of the hospital. It is important that every hospital must have well organized and appropriate processes and systems to provide a better quality of service. Analysis suggests that patients perceived of a range of negative effects in terms of the administrative procedures of the hospitals in the study. The main issues raised by patients include delays to the different stages in the hospital's administrative processes during their stay in hospital. Most respondents experienced delays when it came to admissions, and they were inconvenienced by having to wait for a long time to be admitted. This occurred due to mismanagement within the hospital. Hospitals tend to admit as many patients as they can, rather than allocating time slots and booking appointments to manage footfall. Patients were unable to book appointments with doctors, and on occasions appointments became delayed or even cancelled because some of the doctors, or the resources they use were unavailable. Some participants were unhappy with the lengthy discharge processes, and wanted this to be quicker and more convenient. A number of respondents believe that waiting times were caused as a result of mismanagement in the hospital. Many respondents were critical of time management,

and time management is key to service quality in any hospital setting. Some respondents noted the importance of time, and how it is essential for patients to be treated on time without having to wait for check-ups at OPD, and other sections. A number of patients were unhappy with the medical teams who had caused delays, and these participants expressed dissatisfaction with the disproportionately long waiting times. They suggested that staff should be consistent in providing service. Some respondents complained about overcrowding in the hospital and the consequent neglect of patients by medical clinicians. Some medical staff appeared not to be dedicated to their work, and this created dissatisfaction amongst patients. Some raised the issue of lateness and the late arrival of medical teams at work. This meant that queues developed. In order to create better patient satisfaction, hospitals should provide services on time, based on appointments and based on a simple admissions and discharge process. This will ensure that services meet the needs of patients. If hospitals can provide efficient services to patients through effective administration, then patients will be satisfied and will perceive of a better service offer. Hospitals should therefore standardise their service delivery process to offer patients a convenient experience (Swain & Kar, 2018).

In addition, hospitals should ensure that outpatients and inpatients receive proper care by providing adequate care, thereby building up confidence in the patients that they serve (Kondasani & Panda, 2015). Such hospitals should have a well-defined administrative process which can make hospitalisation as pleasant as possible (Duggirala, et al., 2008). Another study conducted by Pai and Chary (2013) found that hospital administrative procedures mean that admission processes can be lengthy. Zineldin et al., (2011) found in their study that improving administrative processes based on quicker discharge services can enhance the overall evaluation of service quality amongst patients. The finding was supported by one of the respondents in particular. Some studies have found that customer focuses on employee fulfilment can positively impact satisfaction amongst customers. Similarly, Baalbaki et al., (2008) argued that administrative services are core services which can add value for patients who use the service. Atinga, Abekah – Nkrumah & Domfeh (2011) suggested that hospitals should regulate easy administrative procedures to provide satisfaction to patients in terms of service quality.

5.3 SERVICE QUALITY, PATIENT SATISFACTION AND PATIENT PURCHASE INTENTIONS

Perceptions of satisfaction amongst patients were seen as vitally important within this research. Crucially, satisfaction is important in order to assess the level of service that hospitals provide to patients. This study provides some insight into satisfaction and purchase intentions within the health sector of Nepal. Generally, customers who are satisfied with services are more likely to use these services in future and will, in addition, promote them to other customers (Voon et al., 2012). Therefore, hospitals in Nepal must try to understand the needs of patients and provide better services to meet their satisfaction (Neupane & Devkota, 2017). The findings reveal the importance of patient satisfaction and how this can influence purchase intentions. Analysis suggests that satisfaction amongst patients depends on the level of care and service that they receive when in hospital. Most participants pointed to empathy and the care that they had received as vitally important in their assessment of service quality. Only a small number of participants were worried about the physical appearance of the hospital. A number of participants were concerned about the care they have received from nurses and doctors during treatment. Improving patient satisfaction should be a primary goal of any healthcare service provider since the satisfaction of patients can impact on the outcomes of hospitals and can have a bearing on patient retention (Foscht et al., 2009). Communication between patients and service providers was mentioned by a number of participants in the context of patient satisfaction. A number of participants viewed communication as a key factor in forming opinions about service satisfaction. Communication between service providers and receivers helps to identify the needs and expectations of customers (Pai & Chary, 2016).

Many of the participants simply wanted to be listened to by the doctors and nurses. Effective communication makes patients feel valued and cared for, and improves the overall quality of service. Providing important information to patients is key to achieving a positive patient experience (Altuntas, et al., 2012). Listening carefully to patients and providing them with timely information will lift their confidence. Receiving support from doctors and nurses in terms of treatment is important and can work well if clear communication occurs between patient and carer. Many of the participants wanted doctors nurses to communicate clearly with them and many of the nurses and doctors noted that patients were shy and nervous during conversations. In such cases they tried to make them feel comfortable. Empathy and care were some of the most oft-cited themes after communication in the context of patient satisfaction and future purchase intentions. Many of the participants wanted to be treated with care and

respect during their stay in hospital. In terms of providing hospital services, most customers believe that making recommendations to friends and family can occur if the experience has been positive. In such cases patients will be more likely to use the same services again in the future. Word-of-mouth recommendations are one of the key reasons that many participants use hospitals for treatment. The interviews suggest that patient satisfaction is directly linked with the purchase intentions of patients, and this can impact on the outcomes of the hospital (Al-Ekam, 2012). Most participants were unhappy with the level of empathy and care they received from hospital service providers. The gap between the service expectations and service provided by these health services to patients was therefore uncovered. Analysis suggests that patients were very sensitive when presenting for treatment, and expected excellent standards of care and a high trust environment from the service provider. One of the participants was particularly concerned about the reliability of the hospital. As such, empathy, care, the behaviour of staff and the effectiveness of communication reviewed as key factors that drive patient satisfaction. These factors dictate how patients feel about services. Patient satisfaction plays a mediating role between the healthcare service provider and patient loyalty, and future purchase intentions. It also impacts on the rate of patient satisfaction with services and influences the success of healthcare (Al-Ekam, 2012); (Shabbir, et al., 2017). Based on this finding it is clear that patient satisfaction and positive service quality are linked with future patient purchasing intentions.

Indeed, this finding is supported by previous work conducted on the relationship between service quality and satisfaction. Swain and Kar (2018) found that satisfied patients are more likely to make future purchases, and satisfied customer spread positive recommendations or word-of-mouth to other users which can enhance the outlook for hospitals. Similarly, Messala and Paul (2016) found that reliability, trust and responsiveness influence the satisfaction of patients and this has a direct impact on patient loyalty and future service usage Huang et al., (2011). A positive relationship has also been noted between the service quality dimensions and the satisfaction levels of patients.

5.4 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK BASED ON THE FINDINGS RELATING TO SERVICE QUALITY IN NEPALESE HOSPITALS.

This section identifies the conceptual framework which has been developed based upon the major themes and sub themes identified in the findings. The framework is based on the literature review and the conclusions of the study. The framework conceptualises the quality

service of hospitals and identifies the major things that were generated from the data around patient satisfaction and future purchase intentions. The major themes and sub themes that were identified were explained above in the previous section. A key dimension for service quality is selected from the key findings of the study and the major indicators that emerged from interviews are also identified within the model. The literature introduced and discussed the SERVQUAL service quality model which measures service quality. This model is useful for measuring the gap between service expectations and service perceptions, based on five key dimensions. Several researchers have used the model to research healthcare settings and have provided a foundation to conceptualise a newer model based on their findings. Ramsaran - Fowdar (2008) used the SERVQUAL model to measure service quality in private hospitals in Mauritius. Similarly, Rohini and Mahadevappa (2006) applied the model to an Indian hospital. Both authors then modified the SERVQUAL scale to suit the purposes of their studies.

Furthermore, Chahal and Kumari (2010) modified the model to include interaction quality, and physical and outcome quality in order to evaluate service quality. Similarly, Ahmed et al., (2017) used the model in Bangladeshi hospitals to measure services and Murti et al., (2013) used the model to measure the linkages between service quality, behavioural intentions, and customer satisfaction in hospitals. Aagja and Garg (2010) developed a framework named “PUBHOSQUAL”, and Swain and Kar (2018) developed the 6Q framework, referencing the Servqual model. For this study, the SERVQUAL model provides a conceptual background, and enhances the researcher’s understanding of the system. In order to build a conceptual framework for the study, the most salient themes raised by participants have been used to generate a conceptual framework for healthcare services in Nepal. Environmental service quality, communication, empathy and trust were the main dimensions that were mentioned by participants to measure patient satisfaction. Patients also used the same dimensions to measure service quality in hospitals. The findings from this study reveal the most salient determinants of service quality for patient satisfaction and patient purchase intentions. A standard instrument, the “ECET” model has been developed to conceptualise service quality according to patient satisfaction and patient future purchase intentions in Nepalese health care centres. This model can be useful to measure the relationship between service quality, customer satisfaction and purchase intentions in health care industries. The current study investigates the experiences and thoughts of participants in hospitals through their experiential knowledge. Therefore, this study followed a social constructivist (Maxwell, 2013) approach. Previously,

no qualitative research had been carried out in Nepalese hospitals. This is therefore the first study to provide qualitative findings in Nepal. The following diagram (Fig 17) detailed the conceptual frame work “ECET” model and the dimensions of the service quality which was discovered after conducting the qualitative research.

FIGURE 17 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK (THE ECET MODEL)

The ECET framework has been developed bases on the findings from this study. The model is based on the most salient concerns and key indicators around the service quality dimensions. The Servqual dimension of service quality measures the quality of services provided to customers and can assess if they are satisfied or not. The Servqual model was purposed by Parasuraman to measure quality, and his model consists of five key dimensions which can measure customer perceptions of services (Mehta, 2011). According to Parasuraman, the five dimensions of the model (physical, reliable, empathy, assurance, and responsiveness) are the key elements that can help to meet the requirements of patients in hospital. The literature review found that the Servqual model was the most popularly used model amongst numerous

researchers and service organisation. It is useful to measure the service quality dimensions behind customer satisfaction. However, recently more literature has emerged around the Servqual functionality findings (Ladhari, 2010, and Khan, 2010). Some authors have suggested that developing specific scales for measuring service quality could be more appropriate than relying on single improved measures for new cultures (Ladhari,2010; O'cass and Carlson,2011; Ekiz and Bavik,2008). Dabholkar, et al., (2000, p144) support this argument and note that “*Service quality measures across the industries are not feasible. So, future research on service quality should involve the development of the organisation centric model of service quality.*” Some authors have criticised the Servqual model because it has failed to address other key indicators of customer satisfaction in hospitals. In hospitals, strong emotions exist in service encounters which influence perceptions of services amongst patients in all aspects of the setting (Ladhari, 2009). So, it is necessary for hospitals to fulfil the emotional needs of patients. The stronger the emotional experience, the more likely that patients will be satisfied. This study was designed to measure customer satisfaction with Nepalese hospital services through qualitative research. Therefore, the researcher has followed suggestion made by Ladhari (2010) and Ekiz and Bavik (2008), to determine the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction in Nepalese health care sectors.

The ECET model is useful for measuring service quality in Nepalese hospitals, and there are many attributes which the interviews have contributed to it. The most salient characteristics identified were environmental quality, communication, empathy, and trust. These four components were the most frequently cited by patients. Almost all participants believe that the four key elements are the most useful indicators of service quality in hospitals. These elements can help with patient satisfaction. During in-depth interviews with the participants, several variables were discussed by participants which were seen as important when finalising the ECET framework. The four variables which were seen as the most important measures for customer satisfaction in Nepalese hospitals were therefore identified. Patient satisfaction was identified by respondents during in-depth interviews, and their expectations of service were influenced by their personal and past experience of service. They were also influenced by word of mouth recommendations. key concern that patients raised about using hospital facilities related to their health, as well as the outcomes of their treatment which depended upon the quality of the medical staff attending them. Patients were therefore highly motivated to receive the best medical care from the hospitals they attended. In this sense, patient perceptions of service quality can influence their choice of healthcare provider. Hospitals should consider

patient satisfaction as an integral part of their business. There are several reasons why patients might feel more likely to remain loyal to hospitals in the future. These reasons also affect their purchasing tensions. The four components identified in this research were the highest ranked forecasters of quality and patient satisfaction in health centres in Nepal.

The service environment of hospitals was seen as a crucial component within healthcare settings. Hospital environments are the tangible surroundings that are sought through service experiences, and this includes advanced and modern equipment. The participants valued the hospital environment and had high expectations of the quality of services based on this environment. Physical cleanliness and hygiene were also considered important aspects of the physical facilities of hospitals. Participants also valued the appearance of hospitals and sought a clean environment. They wanted to see physical facilities including adequate seating and adequate beds and saw these as key indicators of satisfaction. Many of the respondents wanted the hospitals to have up-to-date equipment and to see well-presented medical staff. Participants also felt that the physical facilities of hospitals had to be visually appealing. Such features can influence perceptions of service quality delivered by hospitals. Analysis suggests that patient satisfaction is directly linked to the physical tangibility of hospitals. Crucial here are the physical environment, the cleanliness, the availability of seating and the standard of equipment. Most of the respondents complained about outdated resources. The physical facilities of hospitals were seen as very important dimensions of patient satisfaction. If hospitals clearly value environmental quality, then patient comfort will be increased in hospitals in Nepal

Communication was viewed as the most important dimension relating to patient satisfaction in the study. Patients were interested in holding meaningful conversations with medical staff. Some perceived of poor communication when it came to interactions with medical staff, and this increased conflict and problems with care. For example misunderstandings and confusion arose around treatment and medical errors were observed. The most commonly cited observation amongst participants was the lack of meaningful communication with doctors and nurses. Some participants were unhappy with the conversations they held with medical staff whilst in hospital. These participants wanted to encounter quality communication. Quality communication means listening carefully to patients and providing meaningful updates in terms of treatments and so forth. Participants wanted medical staff to provide details about their treatment and sought clear explanations about treatment procedures. Many participants suggested improving communication between service providers and receivers as a means to

enhance understanding, which could be beneficial to the overall experience of the service they encountered. Since communication helps patients to engage with staff effectively they feel they can discuss their health issues with medical professionals in confidence.

Similarly, empathy was another important dimension perceived of by patients in hospitals in Nepal. Some of the participants saw empathy as an interaction between service providers and receivers. They identified the emotional care dimension as a form of empathy pointing to quality service. They value emotional care and were concerned about the psychological effects of empathy on their well-being. Many of the participants did not want the service providers to focus only on technical jobs, but to also show empathy and kindness to them. This dimension demonstrates that medical staff can provide emotional support for the needs of patients. Participants saw empathy as an important dimension for patient satisfaction. (Zaim, et al., 2010) also views empathy as an important dimension for the measurement of quality when it comes to patient satisfaction in hospitals. Providing emotional support is key in hospitals and could help to reduce patient vulnerability and anxiety. Patients were happy if the nurses showed an interest in providing quality service.

Trust was another key dimension of service quality and an indicator of patient satisfaction in hospitals in Nepal. Trust between patients and service providers can build security and confidence with hospital services. This can enhance patient satisfaction towards services. Trust is a key measure of consumer behaviour in healthcare. In the healthcare industry, the most trusted companies can successfully influence patients and provide positive health outcomes for them whilst retaining healthy profits for shareholders. Participants wanted hospitals to be patient – orientated, and act in the best interests of patients, rather than prioritising business interests. Participants found that trust is an important factor for patient satisfaction in terms of hospital services. Trust can help develop confidence and can drive usage of services in the future. Some authors also identified trust in previous studies. Chen et al., (2016) argue that trust provides a basis for future collaboration, so it is important to ensure confidence. Padma et al., (2010) argue that when patients trust service providers they will act with goodwill towards them. Trusting patients will deliver positive word-of-mouth about hospital services. Patients that do not trust services may no longer make use of the services of the hospitals that they do not trust. To build trust, hospitals must provide quality services to patients. Better service quality consists of timely service delivery provided by qualified staff. The right

treatment must be provided at the first opportunity with no errors. Up-to-date medical equipment must be provided (Rajguru, 2018).

5.5 SUMMARY

This chapter presented a discussion that outlined the key findings of the study. The five salient themes from the analysis were identified in this chapter. These five themes are the key dimensions of service quality in Nepalese healthcare. Indeed, the five factors were the most salient aspects articulated by participants during interviews. The five themes are: environmental quality, interpersonal quality, technical quality, trustworthiness, and the administrative procedures of the hospital. Based on the interviews these five areas were viewed as the key dimensions that can measure patient satisfaction in eastern Nepalese hospitals. Patient satisfaction was seen as key to measuring the quality of services and the future intentions of patient to use services down the line. Intention to use services in future depends on the extent to which patients are satisfied with services, and whether hospital management were able to meet the expectations of patients or not. Patient satisfaction creates benefits over the long term for hospitals, and presents financial opportunities. The literature and findings point to the idea that patient satisfaction is important for health care providers since it is directly linked to the outcomes of hospitals. The participants agreed that they are influenced to some degree by previous experiences and by word-of-mouth recommendations. Based on the major themes the conceptual framework for service quality that has been developed, the ECET model will help to address customer perceptions of service quality in Nepal's hospitals. The model will help hospitals provide better services to patients. The ECET model focuses on the key indicators of service quality behind patient satisfaction in hospitals in Nepal. Analysis suggests that patients are more satisfied with the care and trust they receive from hospital employees rather than the physical facilities of the hospital. Patients seek care, and empathy when they are attending hospitals for treatment. Patients have high expectations of hospitals in Nepal, and they seek trust and reliability from a service experience in such settings. The ECET model addresses the expectations of consumers towards service quality, and it can provide a better understanding for hospital management when it comes to patient satisfaction. Satisfied patients are more likely to use hospital services in future and to visit the same provider for these. This is particularly the case when trust is established between provider and receiver. Such a high

trust relationship can create beneficial outcomes for hospitals in competitive environments. Satisfied patients will impact positively on the brand image of hospitals.

The next chapter will focus on the key findings and conclusion to the study. This chapter will address some of the managerial implications that have arisen out of the study which might help hospitals create a new strategic plan for better service.

6 CHAPTER SIX CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

6.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter summarises the key findings from the previous chapter and presents a conclusion to the study. The chapter also recommends measures to improve the quality of services in Nepalese hospitals and discusses the key dimensions of service quality that were identified in this study. The researcher addresses the following research questions.

- What are the pivotal elements that measure the quality perceptions of patients in hospitals in Nepal?
- Why is service quality key for health care centres and for customer satisfaction?
- Why higher service quality matters for customer satisfaction and consumer purchase intention?
- How does service quality and customer satisfaction influence consumer purchase intentions in Nepalese hospitals?

6.2 KEY FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

The research was undertaken to identify the key determinants of service quality in hospitals in Nepal and to explore patient satisfaction with service quality and future purchase intentions within that setting. The conceptual chapter on service quality confirmed that it is important for hospitals to understand the expectations and perceptions of patients to provide quality service, and to satisfy patients (Dagger, et al., 2007). Semi structured in-depth interviews were conducted with participants who had experience of service within these hospital settings. The interviews focused on customer perceptions of service quality to identify the key service quality dimensions. The study also evaluated the advantage of patient satisfaction in hospitals when it comes to the retention of patients and the purchasing of services in the future. The findings suggest that providing quality services is important for patient satisfaction in the healthcare industry. Patient satisfaction is important for understanding the behaviours of patients and particularly their propensity to make purchases in future. The study found five major themes which are: environmental quality, interpersonal quality, technical quality, trustworthiness, and the administrative procedures of hospitals. These are key to measuring service quality in hospitals in Nepal. Hospitals are places where care is provided to populations

that is both preventative and curative. Generally, the quality of care in hospitals is measured according to patient perceptions and satisfaction. Patient satisfaction is a feeling of pleasure or disappointment based upon receiving services and according to their prior expectations (Kotler, 2009). Patient satisfaction can be referred to as the emotions and feelings that patients experience when healthcare services have been delivered (Mohan and Saikumar, 2011). In terms of patient satisfaction, it is important to understand the expectations and needs of patients. Understanding patients involves making an effort to empathise with the needs of customers (Parasuraman, Zeithaml & Berry, 2003). This research finds that patient satisfaction increases their willingness to recommend services to others and increases patient retention for the future. The five major themes were identified after carrying out interviews with participants. The study was conducted in two hospitals in the eastern part of Nepal. The semi structured; in-depth questionnaire was prepared based on the literature that was reviewed for the purposes of the study.

This research reveals a major gap between service expectations and the service provided. Most of the participants were unhappy with the services they had received in the hospitals. Many wanted the hospitals to be located in more convenient locations, since a number of them had to travel to attend them. Many patients wanted to see parking spaces introduced. In terms of the physical and technical quality of the hospitals, many participants were dissatisfied with the services and felt that these did not match expectations. In terms of the interviews, various problems with Nepalese hospitals were identified in terms of service provision. It was felt that the environmental quality of hospitals was poor, and the physical environment where service takes place required enhancements. Physical factors such as equipment, bed numbers and the cleanliness of buildings as well as hygiene factors relating to the toilets and bathrooms were raised as concerns by participants. Hygiene at the hospitals, including bed sheets and bathrooms were raised as serious issues by patients. Many complained about cleanliness in the hospitals, and out of date equipment. Most felt that there was a lack of furniture in the waiting rooms. Parasuraman et al., (1988) mentioned that physical facilities, equipment and the appearance of the environment, as well as personnel in hospitals impact significantly on service quality. Ahmed et al., (2017) found that modern looking equipment and appealing facilities are crucial for patient satisfaction.

Analysis suggests that patients had to wait for a long time to be seen by doctors. Such waiting times and queuing made patients frustrated. Another major dissatisfaction was the lack of attention paid to patients by doctors and medical staff to patients. Clinicians were unavailable when needed. There was little clarity provided to patients in terms of their illnesses and treatment. Some participants were even concerned about the distance they had to travel to receive treatment. Some 40% of the participants that took part in the study had to travel more than 60 miles for treatments. Some patients were concerned about the care they had received, and analysis suggests that perceptions of services amongst patients fell short of expectations. The key issue was poor communication between service providers and users, and this had resulted in errors and a breakdown and understanding between patients and hospital staff. Poor communication raised issues around patient safety and impacted on the confidence of service users. These, together impacted negatively on the satisfaction of patients with services.

6.2.1 CONCLUSION: THE ECET MODEL

The ECET model is the key outcome of this study. The model conceptualises this study of service quality in Nepalese hospitals.

To identify patient satisfaction, it is important to identify the expectations, needs and perceptions of services by patients. Customer expectations of service quality are linked with their past experiences with service encounters (Parasuraman, et al., 1994). Patient satisfaction is the feeling that results after comparing the performance of a service with prior perceptions (Kotler,2009). Patient satisfaction reflects the patient's perceptions of service and expectations of the service they received. Patient satisfaction drives trust and loyalty towards service providers (Kamra et al., 2016). Some of the literature has conceptualised hospital service quality as consisting of environmental, technical, interpersonal, and administrative quality (Brady and Cronin, 2001; Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry 2003). Service quality in hospitals is measured in terms of environmental facilities as well as technical and interpersonal quality, and administrative procedures (Dagger et al.,2007). In this sense, Dagger et al., (2007) support the findings in this study. This study finds that patients measure service quality according to physical facilities, technical quality, and the personal and administrative procedures of the hospital. The ECET model supports the dimensions of service quality as a means to measure satisfaction.

This study finds that the satisfaction of customers depends on their expectations. It also depends on the perceptions that patients have of services. In terms of the ECET model, environmental quality refers to the physical surroundings of hospital facilities. In addition, communication empathy and trust refer to the physiological needs of patients. The study finds that patients have varied perceptions of the four service quality elements of the ECET model. Analysis suggests that patients that have used services previously have higher expectations than those who are new to the service.

6.2.2 CONTRIBUTION TO THEORY

Service quality has become a topic of great interest in healthcare settings due to the development of modern techniques and facilities. Standards of living have improved in recent years and people are increasingly focused on their health and quality lifestyles. This has led to an increased demand for medical services and better treatment. As such, to provide better services and to drive the quality of services patients receive it has become important for healthcare organizations to focus on patient satisfaction and retention (Alhashem et al., 2011; Arsali et al., 2008). Various authors have researched service quality since the 1980s (Parasuraman, et al., 1988. Zeithmal, et al., 2009). The focus of the study was to investigate the perceived quality of service amongst patients. The study focuses on customer perceptions and the behaviours of customers. The literature that was reviewed discussed the concept of service quality as well as customer satisfaction and the future purchase intentions of customers.

Based on the literature, service quality is a comparison of customer expectations of service and their perceptions of service after it has been provided (Parasuraman, Zeithaml & Berry, 2003). This is an important driver of customer satisfaction and future purchase intentions (Sudin, 2011). A number of studies from the past have investigated the relationship between service quality and satisfaction in different industries such as in Internet banking (Ramseook – Munnurrun & Naidoo, 2011), retailing (Voss, Godfrey & Seiders, 2010), and healthcare (Duggirala, et al., 2008).

Duggirala et al., (2008a) carried out research in developing countries to measure service quality in hospitals. They concluded that hospitals consist of seven key dimensions “(personnel quality, physical condition, the process of the clinical care, administrative procedures, the

process of clinical care, safety, and social responsibility)” to measure service quality. Another researcher developed five dimensional measures to measure service quality in hospitals and termed this model PubHosQual (Aagja & Garg, 2010) . To date, service quality has been evaluated in various ways by a number of researchers. Some researchers evaluated service quality based on disconfirmation theory which measures the gap between expectations and perceptions of services. Others have applied performance measures to evaluate service quality (Carr, 2007; Parasuraman et al.,1988, 2005; Foscht et al.,2009). The literature review section provides a deep understanding of service quality and the models that are used in various sectors to measure performance. Gap analysis provides a more realistic approach to measure service perceptions and expectations amongst customers in health care. If the expectation of the customer is higher than their perception of service, it can be considered lower or negative because of this higher expectation. In studies conducted in developing countries, almost all researchers have used the Servqual model to measure service quality in the health industries except Duggirala et al., (2008) who incorporated new dimensions. These include trust and clinical processes to measure service quality. The Servqual model was first used by Brown and Swartz (1989) in the health care sector to measure gaps in customer satisfaction. Soon afterwards, several authors like Jabnoun & Chaker (2003), Sohail (2003), Herstein & Gamliel (2006) used the model to measure the expectations and perceptions of patients and hospital management. Therefore, the Servqual Model was chosen as a suitable conceptual model for this particular study. Some researchers modified the Servqual model to develop a new framework. Pai and Chary (2016) modified and modelled a nine-dimensional construct (Healthscope, trust, Clinical care, communication, personal, image, personalisation, relationship, and administrative procedures) to show the relationship between service quality, patient satisfaction and buying behavioural intentions. Similarly, Swain and Kar (2018) conceptualised the 6Q framework (technical, procedural, personnel skills, physical facilities, social care and support, and communication) with reference to Servqual to measure service quality and patient satisfaction in hospitals. Similarly, Chahal and Kumari (2010) added interaction quality, physical quality, and outcome quality to the model to measure the overall quality and outcomes of the hospital. Therefore, the researcher has followed the Servqual model as a conceptual model to develop the conceptual “ECET” model as a result of this study.

Hospital service quality perceptions amongst patients in hospitals in Nepal are based on experiences and judgments in relation to the services that are provided. These include the

physical facilities, the doctors, the relationships between clinicians and patients, and the strength of communication. Service quality was measured by patient satisfaction. Chahal and Kumari (2010) argue that patient perceptions are based in three dimensions in healthcare which are environment quality, interaction quality and outcome quality. Arasli et al., (2005) found that service quality can be measured using six dimensions that accord with service perceptions. Based on this, the interpersonal connection between patients and medical staff has the greatest impact on service quality perceptions. Strong relationships are important for service quality and the relationship between service users and providers is principally impacted by the technical and functional aspects of hospitals (Brady, et al., 2002).

This research suggests that perceptions of service quality are also based on previous experiences, and patient satisfaction is influenced by their understanding of service. However it is challenging for service users to predict the service quality stages that relate to hospitals, since hospitals are complex, and are subject to several measurement dimensions when it comes to service quality. A number of authors have highlighted that it is difficult for patients to judge technical medical service quality as they lack the requisite knowledge and skills (Duggirala, et al., 2008). As such, the evaluation of the quality of hospitals is mainly based on the functional quality dimensions, such as cleanliness, physical facilities and emotional qualities such as empathy, care, respect, reliability and interactions with doctors and nurses. The study finds that communication between patients and medical staff drives confidence in patients (Fatima, et al., 2018). Patient satisfaction in healthcare can be regarded as an outcome of care and is one of the major factors that drives service outcomes. Patient satisfaction and healthcare reflects the expectations, needs and experiences of patients when it comes to service (Padma, et al., 2010).

Communication is another superior quality required of hospitals. Several studies have examined the importance of communication for better service interactions (Swain & Kar, 2018). Outcomes in terms of health services depend on the communication between medical staffs and patients. In providing effective communication, medical staff are more likely to influence patient satisfaction. Better and effective communication can help medical staffs to understand the needs of the patients, which can help deliver better service outcomes.

6.3 MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

Service providers around the world struggle to find appropriate methods that fit with their organisations to improve the quality of services, because better quality leads to enhanced customer satisfaction and purchase intentions. With the growth of competition in healthcare, it is important to improve service quality to drive customer satisfaction and repurchase intentions. This study has shed light on a number of managerial implications. The findings provide management with information which can guide them towards understanding customers and appreciating how to offer excellent service to deliver patient satisfaction and customer retention in competitive markets. Service quality in hospitals was assessed by exploring patient perceptions of experiences of hospitals. The majority of participants were not happy with the service they received, and they also mentioned that many aspects needed to be improved to provide better services. The dimensions which affect the quality of service in hospitals are tangible facilities, patient safety, responsiveness, empathy, care, trust and communication. Patients were concerned with the quality of technical and interpersonal service in hospitals. The ECET model conceptualised the service quality dimensions as perceived by patients in Nepalese hospitals. For this study, two major hospitals from the eastern part of Nepal were chosen by the researcher. The research was designed to investigate perceptions of service quality in Nepalese hospitals and the impact of these on patient satisfaction and repurchase intentions. The perceived quality of service was conceptualised using the ECET framework because patients were more aware of tangible elements, including communication, and emotions. As such, to ensure the satisfaction of patients, it was suggested that if hospitals perceive that performance is matched to customers' expectations then customers tend to be satisfied. The opposite also holds true (Geletta, 2018; Zeithmal and Bitner, 2003). Where customer repurchase intentions depend on the behaviours of customers after the service is perceived, customers tend not to use services again (Ladhari, 2009; Zeithmal et al., 2009). The study shows that patient satisfaction and quality service have a significant connection in Nepalese hospitals. To provide satisfaction to patients, the hospital must establish a higher level of service quality. The four dimensions in the ECET framework are important factors in evaluating customer satisfaction in hospitals in Nepal.

Based on the qualitative findings patients are of the opinion that Nepalese hospitals have poor levels of environmental quality. The physical facilities, cleanliness, and the atmosphere of these hospitals, together with the availability of modern equipment were criticised. Also criticised were ambulance and pharmacy services, and these are seen as key towards patient satisfaction. Respondents suggested that environmental quality was below average in hospitals

in Nepal. Previous studies have discussed the importance of physical facilities in the service industry and healthcare. Raj guru (2018) discussed physical facilities and features and suggested these are key elements that drive patient satisfaction. Many respondents in the study rated the convenience of the location of hospitals, as well as the appearance of buildings and cleanliness as key dimensions of service quality.

Similarly Parasuraman et al., (1985) used the SERVQUAL model to measure service quality using tangibility as an indicator of physical facilities and their impact on service quality. Zhang et al., (2016) suggested that tangibles are the key indicators of service quality in a study conducted in a Chinese public hospital. Previous studies by various authors have corroborated this finding. The respondents complained about outdated equipment, and suggested improvements should be made to hospital management practices. They further suggested that outdated equipment should be replaced. Some older technologies may no longer provide accurate data or results. Analysis suggests that some physical facilities like beds and chairs in OPD waiting rooms are insufficient and so patients have to sit on the floors of waiting rooms, and some have to wait longer than expected to be allocated to a bed. The cleanliness of buildings and toilets were also concerns that were raised by participants. Hospital management must focus on the cleanliness of buildings and must focus on cleaning the toilets inside the hospital wards. If these areas are dirty then patients may be at risk of infection and disease. Indeed, the smell of these facilities makes hospitalisation highly unpleasant.

As a consequence, all of these environmental issues harm patient perceptions of service quality. As such, hospitals must effect improvements in these areas in order to tackle the issues. This might help hospitals improve the efficiency and effectiveness of their service quality. Improving the outlook of hospitals by providing up-to-date equipment and by cleaning should be a priority to improve the overall quality of these hospitals.

Communication in the service industry is another major dimension that drives service quality. Communication between medical staff and participants was a key dimension that was identified in the study which impacts on service quality. This study, in particular focuses on poor communication between patients and medical staff and suggest that this can lead to errors and poor service quality (Subedi, 2019). Many of the participants wanted to experience open and friendly communication with medical staff to discuss their health. Unfortunately, many of the

patients were critical of communications, and a number of them noted that they had not received efficient and timely information about their health, and their families had not been included in discussions. Patients wanted to experience more effective communication from doctors and nurses about care plans. They felt that effective communication was lacking overall. Many suggested that, because of the lack of communication and coordination between staff, their safety in hospital had been compromised. As such, poor communication can risk the safety of patients. Other interpersonal qualities like empathy and trust were also criticised by patients. Thus, to improve the connection between medical staff and patients, health centres must develop a framework for effective communication and interactions between patients and medical staff. Based on the findings of this research the following recommendations are proposed to improve service quality and patient satisfaction in Nepalese hospitals:

- Hospital management should urgently effect physical changes in hospitals, like updating old equipment, focussing on cleanliness, and supplying seating and beds. This will improve the efficiency and effectiveness of service.
- For effective communication, the hospital needs to introduce customer service training and communication skills training for employees to address their professional skills. Indeed, professional skills training builds skills like communication, and the ability to assess patients' needs and perceptions. This can help set priorities for quality improvements to patient satisfaction. Conducting effective communication avoids errors and misunderstandings.
- Health care managers should consider service quality and patient satisfaction as important strategic objectives, and these should be measure regularly so that quality can be monitored to effect improvements if necessary. Evaluating service quality can provide better outcomes to customers/patients.
- Managers should set and apply quality goals to improve the quality and safety of patients .
- Managers should commit to understanding employee motivation which is a key indicator of the achievement of organisational goals.
- Managers should introduce a rewards system for hardworking employees which will motivate them to perform.

- The hospital should introduce a standard policy and guidelines for quality improvement initiatives. Hospital administrative staff, and other professional staffs should be informed about the importance of qualitative initiatives
- The hospitals should introduce personalized and individualized treating systems for patients.
- Hospital management should introduce a survey system to measure patient perceptions and expectations after service has been delivered. This can help to monitor the quality of services and improve services using a patient-centric medical care.

6.4 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

This research examined the relationship between service quality, customer satisfaction and purchasing intentions in hospitals in Nepal. In terms of the research limitations, the study was conducted within a restricted timeframe as the researcher had to travel to Nepal to gather data. There was only a limited time to do this. The study was carried out in two hospitals in the eastern part of Nepal. As such, the findings cannot be generalised to all hospital in Nepal. The two hospitals included in the study were in the same city. It might have been better to include a hospital, or hospitals within another district or city to diversify the findings.

In terms of hospitals in Nepal, there are more quantitative findings available than qualitative. As such, this research is limited because of the availability of prior research in this specific area. No previous studies that had looked at hospitals in Nepal were accessed. The researcher could therefore not learn from prior studies in this area. In addition, it was not possible to cover larger areas given the scope of the study, because of the limited timeframe and the availability of previous research. A major issue in Nepal is transportation, and so it was challenging to reach both of the hospitals. Furthermore the interviews were undertaken in the Nepali language, and later transcribed into English. There was therefore some risk that the meaning from the original language could have been lost. However the researcher attempted to capture all of the information accurately by studying the interview records carefully. This took more time than expected.

6.5 SUGGESTIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

Service quality in hospitals is a broad subject. There are many opportunities within healthcare service provision to carry out future research in different developing countries. This research was conducted to measure service quality and patient satisfaction based on the services provided in hospitals in Nepal. The research focused chiefly on the service quality dimension rather than perceived service quality. The latter aspect could be examined in future. There are many other areas of service quality, and patient comfort which might make for interesting future studies. This research was carried out in one city in Nepal, and only on participants from the two hospitals identified. In future, researchers could study different districts and hospitals to compare the findings. It might also be interesting to conduct the study in more hospitals in other cities.

Furthermore, this research does not take account of the views of management and other non-medical staff who are important aspects of service delivery in hospitals. In addition, this research does not take account of the views of hospital managers who are perhaps one of the most important stakeholders in terms of developing hospital strategies. They provide guidance and create policies in hospitals. In this sense, taking on board the views of other staff that are involved in healthcare delivery could provide a broader overview of the issues in relation to services in hospital

6.6 SUMMARY

This chapter presented a conclusion to the study and produced some recommendations. The chapter identifies the theoretical contribution to service quality literature in the context of hospitals. Furthermore, this chapter discussed the managerial implications of the findings and provided some suggestions that can be implemented in hospitals to improve service.

This study attempted to investigate and evaluate the relationship between service quality and patient satisfaction with implications for their future intentions to use services in Nepalese hospitals. Patient satisfaction was a key factor for hospitals, and there are implications for the financial statuses of the hospitals that were studied. As such, the healthcare sector in Nepal should focus their resources on improving service quality to drive customer retention. The study also indicates that improving the quality of services will result in greater patient satisfaction. Service quality has become a key factor in hospitals for service users. Patients depend on hospitals for treatment and to have their needs met. Quality health services are crucial for the survival of human beings. As such, customers are serious about the types of

healthcare services they receive. The basic expectations of patients in any hospital is to receive efficient treatment and care. Patient satisfaction has a major impact on the image of hospitals, and their performance. The reputation and brand image of hospitals are key factors for the success of businesses over the long term.

To drive patient satisfaction, hospital managers must follow strategies which can help them to measure services. Moreover, this chapter presented some of the limitations to the study. For example the research was conducted in Nepal, and travelling was a key limitation. Finally, the chapter proposed future research in other areas that are tangential to the study which could take place in future. The study focused only on eastern hospitals in Nepal and so the results cannot be generalised to other hospitals in Nepal. Future researchers could examine other areas in Nepal to make comparisons with the findings of this study.

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8 Appendix 1: Ethical Approval letter From University

01/02/2018

Dear Sangita Karki Dholi,

Your application 2146: Relationship between the service quality, customer satisfaction and customer purchase intention in Nepalese health care centres., submission 1812, has been approved by the Business and Enterprise SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr A Kourouklis

9 Appendix 2 : Invitation letter to the hospital.

Respected, Medical Superintendent Sir,

My name is Sangita Karki Dholi. I am a DBA (Doctor in Business Administration) research student from The University of the West of Scotland, United Kingdom. I am conducting research as a part of my thesis submission and my research topic is “the relationship between service quality, customer satisfaction and consumer purchase intentions in Nepalese health care centres”. The main aim of this research is to identify the quality of care in health services in the hospitals of Nepal, and issues relating to patient satisfaction.

I am inviting you to take part in the project. I am hereby seeking your consent to conduct research in your hospital for the purposes of this study. I will be interviewing patients that use your services, or have already used it, and staff within the hospital. The goal of this study is to determine the level of service quality and patient satisfaction.

The data will be collected using semi-structured questionnaires along with in-depth interviews. To complete a questionnaire, it may take around 15 – 20 minutes, and interviews may last 30 – 45 minutes. The conversation, with your permission will be tape recorded. The data and recordings will be stored securely and only the researcher will have access. Participants will remain anonymous in reports, and the information that is recorded will be deleted at the end of the project. Furthermore, I would like to assure you that ethical principles will be maintained throughout the study.

You should not feel coerced. Agreeing to be the part of research is completely voluntary. You may withdraw at any time, and information will be managed confidentially. If you decide not to take part, your health care, or job will not be affected in any way. If you decide to take part, you will be asked to give your consent before any activities take place. You will be invited to sign the consent form if you agree to take part, and a copy of signed consent form will be given to you.

Thank you for taking time to read this information and I hope you will be able to participate in this research. Please do not hesitate to contact me.

Kind regards

Sangita Karki Dholi

Phone no: [REDACTED]

Email: [REDACTED]

10 Appendix 3: Invitation Letter for Participants

Dear participant,

I am DBA student currently studying at the University of the West of Scotland, United Kingdom currently. I'm conducting research as a part of a thesis submission and my research topic is "The Relationship between Service quality, Customer satisfaction and Consumer purchase intentions in Nepalese health care centres."

The main aim of this research is to study the quality of health services in the hospitals of Nepal and to identify the major issues for patient satisfaction. I would like to invite you to participate in this academic study by filling this questionnaire. This questionnaire is designed to obtain data from participants regarding their service experience in hospitals. The main purpose of this questionnaire is to measure the quality of service provided in the hospitals of Nepal and to measure the customer satisfaction.

All responses will be treated confidentially, and the results of the survey will be used for research purpose only no names are required. As a participant, you are free not to participate in answer the questionnaire and have rights to withdraw at any point. I would greatly appreciate if you can take some time to answer these questions. This will assist me in my thesis.

Best Regards

Sangita Karki Dholi

Doctoral Researcher

The University of the West of Scotland

London, United Kingdom

11 Appendix 4 : Participant Consent Form

Name of Researcher:

Title of Research:

Please read and answer this form by ticking the appropriate response.

- 1) I have read the information sheet provided by the researcher for this study and have had the research satisfactorily explained to me.
Yes No
- 2) I understand the answers will be used for research purpose only.
Yes No
- 3) I understand all the information given to me will be treated confidentially.
Yes No
- 4) I understand that I'm free to withdraw from the study at any time without giving any reason to withdraw and my participation is voluntary.
Yes No

Participant's signature:Date:

Participant's Name:

Researcher's Name:

Researcher's signature:

12 Appendix 5: Semi-Structured Research interview questions

SEMI – STRUCTURE QUESTIONNAIRES AND IN-DEPTH INTERVIEW

This questionnaire will help the researcher to find out the patient's satisfaction with the quality health care in hospitals of Nepal. I wish to assure you that this is for academic purpose only and strictly be used for academic purpose only.

1. Age (*please tick* [√])
 - 18-30
 - 31-45
 - 46-60
 - 61 and above
2. Gender (*please tick* [√])
 - Male
 - Female
3. Marital status (*please tick* [√])
 - Married
 - Unmarried
 - Widow
4. Education (*please tick* [√])
 - lower secondary
 - Secondary
 - Higher Secondary
 - University
 - None
5. Occupation (*please tick* [√])
 - Agriculture
 - Service
 - Business
 - Households

- Labour
- Other (please specify) _____

6. Place of Residence:

7. Average monthly income of your family (*please tick* [√])

- Less than Rs10,000
- Rs10,000 – Rs20,000
- Rs20,000 – Rs30,000
- Rs30,000 and above

8. Nationality (*please tick* [√])

- Nepalese
- Indian

9. Number of visits to the hospital in the past 12 months.....

10. Can you tell me a little about your visit in this hospital? How do you get here?.....

11. Who do you currently talk to about your health condition? Do they listen to you? Do you think they understand you?.....

12. From the time, you arrived at the hospital did you feel you have to wait long time to get admission and check-up?.....

13. Do you have any problems getting the treatments you are looking for? Can you share some of the problems?.....

14. Can you tell me about some of your good and bad experience in this? hospital?.....

IN-DEPTH INTERVIEW OVERVIEW

The interview aims to find out the quality of healthcare provided in the hospital of Nepal with regards to patient's satisfaction. I wish to assure you that this is for the academic purpose only and assured of absolute confidentiality and anonymity. Please respond to the questions in this interview.

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Age.....

Gender.....

Nationality:

Qualification.....

Occupation/Post.....

SERVICE QUALITY DIMENSIONS

- 1) In your view, what are the main facilities and services that a hospital should offer to the patients?
- 2) What are your general views and thoughts about the health care centres in Nepal?
- 3) Does the hospital provide employees and patients with up-to-date facilities, clean environment, and technology?
- 4) Is service provided by the hospital are superior quality, cheaper and convenient?
- 5) Does the hospital provide ambulance service if yes how satisfied are you with the service?
- 6) Is the service provided by hospital reliable?
- 7) What is the level of quality of service provided by the hospital?
- 8) Does the hospital provide the service as per the expectation of patients?
- 9) Is the service affordable? Why? How?
- 10) What drives people to travel another country to receive treatment?
- 11) Does management of hospital correctly understand expectation of patients towards the service?
- 12) How will you rate overall health care quality provided by the hospital?

13) Is there anything else you would like to tell us about the quality of service provided by the hospital?

14) Can you give any suggestion to improve health care quality at the hospital?

SERVICE QUALITY MEASUREMENT QUESNTIONAIRE

Statements	Yes	No
1. Hospital cleanliness and hygiene is excellent.		
2. Hospital has up to date equipment and technology.		
3. Hospital has availability of adequate seating for the patients.		
4. Hospital rooms have comfortable bed and furniture.		
5. Bathroom and toilets are clean in hospital.		
6. The hospital has an adequate number of doctor and nurses.		
7. The staffs of the hospital are friendly and supportive.		
8. Services are provided by staff on time.		
9. I find easy to discuss things with the staff of the hospital.		

10. Doctors are friendly and supportive.		
11. Doctors appropriately discussed my previous conditions.		
12. Medical treatments were performed correctly at the first time.		
13. Doctors give enough time to examine patients.		
14. Doctors explain about your problems and treatment what they are going to do.		
15. Drugs in a pharmacy of the hospital are easily available.		
16. Hospital keep patients records accurately.		
17. The charges of hospital are accurate.		
18. Prompt service are provided by staff of the hospital for admission and discharge process.		
19. Staffs are always willing to help you in hospital.		
20. The hospital has skilled staff to provide service.		
21. The hospital staff treats patients with respect.		

22. The staff understand my problem and needs at the hospital.		
23. The staff at the hospital was caring towards you.		
24. Staffs provide adequate explanation of any tests you had to undergo.		
25. Staffs gives you special attention.		
26. I received adequate information on my health condition.		
27. I am satisfied with the service delivered in this hospital.		
28. I was given sufficient information on my treatment.		
29. I will visit this hospital in future.		
30. I will recommend other people to visit this hospital.		

13 Appendix 7: Hospital Approval Letter

Personal details withheld.

Personal details withheld.

